

HORIZON-CL5-2022-D4-02-03 – GA 101123175

User-centric and data-driven retrofitting solutions for a
resilient, energy-efficient, low-emission and inclusive cultural heritage

D 2.1. Study of multi-level barriers

Document Information	
Due Date:	30/04/2024
Actual Submission Date:	10/11/2025
Type of Deliverable (Report/Data/DEC/Ethics):	Report
Dissemination Level (Public/Sensitive)	Public
Prepared By:	Iuliia Kozlova, Angelo Massafra, Angela Santangelo, Elisa Conticelli, UNIBO
Version:	v.2.0

Disclaimer

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Summary

The deliverable reports the output of Task 2.1

The D2.1 – Study of Multi-level Barriers outlines an intricate exploration into the multifaceted obstacles that hinder the effective implementation of energy efficiency to heritage buildings. This deliverable encompasses a detailed description of the barriers identified through the research, segmented into technical, legal, economic, environmental and social categories. The investigation delves also into the mapping and analysis of relevant policies, highlighting the disparities and congruences between EU-level strategies and local implementations.

Table of contents

1.	Executive summary.....	6
2.	Planned criteria	7
3.	Behavioral Change for Energy Efficiency in Cultural Heritage Buildings	9
4.	Multi-level Analysis of Barriers to Energy Efficiency in Heritage Buildings	14
4.1	Methodology of the analysis	14
4.2	Theoretical Framework for Barriers Analysis	16
4.2.1	<i>Technical barriers.....</i>	19
4.2.2	<i>Legislative and regulatory barriers</i>	24
4.2.3	<i>Economic barriers</i>	28
4.2.4	<i>Environmental barriers</i>	34
4.2.5	<i>Social barriers</i>	37
4.3	Representation of the results from the survey	41
4.3.1	<i>Estonia</i>	54
4.3.2	<i>Italy</i>	60
4.3.3	<i>Portugal</i>	64
4.3.4	<i>Spain</i>	69
5.	Policy Framework of Energy Efficiency of Heritage Buildings	75
5.1	Methodology of the analysis	75
5.2	European Policy Instruments.....	76
5.2.1	<i>European Directives</i>	77
5.2.1	<i>European Green Deal</i>	81
5.2.2	<i>European Frameworks</i>	82
5.2.3	<i>European Strategies.....</i>	83
5.2.4	<i>European Standards and Guidelines.....</i>	84
5.2.5	<i>Financial instruments.....</i>	85
5.3	National, regional, and local policy instruments	87
5.3.1	<i>Estonia</i>	87
5.3.2	<i>Italy</i>	93
5.3.1	<i>Portugal</i>	98
5.3.2	<i>Spain</i>	103
6.	Good Practices.....	108
7.	Conclusion	113
8.	References.....	114
9.	Annexes.....	123

List of figures

Figure 1: Galtung's conflict triangle model (1969).....	11
Figure 2: Mapping the Interaction Between Policy Instruments and Barriers to Energy Efficiency in Heritage Buildings	12
Figure 3: Levels of analysis	15
Figure 4: Profiles of responders	41
Figure 5: Representation of collected results	43
Figure 6: Relevance of barriers to general context	45
Figure 7: Barrier Sensitivity Index for Principal Stakeholders	46
Figure 8: The Landscape of Challenges in Energy Planning Phases.....	48
Figure 9: The role of stakeholders as Catalysts in Overcoming Barriers.....	50
Figure 10: Problem tree (general context).....	51
Figure 11: Barrier prioritization in Estonia	54
Figure 12: Barrier Exposure Analysis Across Energy Planning Phases and Stakeholder Groups (Estonia).....	55
Figure 13: Problem Tree (Estonia).....	57
Figure 14: Barrier prioritization in Italy	60
Figure 15: Barrier Exposure Analysis Across Energy Planning Phases and Stakeholder Groups (Italy)	61
Figure 16: Problem tree (Italy)	63
Figure 17: Barrier prioritization in Portugal	64
Figure 18: Barrier Exposure Analysis Across Energy Planning Phases and Stakeholder Groups (Portugal).....	65
Figure 19: Problem tree (Portugal).....	67
Figure 17: Synthesis of barrier analysis in Spain	69
Figure 21: Barrier Exposure Analysis Across Energy Planning Phases and Stakeholder Groups (Spain)	70
Figure 22: Problem tree (Spain)	73
Figure 23: Synthesis of policy mapping in Estonia	89
Figure 24: Integrating results of policy mapping in problem tree (Estonia)	92
Figure 25: Synthesis of policy mapping in Italy	94
Figure 22: Integrating results of policy mapping in problem tree (Italy)	97
Figure 23: Synthesis of policy mapping in Portugal.....	99
Figure 24: Integrating results of policy mapping in problem tree (Portugal)	102
Figure 25: Synthesis of policy mapping in Spain	104
Figure 26: Integrating results of policy mapping in problem tree (Spain)	107

List of tables

Table 1 - Classification of Barriers in Scientific Research	18
Table 2 – Integrated results (General context)	51
Table 3 - Integrated results (Estonia)	56
Table 4 - Integrated results (Italy)	62
Table 5 - Integrated results (Portugal)	66
Table 6 - Integrated results (Spain)	71

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

CO ₂	Carbone dioxide
EE	Energy Efficiency
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IEA	International Energy Agency
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Building
RE	Renewable Energy
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
ZEB	Zero Energy Building

1. Executive summary

Globally, energy efficiency (EE) stands as a crucial component of sustainable and low-carbon energy systems, aligning with the United Nations' 2030 agenda for sustainable development and the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Notably, SDG 7 aims to double the global rate of improvement in EE by 2030, emphasizing its role in ensuring universal access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy sources. EE encompasses various sectors, including transportation, industry, and existing buildings. As attention turns towards enhancing EE policies and retrofitting existing buildings, it is important to recognize the significance of historic buildings. These structures constitute more than a quarter of all buildings globally, with over 40% of homes in Europe. However, achieving EE in heritage buildings presents a multifaceted challenge, intertwined with concerns such as historical preservation, regulatory constraints, and financial limitations. The New European Bauhaus, among several EU initiatives, underscores the importance of cultural heritage in sustainable development, promoting adaptive reuse and circular economy principles. To address the EE needs of heritage buildings, a systemic approach is essential, as energy behavior in the context of enhancing the EE of heritage buildings is a multifaceted domain influenced by both barriers and policy frameworks.

Bridging the gap between the challenges of improving EE in historic buildings and the strategies required for their sustainable preservation necessitates a nuanced understanding of both the obstacles and opportunities present in this field. By acknowledging the intrinsic value of historic buildings not just as relics of the past but as active participants in achieving today's sustainability goals, we pave the way for innovative solutions that respect historical integrity while embracing modern energy standards. Thus, the need for a systemic approach that balances EE with heritage preservation becomes a cornerstone for developing effective policy measures.

This report aims to shed light on such a balanced approach, offering a framework that encompasses both the behavioral and regulatory aspects of energy renovations in historic buildings, thereby setting the stage for a discussion on how decision-makers can leverage these insights to enact policies that are both effective in energy conservation and respectful of our cultural heritage. The insights gained from this deliverable could empower decision-makers to consider a wide range of criteria in their decision-making processes, ensuring that measures to unlock energy-saving potential are holistic and effective. Moreover, recognizing energy behavior as a key factor in the success of strategies for building renovation integrated into existing policy instruments further enhances the relevance and importance of this analysis in fostering sustainable preservation practices for cultural heritage buildings.

2. Planned criteria

The Herit4ages project stands at the forefront of integrating multidisciplinary solutions to enhance the sustainability and EE of cultural heritage buildings, aiming to strike a balance between preserving cultural values and improving energy consumption, comfort, and carbon emissions reduction. Herit4ages is set to offer a suite of solutions that can be employed individually or in combination, catering to the dual objectives of cultural heritage preservation and EE enhancement. Within the framework of the Herit4ages project, this report stands as a critical deliverable, focusing on the mapping and analysis of policies relevant to EE both at the EU level and locally, while also identifying the multi-level barriers—ranging from social to financial—that impede the adoption of energy-saving measures in historic buildings.

The study embarked on several objectives. Firstly, it sought to delve into the barriers hindering EE in historic buildings and understand stakeholders' prioritization of these barriers. This involved conducting a comprehensive literature review, which drew from recent academic research and grey literature published by heritage organizations and policymakers globally. In addition to academic sources, insights were gathered from 54 experts representing various stakeholder groups. Collaboratively, they provided information and prioritized barriers to EE retrofits in historic buildings, bridging the gap between theoretical insights and practical applications.

Secondly, the study aimed to scrutinize how EE is currently addressed in European legislation and across four EU Member States—Portugal, Estonia, Italy, and Spain as demonstration site countries. This investigation aimed to assess the visibility of EE considerations in the legislative frameworks of these countries concerning heritage buildings. The synthesis of these findings culminated in problem tree maps, which offered a visual representation of the challenges and gaps identified in the existing regulatory landscape. Ultimately, the study also compiled a list of good practices that could be applied in reply to identified barriers to EE retrofitting for historic buildings. However, it is imperative to recognize that the knowledge amassed in this report, albeit extensive, does not offer a complete panorama of the intricacies related to EE in cultural heritage buildings. Instead, the report is envisioned as an observatory tool, poised to support Herit4ages pilot sites in implementing their project activities by providing a foundational understanding of the policy landscape and identifying critical barriers to enhancing EE.

To compile this report, the University of Bologna (UNIBO) led the effort, working in close collaboration with project partners such as Institute of Baltic Studies (IBS), Camara Municipal Do Funchal (CMF), Fundacion Santa Maria La Real Del Patrimonio Historico (FSMLR) and exercising co-creation effort with the network of local stakeholders from various sectors. This work is closely related to other activities within the Herit4ages project,

especially the governance mechanisms mapping (Task 3.1) and the knowledge transfer to stakeholders (Task 3.3). The insights gained from this analysis will also support the integration of building renovation strategies in Task 9.4, addressing the key role of energy behavior in the success of these strategies.

3. Behavioral Change for Energy Efficiency in Cultural Heritage Buildings

Enhancing EE in cultural heritage buildings represents a pivotal challenge at the intersection of sustainability, cultural preservation, and occupant behavior. Lidelöw et al. (2019) emphasized that EE measures in heritage buildings require a careful balance between improving energy performance and conserving the buildings' cultural heritage values, highlighting the need for transparent and knowledge-sharing best practices to manage this complex relationship. Galiano-Garrigós et al. (2019) emphasized the complexity of balancing EE upgrades with the conservation of historic buildings, suggesting that regulatory frameworks may not always support the best outcomes for heritage preservation. Conticelli et al. (2017) accentuate the need for broader solutions to urban EE challenges, particularly in historic centers where strict preservation rules often limit the feasibility and affordability of extensive energy renovations. Filippi (2015) highlights the challenges of retrofitting within the constraints of preserving cultural heritage, stressing the necessity for a specific design approach that respects the building's historical value. As well as Mazzarella (2015) points out the gap between the preservation of architectural heritage and energy retrofit needs. Therefore, these challenges necessitate a multifaceted approach to understand and address the various factors influencing energy use within these historically and architecturally significant structures.

The concept of energy behavior is crucial for achieving the overall EE of buildings (Santangelo e Tondelli, 2017). It encompasses not just the patterns of energy use but also the decision-making processes that influence the adoption of energy-efficient practices within structures. Behavioural insights can improve understanding of what drives energy-related decisions. In the context of heritage buildings, understanding energy behavior is especially crucial due to the unique challenges these buildings present, including their historical significance, architectural constraints, and often outdated energy systems. Recent academic literature emphasizes that understanding and optimizing energy use patterns in such buildings can lead to significant energy savings, reduced GHG emissions, and the sustainable preservation of our cultural heritage and that energy behavior not only influences the direct consumption of energy but also affects the effectiveness of any retrofitting measures aimed at improving EE. For instance, Akande et al. (2015) discussed the challenges and strategies for enhancing EE in public heritage buildings, underscoring that successful projects integrate energy management into their daily operational practices to achieve better outcomes in both heritage and energy conservation. Sáez-Pérez et al. (2023) conducted a comparative analysis of the thermal behavior in heritage buildings across different seasons, emphasizing the importance of improving energy performance for energy reduction while preserving heritage values. Broström et al. (2020) highlight the importance of integrating behavioral analyses with technical solutions to optimize energy conservation strategies in heritage buildings, while Galvin (2014) argues for a deeper

understanding of occupants' energy use patterns as a foundation for developing more effective and sustainable EE interventions. Research performed by Hu et al. (2020) underscores the importance of integrating occupant behavior into energy policy to effectively reduce consumption and emissions, highlighting the need for technical innovation, digitalization, and a fair consideration of EE and behavioral change. Berg et al. (2017) suggest that research should an interdisciplinary, bottom-up approach to energy refurbishment in historic buildings, emphasizing that users and residents should play a central role in the decision-making process.

Various analytical methods can scrutinize the determinants of energy behavior, shedding light on how to boost EE in heritage buildings. This enhancement is deeply interconnected with occupant behavior, the structure of policy frameworks, and the identification and surmounting of existing obstacles. Lutzenhiser (1992) suggests that energy consumption is intertwined with cultural processes, where material culture combines with conventional understandings and beliefs into the cultural practices of groups. Recognizing the influence of energy cultures is essential for developing interventions that are not only technically feasible but also culturally sensitive and adaptable. The study by Stephenson et al. (2010) introduces the "Energy Cultures" framework, which aims to understand the factors influencing energy consumption behavior. This framework suggests that energy behavior is influenced by the interactions between cognitive norms (beliefs and values about energy use), energy practices (the actual energy-related actions people take), and material culture (the physical objects and infrastructure that enable or constrain energy use). This comprehensive approach to studying energy behavior highlights the complexity of factors that drive energy use and provides a basis for identifying opportunities for behavior change towards greater EE.

Another tool, the Galtung's conflict triangle model (1969), offers a valuable lens through which the energy behavior in cultural heritage buildings could be examined, aiming to dissect the complex relationship between observable energy behaviors and the underlying latent factors, including assumptions and contextual influences, that shape these behaviors (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1: GALTUNG'S CONFLICT TRIANGLE MODEL (1969)

One vertex of the triangle, context, encompasses the environmental, social, political, and economic frameworks that surround energy behavior in cultural heritage buildings. The context includes existing policy measures, regulatory environments, and incentives that either facilitate or impede the adoption of energy-efficient practices. Attitudes, corresponding to another vertex of the triangle, comprise the beliefs and perceptions towards EE, which can significantly influence decision-making processes. These attitudes are shaped by various factors, including cultural values, knowledge about EE, and personal or collective experiences with heritage buildings. Therefore, analyzing the policy framework provides insights into how external factors, such as legislation, funding mechanisms, and public awareness campaigns, shape the possibilities for EE improvements within the heritage sector. This analysis reveals the need for holistic policy measures that address the identified barriers comprehensively, thereby enabling more sustainable energy behaviors. Barrier analysis can be employed to systematically identify and understand the obstacles to applying EE solutions to heritage buildings.

FIGURE 2: MAPPING THE INTERACTION BETWEEN POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND BARRIERS TO ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN HERITAGE BUILDINGS

The importance of conducting both barrier and policy framework analyses stems from their capacity to reveal the latent factors affecting decision-making in energy retrofitting of cultural heritage buildings. As we can see on Figure 1, all three vertexes of the triangle are interconnected. Moreover, the interplay between energy behavior and policy frameworks shapes decisions towards energy-efficient practices, underscoring the importance of a systemic approach to fostering sustainable energy use in heritage buildings and represents both Top-Down and Bottom-Up approaches (Figure 2). The interconnection between EE barriers and the EE policy framework is a dynamic relationship where policies are designed to overcome existing barriers, yet these barriers can also hinder the effectiveness of policies. This dynamic interplay emphasizes the need for policies to be adaptable and responsive to the evolving landscape of barriers, ensuring that EE efforts are not only conceptualized but are also practical and achievable.

In the following sections, this research undertakes an in-depth exploration of the multifaceted barriers to EE within cultural heritage buildings, alongside a thorough mapping of the pertinent policy framework for the pilot sites of Herit4ages project (Estonia, Italy, Portugal and Spain). They will explore the complex interplay of challenges and opportunities

related to sustainable energy practices in the context of heritage preservation. By engaging in a holistic examination that considers multi-level governance—from EU directives down to national, regional, and local policy instruments—this analysis aims to furnish a comprehensive backdrop that underpins the governance mechanisms mapping and facilitates the transfer of knowledge to stakeholders. This scrutiny is pivotal, as it empowers decision-makers to incorporate a broad spectrum of social, legal, environmental, technical, and financial criteria into their deliberations on implementing measures to unleash the energy-saving potential of buildings. Moreover, by recognizing energy behavior as a crucial element for the success of strategies aimed at integrating buildings renovation within existing policy instruments, this analysis accentuates the importance of fostering synergy between EE initiatives and the conservation of cultural heritage.

4. Multi-level Analysis of Barriers to Energy Efficiency in Heritage Buildings

The quest for EE in cultural heritage buildings presents a unique set of challenges, primarily due to the multifaceted nature of barriers that span social, legal, environmental, technical, and financial domains. Recognizing the complexity of these barriers necessitates a comprehensive analysis that not only identifies but also categorizes them based on their impact and origin. The multi-level governance framework serves as the backbone of our analysis, offering a lens through which the interplay between different levels of governance and their influence on EE in heritage buildings can be understood. This framework facilitates the examination of barriers not just in isolation but as part of a complex system influenced by policies, stakeholders, and historical values at the local, national, and EU levels. A semi-systematic review of existing literature is presented. This approach allows for the identification of recurring themes and barriers, which were then classified into distinct groups. The methodology emphasizes the integration of qualitative data from various sources, ensuring a robust foundation for the analysis. To validate the findings and refine the understanding of identified barriers, a selected group of experts from within and outside the Herit4ages projects was consulted. This panel, representing a diverse range of stakeholders, provides insights into the practical implications, significance, and strategies to overcome these barriers. Building on the performed analysis, subsequent sections delve deeper into the nuances of identified barrier group, stakeholders and each pilot site. This exploration does not only highlight the intricacies of each barrier but also could propose a set of actionable recommendations aimed at mitigating their impact.

4.1 Methodology of the analysis

The primary objective was to develop a comprehensive taxonomy of the most significant barriers to EE in cultural heritage buildings. This involved a rigorous theoretical analysis, described in the previous section, resulted by the hypothesis of barrier taxonomy (Annex 1), which was then analyzed and validated through a survey.

The research employed a small group survey methodology, targeting stakeholders using a structured questionnaire that included both open-ended and evaluative questions, employing the Likert scale for ranking purposes. The survey was disseminated within the Herit4ages project consortium, with particular emphasis on countries hosting Herit4ages pilot sites. It leveraged the network of local experts to gather insights from stakeholders identified as relevant to the project. To determine eligibility, consent criteria were applied.

FIGURE 3: LEVELS OF ANALYSIS

The analysis developed across various structured phases, closely aligned with the contents discussed below, and which are represented in Figure 3:

- **Theoretical Level:** This foundational layer includes outcomes derived from comprehensive desktop research and a thorough review of relevant literature. It established a solid academic groundwork for understanding the barriers within the scope of the study. This corresponds to the analysis conducted in Section 4.2, which delves into the theoretical framework through a comprehensive review of literature.
- **Contextual level:** This layer offers a broad synthesis of the collective feedback, presenting an aggregated perspective that reflects general sentiments and observations. This level aimed to capture the overarching themes and patterns emerging from the data, providing a macroscopic view of the barriers identified across all respondents. Reflecting the general results of the review, discussed in Section 4.3, this layer provides an overview of collective feedback, presenting aggregated perspectives to capture overarching themes and patterns emerging from the data.
- **Country level:** Focuses on the nuanced feedback from specific individuals who represented the stakeholder groups associated with the pilot sites. This focused approach allowed for a deeper understanding of the barriers as experienced in distinct geographical and cultural contexts, highlighting the unique challenges and considerations pertinent to each pilot site. Subsections 4.3.1 to 4.3.4 present the results of surveys conducted with stakeholders from pilot site countries (Estonia, Italy, Portugal, Spain). It highlights unique challenges and considerations pertinent to each pilot site, allowing for a deeper understanding of barriers within distinct geographical and cultural contexts.
- **Factor level:** It delves into the discrete components that collectively contribute to the perception and reality of the barriers. This granular examination dissected the complex interplay of factors at work, enabling a detailed exploration of the individual elements that hinder progress towards EE and other targeted outcomes. This level involves the analysis of prioritized barriers, focusing on selected criteria such as the impact on

exposed stakeholders, presence in different phases of energy planning, and the roles stakeholders play in managing these barriers as enablers, mitigators, or change agents. These analyses are presented in Subsections 4.3.1 to 4.3.4 and are visually represented in problem tree tables.

This approach facilitated a multi-dimensional understanding of the barriers to EE, potentially affecting targeted interventions.

4.2 Theoretical Framework for Barriers Analysis

The concept of the EE gap, also known as the energy paradox, refers to the discrepancy between the potential for cost-effective EE measures and the extent to which these measures are actually implemented (Hirst and Brown, 1990; Jaffe and Stavins, 1994; Sorrell et al., 2004; Thollander et al., 2010). Despite the availability of technologies that could significantly reduce energy consumption at a low cost, there remains a substantial portion of this potential that is untapped. Instead, the standalone technological improvements do not fully encapsulate the wicked nature of EE problems (Thollander et al., 2019). This gap is attributed to a variety of barriers that inhibit the adoption of EE measures, especially in contexts such as heritage buildings where the problem is particularly pronounced. Sorrell defined as a postulated mechanism that inhibits investments in technologies that are both energy-efficient and economically efficient (Sorrell et al., 2004).

Successful EE initiatives necessitate the active engagement and collaboration of various stakeholders, who play a pivotal role in the complex ecosystem of EE renovation. This ecosystem highlights the critical need for a nuanced understanding of the roles and interconnections among stakeholders.

The European Environment Agency (EEA) proposed¹ a categorization of stakeholders designed to reflect their specific roles and interests, while also acknowledging potential overlaps and interdependencies among these groups. For the purposes of this report, the classification by the European Environment Agency has been slightly adjusted to more accurately describe the main actors involved in the concept of retrofitting heritage buildings.

Therefore, the classification of stakeholders, as presented in this report, plays a crucial role in understanding and addressing barriers to energy efficiency (EE). This classification, outlined below, serves as a foundational framework for mapping stakeholders and their relation to identified barriers:

¹ European Environment Agency, "Accelerating the Energy Efficiency Renovation of Residential Buildings — A Behavioural Approach," Briefing no. 14/2023, 29 Jun. 2023. Available: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/accelerating-the-energy-efficiency>

- Heritage owners,
- Heritage occupants,
- Building management operators,
- Advisory intermediaries,
- Installers/contractors,
- Suppliers,
- Advisory bodies,
- Regulators,
- and Financiers.

This comprehensive categorization ensures that all relevant parties involved in the initiative are accounted for, facilitating a clearer understanding of their roles and contributions. Specifically, this classification directly correlates with the subsequent phases of the analysis, particularly in the identification and mapping of barriers. Throughout the report, this stakeholder classification is utilized in various contexts, including the survey analysis described in Section 4.3 and the mapping of results in the problem tree tables found in subsections 4.3.1-4.3.4. Additionally, the same classification will be employed for mapping the policy framework in Section 5.3, ensuring consistency and coherence across different analytical dimensions.

The framework provided by Caputo and Pasetti (2015) is adaptable to the unique challenges of improving EE in heritage buildings. It offers a structured approach to navigating the complexities associated with retrofitting efforts. This phased approach is invaluable for systematically addressing the barriers to EE in such buildings, providing a roadmap to achieve sustainable outcomes. This phased EE approach is crucial for systematically tackling the multifaceted challenges of enhancing EE, especially within heritage buildings, where the need for sensitive retrofitting solutions is paramount.

According to their framework there are four stages in planning energy retrofit:

Phase I: Preparation and Orientation, underscores the necessity of becoming aware of energy problems and setting clear goals for improvement. This initial phase is vital for establishing a solid foundation for subsequent actions, ensuring that the efforts to enhance EE are guided by well-defined objectives and an acute understanding of the local energy landscape.

Phase II: Model Design and Detailed Analysis, involves the collection of data and the possession of technical knowledge. This phase is critical for identifying the specific needs and opportunities for EE improvements within heritage buildings, considering their unique characteristics and constraints.

Phase III: Prioritization and Decision, the framework emphasizes the importance of prioritizing actions based on the analysis and making informed decisions on the most effective interventions. This phase ensures that the resources are allocated efficiently, and

the interventions chosen are likely to yield the highest benefits in terms of energy savings and preservation of heritage values.

Phase IV: Implementation and Monitoring, focuses on the practical aspects of executing the planned interventions and monitoring their performance. This final phase is crucial for realizing the EE improvements and ensuring that the interventions achieve the desired outcomes, including the preservation of the heritage buildings' historical and cultural values.

This framework is particularly relevant to the analysis of barriers to EE in heritage buildings based on investigation of energy behavior due to its comprehensive and structured approach. It can address not only the technical and financial aspects but also considers the social, regulatory, and historical dimensions that are particularly pertinent in the context of heritage buildings. This methodical approach will be further used for analysis for analyzing inertia and ensures that energy retrofit projects meet.

The problem of EE is multifaceted and requires an interdisciplinary approach to effectively address the barriers. These barriers are deeply rooted in various theoretical frameworks, encompassing mainstream economics, organizational economics, and behavioral theories (Thollander et al., 2010) By categorizing barriers into different regimes, the research suggests that policy interventions and solutions should be tailored to the specific nature of the barriers. This approach not only facilitates a deeper understanding of the barriers but also opens up new avenues for creative and effective policymaking and implementation strategies to overcome the EE gap.

Research has systematically classified the barriers to retrofitting initiatives for improving EE of historic buildings into two broad categories: technical, that often relate to the preservation and maintenance of the historical integrity of building, and non-technical, may include social, economic, and regulatory challenges that hinder the adoption of energy-efficient technologies. In the Table 1 provided an overview of selected examples of barrier taxonomy proposed in literature.

TABLE 1 - CLASSIFICATION OF BARRIERS IN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Source	Year	Proposed categories of barriers
Hirst and Brown	1990	Structural Barriers and Behavioral Barriers
Howarth and Andersson	1993	Demand-Side Barriers and Supply-Side Barriers
Weber	1997	Institutional barriers, Market barriers, Organisational barriers, Behavioural barriers
Sorrell et al.	2004	Economic Barriers, Behavioral Barriers, Organizational Barriers
Nagesha and Balachandra	2006	Awareness and Information Barrier, Financial and Economic Barrier, Structural and Institutional Barrier, Policy and Regulatory Barrier, Behavioural and Personal Barrier

Gillingham	2009	Market Barriers and Market Failures, Behavioral Failures, Information Problems, Principal-Agent Problems, Capital Market Failures, Innovation Market Failures
Schleich	2009	Imperfect Information, Hidden Costs, Risk and Uncertainty, Access to Capital, Split Incentives and Appropriability, Bounded Rationality
Thollander et al.	2010	Economic Barriers, Behavioral Barriers, Organizational Barriers
Tuominen et al.	2012	Regulatory Barriers, Barriers Related to Organizations and Decision Making, Financial Barriers, Barriers Related to Information, Promotion, and Education
Ástmarsson et al.	2013	Economic Barriers and Informational Barriers
Cagno et al.	2013	External Barriers and Internal Barriers
Zhang and Wang	2013	Legal barriers, Administrative barriers, Financial barriers, Market barriers, Social barriers, Other barriers
Trianni	2014	Economic Barriers, Information-related Barriers, Organizational Barriers, Behavioural Barriers, Competence-related Barriers, Technology-related Barriers, Awareness Barriers
Şahin et al.	2015	Technical Barriers, Financial Barriers, Regulatory Barriers, Informational/Behavioral Barriers
Dixon-O'Mara and Ryan	2017	Economic Barriers, Organizational Barriers, Informational Barriers, Behavioral Barriers
Paiho and Ahvenniemi	2017	Social Barriers, Economic Barriers, Regulatory Barriers
Zuhaib et al.	2017	Technical, Environmental, Industrial, Legislative, Social, Economic
D'Oca et al.	2018	Technical Barriers, Financial Barriers, Social Barriers
Kaveh et al.	2018	Legal and Political Influences, Economic Influences, Technical Influences, Social Influences
Kangas et al.	2018	Economic Market Failures, Economic Market Barriers, Behavioural Barriers, Organisational Barriers, Institutional Barriers
Alam et al.	2019	Financial Barriers, Knowledge Barriers, Administrative Barriers, Social Barriers
Herrera-Avellanosa et al.	2019	Social Viability, Economic Viability, Technical Viability
Palm and Bryngelson	2023	Financial Barriers, Lack of Regulations, Lack of Knowledge and Information, Conservatism of the Industry, Technological Barriers
Lucchi	2023	Technical Barriers, Economic Barriers, Policy Barriers, Information Barriers

Drawing from the insights provided, this report categorizes the barriers to EE in heritage buildings into five main groups: Technical Barriers, Legislative and Regulatory Barriers, Economic Barriers, Environmental Barriers, and Social Barriers (refer to Annex 1 for detailed categorization). The subsequent sections offer comprehensive explanations of each barrier, elucidating their distinct characteristics and the challenges they pose to the EE renovation of heritage buildings.

4.2.1 Technical barriers

The endeavor to enhance EE in cultural heritage buildings is fraught with complex technical challenges. These challenges not only stem from the intrinsic characteristics and conservation requirements of such buildings but also from the technological and material

solutions available for retrofitting. In exploring the complex issue of technical barriers in the adoption of new technologies for historic buildings, several key challenges emerge, requiring nuanced understanding and innovative solutions. These challenges are:

Competence-Dependent Technology Complexity and Skilled Workforce Shortage:

The integration of energy-efficient technologies into heritage buildings presents significant challenges due to the complexity of such technologies and the shortage of skilled professionals. Competence-Dependent Technology Complexity refers to the challenge of integrating modern EE technologies into heritage buildings without compromising their historical integrity. Heritage buildings often require bespoke solutions that can seamlessly blend with their unique architectural features. This demands a high level of technical competence in both the understanding of historical construction techniques and the latest energy-efficient technologies. Skilled Workforce Shortage exacerbates the situation by limiting the availability of professionals who possess the unique blend of skills required for this task. The shortage of skilled craftsmen and engineers who understand both the historic fabric of these buildings and modern EE requirements is a significant hurdle. This gap in skilled labor not only slows down the renovation process but can also lead to suboptimal implementations of energy-efficient technologies, ultimately affecting the performance and sustainability goals. The demand for professionals who are adept in traditional building crafts and in the application of cutting-edge energy solutions appropriate for heritage buildings, far exceeds the supply, leading to delays and increased costs in retrofitting heritage buildings for better EE.

Recent research has highlighted importance of this barrier. D’Oca et al. (2018) in their study highlight a pronounced lack of skilled workers and insufficient training among construction professionals as significant hurdles. This shortage of expertise directly impacts the ability to undertake complex renovation projects, underscoring a gap in the necessary competence or skills for such specialized tasks. This complexity is compounded by the need to consider the architectural value and historical significance of these buildings, requiring bespoke strategies that balance EE with heritage conservation. Fouseki et al. (2020) discuss the importance of a workforce capable of navigating this delicate balance, underlining the advanced technical knowledge required for modern energy solutions in the context of preserving cultural heritage. This complexity necessitates an important level of technical competence, echoing findings by Pino (2018) and others about the challenges inherent in selecting and applying appropriate strategies for the energy retrofitting of heritage sites. The need for skilled professionals capable of navigating these complexities is critical, as is the challenge of ensuring that those tasked with such renovations are adequately trained and confident in their ability to deliver effective solutions. Furthermore, the scarcity of professionals skilled in both modern energy solutions and historical preservation amplifies the challenge. Nair, Verde, and Olofsson (2022) highlight the dual requirement for competency in cutting-edge energy solutions and in-depth knowledge about heritage

conservation. This necessitates specialized training programs and interdisciplinary collaboration to bridge the gap between EE technologies and heritage conservation principles, underscoring the need to overcome competence-dependent technology complexity and skilled workforce shortage for the sustainable future of heritage buildings. The research by Glew et al. (2017) identifies a gap in competence among installers, pointing out that many installation failures are attributed to non-compliance with guidelines. This calls for stricter enforcement of standards and a fundamental change in installer practices to ensure retrofit quality. Similarly, Buda et al. (2021) discuss the decision-making complexity in retrofit processes, driven by the diverse values of owners and building professionals. This complexity, linked to a notable lack of expertise among professionals, introduces challenges in coordination and decision-making, emphasizing the need for tailored solutions that consider the peculiarities of historic buildings.

The competence-dependent technology complexity and skilled workforce shortage significantly impact the energy retrofit of heritage buildings. The specialized knowledge required for integrating sustainable energy solutions in such buildings, coupled with the need for a skilled workforce that understands both EE and historical preservation, presents a critical barrier.

Structural constraints and Complexity in Conservation-Compatible Retrofit Solutions:

The challenge of retrofitting heritage buildings for improved EE encompasses a wide range of structural constraints and complexities that necessitate conservation-compatible solutions. Historic buildings are repositories of cultural, architectural, and historical value, necessitating a delicate balance between preservation and modernization. The inherent structural constraints of these buildings often limit the extent to which contemporary EE measures can be applied without compromising their integrity.

Structural constraints in historic buildings often include limitations on altering the building's fabric due to its historical, architectural, and cultural value. This includes restrictions on adding external insulation, changing windows, or installing modern heating and ventilation systems that could visually or materially alter the building's character. The complexity of retrofit solutions emerges from the need to balance EE improvements with conservation values, ensuring that retrofitting does not compromise the building's heritage value. This involves a careful selection of materials and technologies that are compatible with the historic fabric, as well as methodologies that respect the building's original construction techniques and aesthetic qualities (Nair, Verde and Olofsson, 2022). Furthermore, the challenges extend to the design phase of refurbishment projects for historical buildings, described as problematic due to artistic and architectural constraints that complicate the application of envelope refurbishment measures (Vallati et al., 2023). The inherent characteristics of heritage buildings necessitate substantial retrofit actions to improve EE, potentially leading to prohibitive capital costs. The challenge is further amplified by the

diverse building typologies, constructed before the introduction of current regulations on energy consumption, demanding tailored retrofit solutions for each building (Pereira et al., 2021; Franco and Mauri, 2024; Buda et al., 2021).

Another pivotal aspect is the space constraints and design limitations when implementing systems in existing structures, where retrofitting actions must contend with pre-existing conditions, such as inadequate insulation and the architectural heritage of the building. Designers must navigate space constraints, existing equipment requirements, and the building's original design, limiting the scope of potential EE improvements (Pereira et al., 2021). These conditions often result in prohibitive costs and reduced design flexibility, particularly in urban contexts where space for technical installations is limited.

Structural constraints and the complexity of conservation-compatible retrofit solutions present significant barriers to EE in heritage buildings. Addressing these challenges requires an integrated and adaptable evaluation method that supports a holistic approach to retrofitting, ensuring not only enhanced EE but also the preservation of the building's integrity, heritage values, and sustainability.

Demand for Costly and Scarce Heritage-Compatible Materials:

The pursuit of EE in historical buildings encounters a notable barrier in the demand for costly and scarce heritage-compatible materials. This obstacle is rooted in the specific requirements for materials that not only meet contemporary EE standards but also comply with the conservation criteria for historical structures. Such materials must preserve the architectural integrity and aesthetic value of these buildings, while providing improved thermal performance. The scarcity or high cost of these specialized materials stem from their unique properties and the limited number of suppliers capable of producing them to the required specifications.

Buda et al. (2021) shed light on the unique retrofitting considerations for historic structures, which rely on locally sourced materials and age-old construction methods designed to provide natural lighting, ventilation, and thermal comfort through traditional techniques. This dependency underscores the challenge of integrating modern EE solutions without undermining the inherent architectural and cultural value of historical buildings. This, in turn, suggests that the demand for costly and scarce heritage-compatible materials is an inherent barrier to improving the EE of historical buildings, even if not directly stated (Grazulino, 2020).

The significance of material compatibility in the context of historical buildings is emphasized by Lucchi (2023), who presents "Material compatibility" as a critical criterion for preserving the heritage values of buildings while enhancing their EE. This focus aligns with the broader goal of maintaining the "material culture" of a specific period and territory without

compromising its heritage values. Gireesh Nair, Leo Verde, and Thomas Olofsson (2022) also highlighted the importance of selecting retrofit materials that are compatible with the original building materials in terms of mechanical, physical, and chemical properties. This challenge is emblematic of the broader difficulty in finding materials that do not detract from a building's historical integrity while striving for EE. Litti et al. (2013) note that while the improvement of the building envelope is a common strategy to reduce energy demand and enhance indoor thermal quality, the choice of retrofit materials often prioritizes high thermal performance and cost-effectiveness over compatibility with original materials. This approach risks long-term damage to traditional materials, despite its short-term energy-saving benefits.

The demand for heritage-compatible materials presents a significant barrier to the energy retrofitting of historical buildings. The literature collectively articulates the need for a careful balance between conserving historical integrity and achieving EE goals, pointing to the necessity of selecting appropriate materials that respect the building's original character while contributing to sustainable energy use. This discussion encapsulates the inherent complexities and challenges involved in retrofitting historical buildings for EE, underscoring the scarcity and high cost of suitable materials as a pivotal constraint.

No One-Fits-All Solutions

The pursuit of EE in historical buildings is confronted with the fundamental challenge that there exists no universal solution applicable to all structures. This complexity is rooted in the unique characteristics of each building, including its architectural style, construction materials, historical significance, and the climatic conditions of its location. Such diversity demands customized approaches to energy retrofitting that respect the building's heritage while striving for sustainability. Various studies emphasize the importance of customized approaches, multidisciplinary collaboration, and innovative methodologies to navigate this complexity.

Historical buildings, constructed with traditional techniques and materials, diverge markedly from modern structures, complicating the application of standard retrofitting solutions. This complexity is compounded by the diverse range of historical buildings, including residential homes, public monuments, and religious buildings, each presenting its unique retrofitting challenges (Gireesh Nair, Leo Verde, and Thomas Olofsson, 2022). The heterogeneity of these buildings means that strategies effective in one context may be inappropriate or even detrimental in another, necessitating a multi-criteria decision-making process to evaluate potential retrofitting solutions against various factors including heritage significance and energy impact (Kyritsi et al., 2023). This approach ensures that retrofitting measures not only reduce energy consumption but are also compatible with the preservation of the building's heritage values. D'Oca et al. (2018) identify a critical barrier to deep renovation efforts in Europe—the lack of a one-size-fits-all solution. This suggests the

complexity of implementing innovative technologies in renovation projects. Besides, they argue for a holistic approach integrating technical, financial, and social strategies to overcome the myriad barriers to deep renovation. This perspective acknowledges the need for context-specific strategies that consider the unique challenges and opportunities of each renovation project. Rispoli and Organ (2019) further elucidate the barrier posed by the absence of a universal solution in retrofitting historic buildings. The research underscores the need for a case-by-case assessment to develop less invasive, reversible, and compatible retrofitting measures that do not detract from the building's heritage value.

The absence of a one-fits-all solution necessitates a careful balance between conservation principles and modern EE standards, requiring multidisciplinary expertise to devise solutions that are both effective and sensitive to the building's historical context. This bespoke approach to enhancing EE underscores the need for innovative, adaptable strategies that can accommodate the wide variability inherent in historical buildings, thereby posing a significant barrier to straightforward implementation of energy conservation measures.

4.2.2 Legislative and regulatory barriers

The legislative and regulatory frameworks that govern the retrofitting of heritage buildings with energy-efficient technologies play a pivotal role in shaping the success of such endeavors. However, these frameworks often act as significant barriers to EE, primarily due to their complexity, rigidity, and the intricate balance they seek to maintain between preserving cultural heritage and promoting sustainability. Heritage buildings, by their nature, require a sensitive approach that respects their historical value and architectural integrity. Yet, the existing legislative and regulatory environments can impose stringent restrictions that limit the scope of permissible interventions for EE improvements. The complexity of navigating these legislative and regulatory landscapes often leads to increased costs, prolonged project timelines, and, in some cases, the complete abandonment of EE initiatives. These challenges could be described as following:

Lack of policy coherence and protocol deficiency:

Enhancing EE in heritage buildings is not only a technical challenge but also a policy issue. The lack of coherent policies that guide the adaptive reuse of heritage buildings for EE leads to a fragmented approach, where individual projects may pursue sustainability goals without a unified framework or standards. This absence of policy coherence can result in missed opportunities for maximizing EE gains across the heritage building sector (Yazdani Mehr and Wilkinson, 2018).

Lack of policy coherence refers to the disjointedness and inconsistencies within the legal system that hinder the achievement of EE. The legal framework is pivotal for handling

conflicts between energy goals and the preservation of cultural values. However, the effectiveness of the legal instrument in steering human behavior towards sustainability objectives greatly depends on the coherent design of the legal system as a whole, including its laws and their application. The deficits stem from both the legislative design and its application, particularly within land use planning, building legislation, and heritage protection law, which are crucial for managing conflicts between EE and cultural heritage preservation. However, even when the legal system is well-designed, the lack of consistent application and enforcement in relation to the legislator's intent can undermine the achievement of its objectives.

The legal and regulatory landscape surrounding the EE retrofitting of heritage buildings presents a significant barrier, notably through the lack of policy coherence and protocol deficiency. This challenge encompasses the absence of consistent and specific regulations, standards, and protocols at various levels (regional, national, and European), particularly evident during the retrofit planning phase. Such a deficiency hampers the establishment of compulsory standards or targets and creates challenges in aligning national legislation with European directives, resulting in ambiguity regarding definitions, regulations, and effective energy measures for historical buildings.

The absence of a unified framework of specific standards at various regulatory levels (regional, national, and European) exacerbates this issue, (Yazdani Mehr and Wilkinson, 2018; Christiernsson et al., 2021; Buda et al., 2021; Friedman and Cooke, 2012). Concurrently, a deficiency in protocols complicates the decision-making and implementation processes for retrofit solutions, owing to the unique characteristics of historic buildings compared to modern constructions. The negotiation space for selecting retrofit solutions, which strongly depends on stakeholder interactions, is limited by absolute constraints to preserve heritage values, thereby rendering the protocol for selecting and implementing retrofit solutions complex and nuanced (Buda et al., 2021; Battista et al., 2022). This scenario is further complicated by a lack of specific policies supporting the improvement of energy performance and the absence of standards or methodologies tailored for historical buildings, leading to variability in local planning policies and practices across different councils (Friedman and Cooke, 2012; Ulu and Arsan, 2020).

Addressing these barriers through an integrated approach that emphasizes collaboration among stakeholders, adopting a whole-building approach, and developing common frameworks for assessing retrofit solutions is imperative for balancing EE goals with the preservation of historic and cultural values.

Bureaucratic Hurdles: Regulatory Approvals and planning permissions regime

Bureaucratic hurdles pose significant barriers to enhancing EE in historical buildings, particularly through the complex landscape of local (city, region) regulatory approvals and

planning permissions regimes. The disparate planning approvals criteria set by local planning authorities can impede the implementation of technologically advanced solutions designed to improve EE in a manner sensitive to historical preservation.

As noted by Brooks et al. (2014), the criteria for planning approvals set by local planning authorities often do not align with the pace of technological advancements aimed at improving EE in a way that respects historical preservation. This discrepancy presents a formidable barrier not only to homeowners eager to adopt such innovations but also to businesses looking to introduce environmentally friendly products to the market. The process is further complicated by the division of licensing and regulatory frameworks into separate legislations for below-ground and above-surface installations, requiring multiple permits from various authorities, each with its own timeframe. The lack of unified national and EU standards for implementing RE sources in historical buildings necessitates a case-by-case evaluation of conservation constraints and energy improvement solutions. The situation results in a scenario where the final authority to decide on the application of sustainable energy solutions within historical buildings often lies with heritage conservation bodies, who must balance the need for EE with the imperative to preserve the building's cultural value.

This balancing act requires a multidisciplinary approach to ensure that any energy improvements respect the heritage significance of the building, as dictated by international, national, and regional standards, thereby underscoring the complex interplay between the preservation of cultural heritage and the pursuit of EE within the regulatory landscape.

Preservation Regulations Safeguarding Historical, Sociocultural, and Architectural Values

The preservation of historical, sociocultural, and architectural values in the context of EE improvements in historic buildings presents a significant and complex barrier. This challenge is highlighted by Buda et al. (2021), who point out that retrofit solutions necessary for meeting minimum energy performance requirements may be detrimental to the cultural built heritage values, especially in buildings with a high level of legal protection. The issue is further compounded when traditional buildings are under statutory protection, as noted by Polo López et al. (2021), which restricts the types of modifications that can be made to enhance energy performance while preserving cultural significance.

E. Alexandrou highlighted that the first version of the Directive on the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD) excluded heritage buildings from certain requirements to avoid compromising their heritage value. However, this exclusion poses a risk to the old fabric and heritage value of a significant number of old and mainly traditional buildings due to incompatible interventions that can be argued to be out of the EPBD scope.

Litti et al. (2013) underscore the incompatibility of current energy retrofit interventions with historic buildings. The regulations for preserving architectural heritage and the rational use of energy are not interconnected within European standards, leading to a gap in the legislative and methodological protocol for energy retrofit feasibility within historical and heritage buildings. This gap results in scientific and legislative heterogeneities, increasing differences in awareness and in historical building protection across the European Union.

Yazdani Mehr and Wilkinson (2018) delve into the technical issues and energy-efficient adaptive reuse of heritage-listed city halls in Queensland, Australia. They highlight the balance required to enhance EE while respecting and preserving heritage values. The complexity of installing energy-efficient systems without compromising architectural integrity and historical significance presents significant challenges. These are exacerbated by preservation regulations designed to safeguard the historical, sociocultural, and architectural values of heritage buildings.

Collectively, these works emphasize the multifaceted challenge of improving EE in historic buildings. The need to navigate legal protections, cultural significance, and technical feasibilities demands a nuanced approach that carefully balances energy performance improvements with the preservation of heritage values. This delicate balance necessitates innovative solutions, interdisciplinary collaboration, and possibly new legislative frameworks that reconcile the goals of EE with those of heritage conservation.

Insufficient support and guidance

In addressing the EE of historical buildings, one significant barrier consistently identified across various studies is the issue of insufficient support and guidance. This multifaceted challenge encompasses a range of aspects, from the lack of adequate information and training for stakeholders to the absence of clear and coordinated policies from regulatory authorities. These barriers collectively hinder the effective implementation of energy-efficient measures in historic buildings, underscoring the crucial need for a more supportive and well-guided approach to retrofitting these structures.

Buda et al. (2021) specifically address the barrier of insufficient support and guidance in their paper, identifying key issues such as the lack of confidence among decision-makers due to the complexity of energy performance legislation requirements, the lack of engagement from users due to perceived economic unviability, and the limited access to documented conservation-compatible retrofit measures. This comprehensive analysis illustrates the critical need for enhanced support and guidance to successfully implement energy-efficient solutions in historic buildings. Herrera-Avellanosa et al. (2019), through his analysis, emphasizes that informational barriers significantly limit the implementation of energy-efficient measures in historic buildings, more so than the absence of technical

solutions. The lack of clarity in planning policies and energy modeling is identified as technical barriers, further complicating the retrofit process. Similarly, Brooks et al. (2014) note the incompatibility of guidance and advice offered by various organizations and the lag in planning approvals criteria for historic buildings behind technical innovations. This scenario points to a lack of coordinated support and clear guidance for stakeholders. Mata et al. (2021) highlight the critical role that information plays in fostering the adoption of energy-efficient technologies. Their study reveals how the willingness to adopt such technologies increases with access to information sessions, while a notable reluctance persists among residents due to insufficient information and training. Yazdani Mehr and Wilkinson (2018) echo these sentiments in their comprehensive review, stressing the need for improved support and guidance to navigate the complex design processes and access tested retrofit solutions that ensure heritage compatibility and long-term performance. Rispoli and Organ (2019) further corroborate these findings by pointing out the lack of coherent support and understanding as significant barriers to EE improvements in historic housing. This lack of support not only affects the technical aspects of retrofitting but also impacts the overall willingness and ability of stakeholders to undertake such projects.

The consistent identification of insufficient support and guidance across various studies highlights a crucial barrier to enhancing the EE of historic buildings. Addressing this issue requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses improved information dissemination, training, policy development, and the provision of clear and coordinated guidance. Such efforts are essential to overcoming the existing challenges and successfully implementing energy-efficient retrofit measures that respect and preserve the heritage value of historic buildings.

4.2.3 Economic barriers

Economic barriers significantly impede the advancement of EE in historical buildings. Economic viability of retrofit interventions may affect users' engagement with appropriate technical solutions (Buda et al., 2021). This financial strain is exacerbated in contexts where regulatory and bureaucratic barriers increase project costs through extended permitting processes and compliance with stringent conservation standards. The combination of high initial investment, delayed returns, and insufficient financial incentives creates a significant economic barrier to improving EE in historical buildings, hindering efforts to balance heritage conservation with contemporary environmental sustainability goals. The economic viability of interventions also has a prominent place in literature. Various authors address the barrier of investment payback time or short payback periods to EE in different contexts, specifically in the realm of retrofitting heritage or traditionally constructed buildings for better energy performance. Below is a summary of the relevant economic barriers:

Investment payback time

The enhancement of EE within historical buildings encounters a significant hurdle when addressing investment payback time. This term, referring to the duration needed to recover the costs of an investment through the savings it generates, is a critical factor in the feasibility and attractiveness of retrofitting projects aimed at improving EE. Traditional investors and financial institutions often harbor reservations about the returns from EE projects, such as modernization into district heating or lighting system upgrades, due to their typically lower yield compared to other investment opportunities. This perception significantly influences the decision-making process, contributing to a notable EE gap—the discrepancy between the optimal level of EE that is technically and economically achievable and the level actually realized.

Capital constraints and investment priorities are highlighted as major financial barriers, encompassing a lack of investment capital, competing investment priorities, and long payback periods. High upfront costs, high investment hurdles, and the perception of higher rent premiums deter investment in EE. Marquez et al. (2015) note that businesses often prioritize investments that promise quicker returns, leading to EE measures being sidelined due to their longer payback periods. Research conducted by the UK Department of Energy & Climate Change and ENWORKS (2014) underscores the pivotal role of payback periods in the decision-making calculus for EE improvements. While a majority of businesses surveyed recognized the logical appeal of projects with a payback period of less than two years, the actual implementation rate of such projects remains strikingly low, at only 13%. This discrepancy highlights a departure from a straightforward calculation-decision-implementation model in practice.

Profitability-related barriers further complicate the financial landscape of EE projects. As described by Reddy (2013), factors such as project performance, sales volume, price, and tariff impact the gross revenue of these projects. These elements, alongside development and operating costs, determine the cost-effectiveness and, consequently, the appeal of such investments to private investors. Nair et al. (2011) note the cautious stance adopted towards investments in EE, spurred by uncertainties surrounding return on investment and future energy prices. The apprehension towards higher monthly payments post-investment was identified as a significant deterrent, despite the potential benefits offered by economic policy instruments like investment subsidies and tax deductions. Sorell et al. (2011) point out that hesitancy to invest in EE measures extends beyond financial concerns, encompassing technical risks and doubts about reliability of energy-efficient technologies. This apprehension is often met with the imposition of stringent payback periods, perceived as a rational mitigation strategy against multiple risks inherent in such investments. Schleich (2007) delves into the investment decision-making process, revealing a preference for evaluating investments based on payback periods rather than comprehensive discounted cash flow analyses. This approach results in implicitly higher required rates of return for EE

investments compared to those for general business development projects. Schleich highlights the multifaceted nature of the risks involved, including financial uncertainties like energy price volatility and potential shifts in governmental policy, as well as technical risks pertaining to the reliability and performance of energy-efficient technologies.

The economic feasibility of retrofitting historical buildings with energy-efficient solutions is linked to the concept of investment payback time. Overcoming this barrier necessitates a holistic approach that addresses not only the financial and technical uncertainties but also the perceptual challenges that deter investment in this critical area.

Hidden costs

Hidden costs represent a significant barrier to EE, particularly within the context of historical buildings. These costs, which encompass a range of often overlooked expenses associated with the implementation of EE measures, can significantly impact the financial viability and attractiveness of such initiatives.

Thollader (2010) introduces hidden costs within the framework of non-market failures, defining them as expenses related to information-seeking, negotiations with sellers, contract drafting, and other ancillary activities. When these hidden costs exceed the profits derived from EE measures, they can deter investment. Amecke (2013) identifies hidden costs as a significant barrier to EE. These costs, including search and transactions costs, amenity losses, and other less obvious expenses, can diminish the cost-effectiveness of EE measures. The necessity for building owners to invest time or money in researching EE measures, coupled with the disruption caused by their installation, exemplifies how hidden costs can undermine the perceived feasibility of such initiatives. Trianni et al. (2016) focus on the role of hidden costs as an economic barrier in small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises (SMEs), highlighting their influence on the decision-making process. Indirect expenses, such as production disruptions and inconvenience associated with implementing EE measures, underscore the significance of hidden costs in financial analyses and evaluations. These costs can render EE projects less attractive, particularly to SMEs that operate with limited financial resources and tight budgets. Schleich (2007) elaborates on the implications of hidden costs for the cost-efficient potential of EE technologies, categorizing them into three groups: potential loss of utility associated with energy-efficient choices, site-specific investment costs, and general overhead costs of energy management. These categories encompass a range of costs, from design fees and civil engineering costs to the organizational costs associated with establishing and maintaining an energy management scheme. While hidden costs pose challenges to incorporating them into engineering-economic models due to their specificity and variability, they remain critical to understanding and addressing the EE gap.

Hidden costs emerge as a multifaceted barrier to EE in historical buildings, affecting the overall cost-effectiveness and decision-making processes related to EE measures. Addressing these costs requires a comprehensive understanding of their nature and impact, as well as targeted policy interventions and organizational strategies designed to mitigate their effects and promote the adoption of EE measures.

High upfront costs

The challenge of high upfront costs significantly impedes the adoption of energy-efficient technologies, especially within the context of historic buildings. This barrier includes issues of credit constraints, disparity between initial investments and gradual accrual of benefits, and intricate dynamics of investor-user relationships. The substantial initial financial outlay required for the implementation of energy-efficient measures, juxtaposed with the incremental nature of the benefits, creates a significant hurdle for building owners, tenants, and investors alike.

According to Marquez et al. (2015) these costs include not only purchase and installation of energy-efficient equipment but also potentially extensive modifications to existing structures to accommodate new technologies. The financial burden is often perceived as high, particularly in comparison to conventional systems, with energy-efficient options sometimes requiring a higher initial investment. Despite long-term cost savings and environmental benefits of EE measures, initial costs can deter building owners and managers from undertaking such projects, highlighting the need for financial incentives or mechanisms to offset these initial costs and encourage wider adoption.

Retrofitting, characterized by its initial cost burden, poses a challenge, especially when the benefits, in terms of energy savings, materialize over extended periods. Thollander et al. (2010) state the difficulty in acquiring additional capital for investment in these technologies, pointing out that energy-efficiency goals are often relegated behind economic considerations. Credit constraints emerge as a critical factor, with Golove and Eto (1996) noting that individuals often lack the necessary financial resources or access to credit to cover the high upfront costs associated with retrofitting. This scenario is more pronounced in private residential properties, where the availability of finance is a predominant barrier (Buda et al. (2021)), especially for private residential property owners who may not have sufficient funds for retrofitting. Retrofitting demands upfront costs, and the benefits, such as energy savings, accrue over time, typically resulting in long payback periods. This financial barrier is further compounded by a discrepancy between actual and predicted energy savings (performance gap), which can affect the decision-making process. Stakeholders might prefer retrofitting measures subsidized through national incentives, which can oversimplify the planning process and potentially overlook the preservation of the historic building's values. Blomqvist et al. (2022) highlight that reducing costs remains a major driver for EE in the sector, with more capital for EE projects becoming available, especially in the

private sector. This indicates a growing recognition of the economic benefits of EE, not just as a cost-saving measure but also as an investment opportunity.

The barrier of high upfront costs to EE in historical buildings is entrenched in financial, contractual, and organizational dynamics. Addressing this barrier necessitates a concerted effort to alleviate credit constraints, enhance access to financial resources, and foster innovative contractual and organizational solutions. These measures would facilitate a more favorable environment for the adoption of energy-efficient technologies, thereby contributing to the conservation and sustainable use of historic properties.

Scarcity and limited access to Public Financial Support

Scarcity and limited access to public financial support emerge as significant barriers to enhancing EE in historic buildings. This challenge is exacerbated by inherently higher costs associated with energy-efficient technologies and the complex nature of retrofitting projects that aim to preserve historical integrity. The availability and accessibility of public financial support are crucial in mitigating market failures and promoting the adoption of energy-efficient technologies.

Jaffe and Stavins (1994) underscore that the effectiveness of interventions aimed at closing the energy-efficiency gap heavily relies on the design, implementation, and accessibility of government programs or financial incentives. When such support is scarce or difficult to access, it significantly hinders efforts to bridge the gap between current practices and the potential for EE. Webb (2017) highlights the particular challenges faced by owners and custodians of historic buildings. The limited availability of public financial support, coupled with stringent requirements to maintain historical integrity, complicates the implementation of standard energy retrofit solutions. This underscores the necessity of tailored financial support mechanisms that recognize the unique challenges associated with retrofitting historic structures. Schleich (2007) discusses capital access barriers in the context of private households and enterprises. Their limited access to credit, especially at high interest rates, can prevent the realization of EE projects with high returns. This barrier is not necessarily indicative of a failure in capital markets but rather reflects the high-risk perception of low-income households by potential lenders. In the enterprise sector, the 'access to capital' problem encompasses both external finance issues and internal budgeting procedures that often neglect EE. Investments in EE are frequently classified as discretionary, resulting in a lower priority compared to essential maintenance projects or strategic investments.

Scarcity and limited access to public financial support for EE projects, particularly in the context of historic buildings, underscore the need for well-designed and accessible financial incentives. Tailoring these support mechanisms to address the unique constraints of historic buildings, while also simplifying the process of accessing such support, could significantly

alleviate this barrier. Policy interventions, alongside initiatives aimed at reducing transaction costs and reevaluating the risk perceptions associated with EE investments, could foster a more conducive environment for the preservation and sustainable retrofitting of historic structures.

Split incentive

The split incentive barrier presents a significant challenge to improving EE, particularly in the realm of historical buildings. This barrier arises from a misalignment between the entities responsible for making EE investments and those who stand to benefit from such improvements. The concept of split incentives complicates the pursuit of energy-efficient practices and technologies, as it often leads to underinvestment, especially when the costs and benefits of EE are not accrued by the same party. This issue is prevalent across various sectors, including residential, commercial, industrial, and organizational contexts, and is particularly pronounced in landlord-tenant relationships.

The split incentive problem is illustrated by Thollander et al. (2020), on how individuals or departments making investments in EE may not directly reap the benefits, thus diminishing their interest in such initiatives. This scenario is frequently observed in landlord-tenant dynamics, where landlords might lack the incentive to invest in EE enhancements because it is the tenants who are responsible for utility bills. Consequently, landlords may not see a direct financial return on investments aimed at reducing energy consumption, leading to a reluctance to invest in energy-efficient technologies or practices. Jaffe and Stavins (1994) delve into the intricacies of the energy-efficiency gap, highlighting how split incentives can emerge due to the distribution of costs and benefits among different parties. They point out that a lack of motivation to adopt EE measures can arise when the adopter is not the one bearing the energy costs. This situation is common in the building sector, where building owners may not consider EE a priority if the benefits are primarily experienced by the tenants through lower energy bills. Melvin (2018) further elaborates on the split incentive barrier, noting that it occurs when the potential adopter of an energy-efficient investment does not pay the energy bill. This misalignment of incentives leads to a scenario where the economic and environmental benefits of EE are not fully realized, contributing to the persistence of the EE gap.

To address the challenge posed by split incentives, policy interventions can play a pivotal role. Policies designed to reduce the costs of implementing EE measures, such as labeling, can enhance the economic efficiency of such interventions. By making the benefits of EE more transparent and aligning the interests of all parties involved, it is possible to mitigate the effects of split incentives.

The split incentive barrier significantly impedes progress towards closing the EE gap, especially in settings involving historical buildings. The disconnection between those who

invest in EE and those who benefit from reduced energy consumption necessitates thoughtful policy solutions. By aligning the incentives of property owners and tenants, or other relevant parties, through targeted interventions, it is possible to foster a more conducive environment for EE investments. This alignment is crucial for advancing EE initiatives and realizing the associated economic and environmental benefits.

4.2.4 Environmental barriers

Depending on the nature of the intervention, specific operations required for installing energy-efficient retrofitting systems may give rise to additional environmental considerations. Buildings, particularly historical structures, often face significant environmental barriers hindering EE. These barriers stem from various factors, including architectural design, material composition, and the integration of modern technologies. The environmental barriers underscore the complexity of promoting EE in historical buildings, requiring a delicate balance between preservation and sustainability goals.

Installation-related impacts, including noise, drilling vibrations, waste, and pollution leakage

Installation-related impacts in historical buildings pose significant challenges to EE efforts, encompassing various factors such as noise, drilling vibrations, waste management, and pollution leakage. Baechler et al. (1992) explored the potential environmental impacts of implementing energy conservation measures in industrial settings, specifically addressing issues such as noise, waste, and pollution leakage (i.e. technologies like adjustable speed drives). When drilling for energy-related purposes, whether for geothermal heat pumps, wind turbines, or solar panel installations, several logistical issues arise. These include the energy required for drilling operations, typically sourced from diesel engines or electric power cables, along with securing supplies such as fuel, lubricants, tools, and replacement parts, which may encounter accessibility problems. Waste removal, particularly of drill cuttings or mud, presents another challenge, requiring careful segregation and disposal to prevent environmental contamination. Additionally, the disposal of drilling fluid, often containing hazardous materials, demands specific permissions and treatment before discharge, particularly in urban settings where waste disposal through on-site storage is common practice. (Lucchi, 2023; Grytli et al., 2012). Furthermore, drilling operations in historical environments necessitate stringent measures to minimize disruptions to nearby residents, office occupants, or passers-by. Noise, dust, dirt, odor, and vibrations generated during drilling must be controlled to mitigate their impact on the surroundings (Lucchi, 2023). The construction operations associated with drilling also have implications for ground and hydrogeological conditions. Careful planning is required to minimize subsidence risks and prevent contamination of aquifers during drilling. Waste disposal, including solid cuttings and liquid waste, necessitates segregation and appropriate disposal methods, with

special considerations for urban settings where on-site storage may be the primary option. Furthermore, noise restrictions, vibration levels, and visual impacts during both construction and operation phases must be carefully managed to avoid adverse effects on the landscape and historical buildings in close vicinity. (Lucchi, 2023; Dowson et al., 2012).

Addressing installation-related impacts on EE in historical buildings requires a comprehensive approach that integrates technological solutions with environmental considerations and community engagement. Strategies such as minimizing drilling-related disruptions, implementing effective waste management practices, and adhering to stringent environmental regulations can help mitigate the adverse effects of energy-related installations while preserving the historical integrity of these buildings. (Baechler et al., 1992; Grytli et al., 2012).

Long-term visual and landscape impacts

Long-term visual and landscape impacts play a critical role in the EE of historical buildings, presenting challenges during both construction and operation phases. Grytli et al. (2012) highlight the potential architectural composition alterations resulting from interventions like external wall insulation, which may lead to the loss of original surfaces, windows, and ornaments, thus impacting the overall visual aesthetics and landscape character. Similarly, Buda et al. (2021) discuss the integration of RE systems, such as solar panels, in historic buildings, emphasizing the need to preserve their architectural integrity while enhancing EE. Webb (2017) echoes these concerns, emphasizing the significance of minimizing visual impact when implementing energy supply retrofits like solar panels. These interventions, while beneficial for reducing CO₂ emissions, can significantly alter a building's appearance, thus affecting its historical and landscape value. Lucchi (2023) delves into the assessment of wind turbines' visual acceptability within landscapes, emphasizing criteria such as technical dominance and preservation of the landscape scale. The study underscores the importance of minimizing the visual impact on heritage sites and landscapes, indicating the need for strategic placement to maintain aesthetic harmony. Polo López (2014) further explores the balance between technical and aesthetic requirements when installing solar energy systems in historic buildings, advocating for high architectural design quality to mitigate long-term visual and landscape impacts. It underscores the necessity of reconciling historical preservation with RE integration, highlighting the importance of careful planning and design considerations.

Addressing long-term visual and landscape impacts in historical buildings' EE entails navigating complex trade-offs between preservation and sustainability goals. While interventions such as external insulation and RE systems offer opportunities for EE improvements, they must be executed with sensitivity to maintain the historical and aesthetic integrity of these buildings and their surrounding landscapes. Achieving this balance requires careful consideration of architectural design quality, strategic placement

of energy infrastructure, and adherence to preservation principles. Through interdisciplinary approaches and meticulous planning, it is possible to enhance EE in historical buildings while preserving their visual and landscape values for future generations.

System Inefficiency Impact on Carbon Footprint

System inefficiency significantly impacts the carbon footprint of historical buildings, presenting challenges in achieving meaningful EE improvements while preserving their architectural integrity. This underscores the importance of a holistic approach to energy-saving measures to mitigate potential negative environmental impacts and prevent an unintended rise in carbon emissions (Grytli et al., 2012). The challenge of balancing EE with environmental considerations and architectural preservation becomes evident, as highlighted by Mozartella (2015), who stresses the importance of considering multiple parameters such as indoor comfort, material conservation, and architectonic character during retrofitting.

Galvin and Sunikka-Blank (2016) discuss the rebound effect, where anticipated energy savings from efficiency improvements may be offset by changes in behavior or economic responses, ultimately affecting the carbon footprint. This phenomenon underscores the complexity of accurately predicting the impacts of EE measures on energy consumption and carbon footprints, necessitating more nuanced policy approaches. Similarly, Örn (2018) emphasizes the need for an integrated approach that balances EE goals with heritage preservation, highlighting the intricate relationship between system inefficiency and carbon footprint reduction in heritage buildings.

Another prominent issue is the lack of insulation in historical structures, leading to substantial heat loss in colder climates and heightened energy consumption for heating purposes. This deficiency, coupled with the architectural features of historical buildings such as large windows and high ceilings, complicates the implementation of modern energy-saving technologies without compromising their historical significance. Retrofit measures intended to enhance EE, such as cavity wall insulation and loft insulation, may not always yield the anticipated energy savings due to factors like thermal bridges, gaps in insulation, and changes in occupant behavior post-refurbishment (Dowson et al., 2012; Grondzik et al., 2014). Additionally, climate change poses further challenges by exacerbating system inefficiency in historical buildings, leading to a mismatch in HVAC capacity, increased cooling energy use, and changes in envelope moisture buffering (Webb, 2017). This can result in heightened energy consumption and carbon emissions, highlighting the importance of adapting historical buildings to future climate conditions while preserving their architectural and historical significance.

Addressing system inefficiency and its impact on the carbon footprint of historical buildings requires a multifaceted approach that considers architectural preservation, EE measures, and environmental sustainability goals.

4.2.5 Social barriers

Social or ideological barriers play a significant role in the challenges faced when attempting to enhance EE in heritage buildings. These barriers often stem from deeply held beliefs and values regarding the preservation of historical integrity and architectural authenticity. For many stakeholders involved in the conservation of heritage buildings, including owners, conservationists, and regulatory bodies, there is a prevailing concern that EE interventions may compromise the historical character and aesthetic value of these structures. This ideological commitment to maintaining the original state of heritage buildings as closely as possible can lead to resistance against the implementation of modern energy-saving technologies and practices. Such interventions are sometimes perceived as intrusive or inappropriate, particularly when they involve visible changes to the building's facade or interior.

Lack of awareness or interest stemming from insufficient or asymmetric information

Lack of awareness or interest in EE, particularly within the domain of heritage buildings, often stems from insufficient or asymmetric information. This barrier significantly impedes the adoption of energy-efficient technologies and practices, as potential investors, owners, and custodians of historic buildings may not fully understand the benefits or feasibility of such interventions, leading to misconceptions about the viability and operational complexity of these energy-efficient systems.

Herrera-Avellanosa et al. (2019) point out that one of the principal barriers for decision-makers, especially private owners of historic buildings, is the challenge of determining "what to do, where to start, and which measures to implement in which order." This confusion is largely attributed to informational barriers, which, as Ástmarrsson et al. (2013) concluded, can be more limiting than the actual lack of technical solutions. Palm and Bryngelson (2023) discuss the barriers posed by lack of information or imperfect information about existing EE measures. Thollander et al. (2010) expand on this, noting that consumers are often poorly informed about market conditions, technology characteristics, and their own energy use. This insufficient information about potential energy-efficient technologies inhibits investments in EE measures. Schleich (2007) categorizes information problems hindering EE investments into three broad areas: inadequate information on current energy consumption, imperfect information on specific energy-saving opportunities, and asymmetric information on the energy consumption of new and refurbished buildings. This imperfect information can lead to underinvestment in EE, as the benefits of such investments are not fully recognized or understood by potential adopters. The costs

associated with seeking and acquiring information about energy-efficient technologies can also inhibit awareness of these solutions. The significance of training and awareness-raising activities is highlighted by D'Oca et al. (2018), who recognize the need for such initiatives to bridge the knowledge gap in building EE. This suggests an existing lack of competence in the field, underlining the importance of educational efforts to impart necessary knowledge and skills.

The lack of awareness or interest due to insufficient or asymmetric information represents a significant barrier to enhancing EE in heritage buildings. Overcoming this barrier requires targeted information campaigns, training, and awareness-raising activities designed to improve the understanding of EE benefits and opportunities among stakeholders. Additionally, policy interventions such as energy labelling could help alleviate this barrier by providing reliable and accessible information on the energy performance of technologies and buildings.

Absence of consensus among various stakeholders

The absence of consensus among various stakeholders represents a significant barrier to implementing EE in historical buildings. This challenge emerges from the diverse array of values, interests, and objectives that stakeholders bring to the table when considering retrofitting solutions for heritage properties. The cultural, economic, and social backgrounds of the stakeholders can exacerbate the challenge of reaching consensus. Diverse backgrounds may result in divergent views on technological development and its implementation within the framework of heritage conservation.

Yazdani Mehr and Wilkinson (2018) point out that the ownership and interest of the local community are especially critical in the context of public historic buildings. The local community's attachment to and valuation of the heritage significance of such buildings can deeply impact the decision-making process regarding retrofitting efforts. This communal stake in the preservation of historical buildings necessitates a broader consensus-building process that includes not only technical and financial considerations but also cultural and social dimensions. Buda et al. (2021) highlight that owners and building professionals involved in the retrofit process might prioritize different aspects such as heritage and cultural values, aesthetic considerations, or architectural integrity. These diverging priorities can lead to tensions or, conversely, synergies in identifying viable energy-efficient retrofitting solutions. The negotiation of retrofit solutions is profoundly influenced by interactions among stakeholders, particularly in the early stages of decision-making, to align on interventions compatible with the building's characteristics.

Overcoming the barrier of an absence of consensus among stakeholders in the EE retrofitting of historical buildings requires a multifaceted approach. This approach should prioritize open dialogue, effective communication of technical information, and the early

inclusion of all relevant parties in the decision-making process. By fostering a collaborative environment that respects and integrates the diverse values and interests of stakeholders, it is possible to identify and implement retrofitting solutions that balance the goals of EE with the preservation of heritage and cultural integrity.

General reluctance to depart from conventional systems and traditional materials:

The journey toward enhancing EE in heritage buildings is frequently hindered by a general reluctance to depart from conventional systems and traditional materials. This resistance is deeply rooted in the values, preferences, and organizational culture of those involved in the management, renovation, and conservation of historic properties. The complexities involved in achieving a consensus among stakeholders, compounded by varying levels of familiarity with EE technologies, underscore challenges faced in integrating modern EE solutions into historic buildings.

Stakeholders, including owners, conservators, and construction professionals, often exhibit skepticism towards adopting new technologies in heritage buildings due to uncertainties and perceived risks associated with their implementation. Herrera-Avellanosa et al. (2019) highlight that up to 70% of households may abandon the idea of incorporating energy-efficient measures into their homes' renovation due to a strong attachment to personal values. This attachment is coupled with concerns regarding the availability of professionals with sufficient expertise and the compatibility of new technologies with historic features. The construction industry's organizational culture, characterized by its conservatism, further exacerbates resistance to adopting new design strategies and integrating processes within the building supply chain. The challenges include adopting different design strategies, fostering new kinds of collaboration across organizations, and enforcing more discipline and rigor in executing various building techniques, such as creating airtightness within building facades. Thollander et al. (2010) introduce the concept of "inertia" as a factor contributing to the gap between the potential for and the realization of EE, where individuals and organizations are, to some extent, creatures of habit and established routines, making it challenging to enact changes in behaviors and practices. This resistance to change is driven by a desire to reduce uncertainty and avoid problems, with individuals often seeking to justify past decisions to confirm their correctness. This inertia can partially explain why many energy users fail to undertake economically justifiable actions to save energy, as EE typically requires starting with small commitments that may later lead to more significant ones.

The reluctance to depart from conventional systems and traditional materials in the context of heritage buildings is influenced by stakeholders' values, the conservative culture of the construction industry, and an inherent inertia against change. Overcoming this barrier necessitates effective communication, the provision of comprehensive information about the benefits of EE technologies, and fostering a culture that is open to innovation and

collaboration. Addressing these challenges is crucial for reconciling the preservation of historic integrity with the pursuit of EE.

Hesitancy to disrupt regular operation during site works and/or relocation

Hesitancy to disrupt the regular operation of historical buildings during site works, or the reluctance to relocate temporarily, represents a significant barrier to implementing EE improvements. This challenge is rooted in the unique nature of historic properties, which often serve as active sites for cultural, educational, commercial, or residential purposes.

Historical buildings, by their very nature, are custodians of cultural heritage and often continue to play an active role in the community. Whether they function as museums, offices, residential spaces, or venues for special events, the continuous operation of these sites is crucial for their sustainability and relevance. The necessity to maintain regular operations without interruptions poses a significant challenge to undertaking comprehensive EE retrofitting projects. These projects typically require extensive site works, including structural modifications, installation of new systems, and sometimes, temporary closure of the facility.

Vadodaria et al. (2010) note that householders must perceive the benefits of EE improvements as outweighing the inconvenience and disruption caused by the retrofitting process. This highlights a critical barrier: the reluctance to undergo short-term disruptions for long-term gains, a sentiment that can significantly impede the implementation of energy-efficient solutions in historical buildings. Further studies corroborate the significance of this barrier. The reluctance to undertake actions that could disrupt the budget or time plan is a significant barrier, emphasizing a cautious approach to the retrofitting process to avoid operational disruptions. This concern is particularly pronounced in the context of historical buildings, where the risks of operational downtime and the potential impact on visitor numbers or tenant satisfaction are critical considerations in decision-making (Carlander and Thollander, 2023).

The apprehension about disrupting operations is compounded by concerns over the potential need to relocate occupants or activities temporarily. For residential historic buildings, this means finding temporary housing for residents, a process that can be both complex and costly. For commercial or public historic buildings, temporary relocation can lead to a loss of revenue, diminished public engagement, or interruptions to critical services provided to the community. These potential outcomes create a strong disincentive for initiating EE projects, despite the long-term benefits such projects might offer in terms of reduced energy consumption and improved environmental sustainability.

4.3 Representation of the results from the survey

Following the analysis methodology, 20 selected barriers from 5 main groups (Technical, Legal, Economic, Environmental and Social) identified with a literature were then validated through a survey that gathered inputs from 54 stakeholder representatives from four pilot site countries and beyond. The survey synthesized a wealth of insights from a diverse array of stakeholders in the domain of EE in heritage buildings (see Figure 4).

FIGURE 4: PROFILES OF RESPONDERS

Garnering responses from an equal number of men and women, the survey reflected a broad spectrum of viewpoints, with a noteworthy participation from individuals in the age brackets that often occupy mid-level to senior professional roles. Such a demographic composition is indicative of an engaged and experienced community, well-positioned to provide informed feedback on the barriers to EE within this sector. A detailed examination of stakeholder roles revealed that a significant number of respondents were heritage occupants, regulators, and advisory intermediaries. This mix of participants underscores the multifaceted nature of the challenges faced in retrofitting heritage buildings for better energy performance. The active involvement of these groups is crucial; it reflects a scenario where those who experience the impact of energy inefficiency firsthand, as well as those who draft regulations and provide guidance, are contributing their expertise and perspective. On the flip side, the less substantial input from suppliers and building management operators signals a potential gap in representation, hinting at the need for a more concerted effort to capture these stakeholders' unique insights in future engagements. Collectively, the responses gathered provide a rich foundation for understanding the intricate web of technical, legislative, economic, environmental, and social factors that frame the current state of EE in heritage buildings. The data collected is instrumental for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners as they map out the landscape of barriers and pinpoint strategic opportunities for intervention and improvement. It's a testament to the collaborative spirit required to address the multifaceted challenges of preserving heritage while advancing energy sustainability.

Respondents were asked to prioritize the barriers identified in the literature review through assessing their relevance and to suggest additional barriers that they perceived. From the survey, a varying number of records were prioritized across the four mentioned regions - Estonia, Italy, Portugal, and Spain - resulting in a diverse compilation of barriers that were further expanded upon by the respondents, illustrating a detailed and location-specific understanding of the challenges faced (see Figure 5). This collated data underwent a rigorous analysis to establish a comparison base. The barriers were scrutinized for their relevance and their impact on stakeholders, identifying the phases in which the barriers are most prominent. The survey also aimed to understand the roles of different stakeholders in mitigating these barriers, categorizing them as mitigators, enablers, or change agents. The results of this analysis were distilled into a problem tree, a graphical representation that articulates the root causes of the barriers to EE in heritage buildings and the relationships between them. This problem tree lays the groundwork for scenario analysis, where different phases are scrutinized, and for mapping out potential mitigation strategies, ultimately aiming to streamline the process of enhancing EE within this specific context.

FIGURE 5: REPRESENTATION OF COLLECTED RESULTS

In the survey conducted to evaluate the relevance of barriers to EE in heritage buildings, respondents were provided with a Likert scale to measure their perceptions. This scale ranged from 'Not Relevant' to 'Very Relevant,' with intermediary options of 'Low Relevance,'

'Neutral,' and 'Relevant.' This methodological approach enabled a nuanced capture of stakeholders' assessments, ensuring that varying degrees of relevance could be accurately recorded and reflected. To translate these qualitative assessments into a quantifiable prioritization, each response on the Likert scale was assigned a numerical score: 'Not Relevant' was allocated a score of 0, 'Low Relevance' a score of 25, 'Neutral' a score of 50, 'Relevant' a score of 75, and 'Very Relevant' a score of 100. These scores allowed for the aggregation and comparison of data in a standardized format. An average score was then calculated for each barrier, synthesizing the individual scores into a collective assessment that represents the perceived importance or urgency of each barrier as viewed by the survey participants. This scoring system facilitated a structured prioritization process, highlighting which barriers are deemed most critical to address by the diverse set of stakeholders involved in the field of heritage building EE.

In addition to the Likert scale for assessing the relevance of known barriers to EE in heritage buildings, the survey methodology included an open-ended component. This allowed respondents the flexibility to identify and describe additional barriers that were not listed in the survey. Such open questions are crucial as they provide room for participants to draw from their personal experiences and insights, potentially uncovering novel or underrepresented barriers.

These supplementary barriers, as identified by the respondents (see Annex 2), add a layer of detail to the understanding of what impedes EE improvements in heritage buildings and are instrumental for developing comprehensive strategies to overcome them. They encompass a range of categories from technical and legal to economic, environmental, and social factors, each presenting unique challenges across various phases of project development. The respondents' contributions emphasize the importance of a comprehensive and adaptive approach to address the multifaceted barriers to EE in heritage buildings. A notable concern is the misalignment between regulatory frameworks and conservation practices, especially in instances where modern building codes clash with heritage preservation laws. Technical issues such as the integration of insulation in cold climates and the influence of EE measures on the landscape and structural authenticity of historic buildings emerge as pivotal points of contention, requiring careful balance between modernization and preservation. Economic challenges are also prevalent, with a distinct focus on financing limitations, the impacts of low-income ownership on decision-making, and the property value disparities in rural areas. These economic barriers highlight the need for inclusive financial strategies that accommodate a spectrum of socioeconomic conditions. Environmentally, the survey brought to light the necessity of considering biodiversity, local bio-habitats, and the imperative to establish circular economy practices within the renovation process. These inputs stress the importance of sustainability not just in the renovation outcome but throughout the entire lifecycle of materials and technologies. Social aspects are not overlooked, with responses emphasizing the significance of stakeholder knowledge, owner and tenant resistance, and the overarching benefits of environmentally

friendly solutions. There is a clear call for better communication and education to facilitate more informed and community-aligned decision-making.

Upon validation of the barriers, focus was done on those classified as 'relevant' and 'most relevant.' According to the previously described scaling system, these are the barriers that garnered an average score exceeding 75.

This threshold was established to ensure that only the barriers perceived as significantly impacting EE efforts in heritage buildings were carried forward for in-depth analysis and consideration in the development of solutions and policy recommendations. The barriers that met this criterion and will be subject to further investigation are (see Figure 6):

- L2. Bureaucratic Hurdles: Regulatory Approvals and planning permissions regime;
- L3. Preservation Regulations Safeguarding Historical, Sociocultural, and Architectural Values;
- E1. Investment playback time;
- E3. High upfront costs;
- E4. Scarcity and limited access to Public Financial Support;
- EN2. Long-term visual and landscape impacts.

FIGURE 6: RELEVANCE OF BARRIERS TO GENERAL CONTEXT

The selection of these barriers for detailed investigation reflects a strategic choice to concentrate efforts on areas where improvement can significantly enhance the EE of heritage buildings. The other barriers, while noted, will not be included in the problem tree analysis, allowing for a focused and resource-efficient approach to overcoming the most critical obstacles identified by stakeholders in the survey. The analysis of the survey results identifies a group of stakeholders who are particularly exposed to the challenges presented by the barriers to EE in heritage buildings (see Figure 7).

FIGURE 7: BARRIER SENSITIVITY INDEX FOR PRINCIPAL STAKEHOLDERS

The data indicates that advisory intermediaries, heritage owners, and regulators are particularly susceptible when navigating the bureaucratic hurdles of regulatory approvals and planning permissions (L2). These stakeholders are also sensitive to the challenges posed by preservation regulations that protect historical, sociocultural, and architectural values (L3), often navigating complex requirements to preserve the integrity of heritage sites. Heritage owners and financiers emerge as notably exposed groups when it comes to economic barriers. They face significant concerns regarding the investment payback period (E1), the burden of high upfront costs (E3), and the challenges of accessing public financial support (E4). These financial challenges can be a significant deterrent to initiating EE projects, as they directly affect the feasibility and return on investment for stakeholders. Furthermore, the analysis highlights the concern for heritage owners, heritage occupants, advisory intermediaries, and regulators regarding the long-term visual and landscape impacts (EN2) of EE measures. These groups must balance the need for modern energy solutions with the conservation of heritage sites' visual integrity and their surroundings.

These identified groups suggest a need for targeted support and tailored solutions to overcome the specific barriers they face. Addressing their concerns is crucial for enabling progress toward energy-efficient heritage conservation and achieving the broader goals of sustainability and preservation.

Stakeholders were asked to pinpoint the phase in the planning of energy retrofitting (as were presented in Section 4.2 “Theoretical Framework for Barriers Analysis”), where specific barriers would most likely surface or exert the most influence to understand at which stage particular issues need to be addressed to streamline the retrofitting process effectively. Understanding the phases where these barriers are most prevalent can guide planners and stakeholders in allocating resources, planning interventions, and developing strategies to anticipate and mitigate these challenges effectively (see Figure 8). Survey respondents indicated that legal and regulatory barriers (L2), such as bureaucratic challenges and the need for regulatory approvals, are most prominent in the design and decision-making phases, affecting project progression and prioritization. Preservation regulations (L3) are crucial in the initial preparation phase (Phase I), where the integration of heritage values into the retrofitting plan is foundational. Economic concerns, encompassing payback periods and upfront costs (E1, E3, E4), are significant during the initial (Phase I) and decision-making phases, where financial viability shapes the project's approach. Environmental impacts (EN2), particularly those affecting visuals and landscape, become critical in the implementation phase (Phase IV), where the physical alterations to heritage sites take place.

FIGURE 8: THE LANDSCAPE OF CHALLENGES IN ENERGY PLANNING PHASES

In the survey, participants were asked to identify the roles of different actors in the context of barriers to energy retrofitting in heritage buildings. The roles were categorized into:

- Enablers- individuals or groups that may unintentionally or deliberately uphold or strengthen the barriers.
- Mitigators- actively seek to minimize or eliminate the barriers.
- Change agents- pivotal in spotting and instituting the means to surmount these challenges.

The results (see Figure 9) show that heritage occupants are frequently seen as enablers for various barriers, potentially because their actions or inactions can inadvertently maintain the status quo. For Legal Barriers, installers and contractors are viewed as mitigators, possibly due to their hands-on ability to navigate and work within or around existing regulations during the actual retrofitting process. Regulators are acknowledged as change

agents for Legal Barriers, underlining their capacity to alter or enforce policies that can either alleviate or compound these barriers. For Economic Barriers, heritage occupants are again seen as enablers. This could reflect a situation where their decisions based on immediate financial considerations might inadvertently perpetuate energy inefficiency. Advisory intermediaries are identified as mitigators, which suggests their role in providing guidance and strategies to overcome financial hurdles. Advisory bodies, regulators, and financiers are all recognized as change agents, indicating their influence in creating financial models and policies that enable energy retrofitting. Environmental Barriers also see heritage occupants as enablers, which could relate to preferences that impact environmental outcomes. Advisory bodies and Building management operators are the mitigators, suggesting their involvement in developing and promoting environmental best practices. Advisory intermediaries serve as change agents, showcasing their role in educating and influencing the implementation of environmentally sound practices.

The scoring depicted in Figure 9 was derived from the aggregated responses collected during the survey phase where Participants were instructed to classify each stakeholder into one of three roles: barrier enabler, mitigator, or change agent. The score for each stakeholder represents the aggregate responses collected across all participants, reflecting the perceptions of the stakeholders' roles in either enabling, mitigating, or catalyzing change regarding the identified barriers.

The problem tree (Figure 10) synthesizes the findings from the survey, detailing how different stakeholder groups are perceived in their roles related to energy retrofitting in heritage buildings. It's a tool used to understand the complex web of challenges (barriers) within a system and the interactions of various actors within it. In this diagram, stakeholder groups are divided into exposed groups, barriers enablers, barriers mitigators, and change agents, while horizontal bars represent different phases of energy retrofitting planning, and the lines connecting stakeholders to these phases indicate their influence or impact at each stage. The network of lines illustrates the complexity and interconnectivity of roles and phases in the energy retrofitting process.

To systematically align all the gathered survey findings with the problem tree, the results were integrated in Table 2. This table is used to consolidate survey results for clarity and analysis. The results featured in Table 2 are presented in two distinct formats: Relative Comparison and Absolute Maximum (abs max). The Relative Comparison section highlights peaks of replies from survey responders, focusing on the most frequently mentioned results. Conversely, the Absolute Maximum section showcases selected results representing only the absolute maximum occurrences, providing a concise overview of the most prominent findings.

TECHNICAL BARRIERS

	Heritage owner	Heritage occupant	Advisory Intermediaries	Installer/Contractor	Suppliers	Advisory body	Regulators	Financiers	BMO
Barrier Enabler	26	31	9	8	11	10	29	19	7
Barrier Mitigator	18	18	14	31	15	18	13	24	31
Change Agent	10	5	31	15	28	26	12	11	15

LEGAL BARRIERS

	Heritage owner	Heritage occupant	Advisory Intermediaries	Installer/Contractor	Suppliers	Advisory body	Regulators	Financiers	BMO
Barrier Enabler	15	26	5	15	11	11	18	17	13
Barrier Mitigator	30	22	29	32	30	15	6	25	31
Change Agent	9	6	20	7	13	28	30	12	9

ECONOMIC BARRIERS

	Heritage owner	Heritage occupant	Advisory Intermediaries	Installer/Contractor	Suppliers	Advisory body	Regulators	Financiers	BMO
Barrier Enabler	21	29	6	17	15	7	17	12	14
Barrier Mitigator	19	19	36	24	28	22	12	17	31
Change Agent	14	6	12	13	11	25	25	25	8

ENVIRONMENTAL BARRIERS

	Heritage owner	Heritage occupant	Advisory Intermediaries	Installer/Contractor	Suppliers	Advisory body	Regulators	Financiers	BMO
Barrier Enabler	21	30	7	20	12	7	12	14	10
Barrier Mitigator	23	20	17	19	22	28	20	27	28
Change Agent	10	4	30	15	20	19	22	13	15

SOCIAL BARRIERS

	Heritage owner	Heritage occupant	Advisory Intermediaries	Installer/Contractor	Suppliers	Advisory body	Regulators	Financiers	BMO
Barrier Enabler	31	32	7	18	12	4	10	8	9
Barrier Mitigator	11	12	23	27	26	26	21	29	28
Change Agent	12	10	24	9	16	24	23	17	16

FIGURE 9: THE ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS AS CATALYSTS IN OVERCOMING BARRIERS

FIGURE 10: PROBLEM TREE (GENERAL CONTEXT)

TABLE 2 – INTEGRATED RESULTS (GENERAL CONTEXT)

GENERAL						
Barrier Code	Overall Relevance Score	Exposed groups (Relative Comparison (peaks))	Scenario (Relative Comparison (peaks))	Enabler (abs max)	Mitigator (abs max)	Change Agents (abs max)
L2	83	Advisory Intermediaries, Heritage owners, Regulators	Phase 2, Phase 3	Heritage occupant	Installer/ Contractor	Regulators
L3	76	Advisory Intermediaries, Heritage owners, Advisory bodies	Phase 1	Heritage occupant	Installer/ Contractor	Regulators
E1	76	Heritage owners, Financiers	Phase 1, Phase 3	Heritage occupant	Advisory intermediaries	Advisory body, Regulators, Financiers
E3	81	Heritage owners, Financiers	Phase 1	Heritage occupant	Advisory intermediaries	Advisory body, Regulators, Financiers
E4	79	Heritage owners, Financiers	Phase 1	Heritage occupant	Advisory intermediaries	Advisory body, Regulators, Financiers

EN2	76	Heritage owners, Heritage occupants, Advisory Intermediaries, Regulators	Phase 4	Heritage occupant	Advisory body, BMO	Advisory Intermediaries
-----	----	---	---------	-------------------	-----------------------	-------------------------

Based on the problem tree, most relevant barriers were identified as legal (regulatory hurdles, preservation regulations), economic limitations like investment payback time, high upfront costs and limited access to financial support, as well as long-term environmental impacts (both visual and landscape). These barriers were not uniformly impactful across all phases but were most critical at specific junctures in the retrofitting process. Economic barriers, for instance, were predominant during the initial preparation and decision-making stages, environmental impacts were crucial during the implementation and monitoring phase, while the legal barriers were prominent in the first three phases.

Heritage owners and advisory intermediaries consistently face challenges in the retrofitting of heritage buildings that impede EE efforts. Encumbered by the complexities of legal, environmental, and financial barriers, their potential to enact change is often limited, suggesting that the more exposed the stakeholders, the greater the difficulty in implementing energy-efficient upgrades. Heritage building owners may recognize the merits of EE but find themselves constrained by fiscal risks and intricate legalities. Advisory Intermediaries, bearing the responsibility to reconcile the technical feasibility of modern energy solutions with historical preservation, navigate a labyrinth of multifaceted advisory roles. Regulators experience mounting pressures to harmonize advancing energy solutions with conservation laws, a task that grows more complex with project progression. Meanwhile, financiers face the challenge of evaluating the long-term returns of retrofitting heritage buildings, a task particularly daunting during the crucial stages of planning and decision-making. Heritage Occupants’ late-phase vulnerability suggests their potential disengagement or lack of understanding, risking inefficient operation and maintenance of energy systems, which are essential to the efficacy of energy improvements.

The data underscores the role of Heritage Occupants as consistent enablers across the retrofitting process, highlighting their potential to significantly influence project success. Their active participation is vital to navigate and overcome barriers, emphasizing their critical role in endorsing energy-efficient practices.

The analysis reveals that installers and contractors, alongside advisory intermediaries, serve as principal mitigators, playing a pivotal role in reducing barriers to EE in heritage buildings. Their hands-on expertise and advisory capacity are crucial in navigating the complexities inherent in retrofitting. Installers and contractors, in particular, bring practical solutions to the table, directly addressing the on-site challenges and translating energy-efficient concepts into feasible actions that respect the historical value of properties. Advisory intermediaries, by providing expert guidance, become instrumental in the process,

especially in negotiating the economic and environmental barriers. This critical involvement of mitigators highlights the importance of their role at every stage of the retrofitting journey, ensuring that heritage buildings can successfully adopt sustainable practices without compromising their integrity. These stakeholders possess the ability to navigate through the maze of regulatory frameworks and offer practical solutions, thereby reducing barriers from the initial to the final stages of retrofitting. Their input is crucial in translating energy-efficient concepts into actionable steps that respect the historical integrity of buildings.

The findings indicate that regulators, along with advisory bodies, advisory intermediaries and financiers, serve as pivotal change agents in the retrofitting of heritage buildings, particularly influential from the second phase onward. Their roles are critical in shaping and enforcing policies that facilitate the integration of EE measures while safeguarding heritage values. Regulators are especially key in navigating the legal intricacies that come with retrofitting historic properties, influencing the compliance landscape to accommodate modern energy-saving technologies. Financiers also act as change agents by determining the flow of capital towards sustainable retrofitting projects, thereby endorsing EE as a valuable investment. Interestingly, the role of financiers is highlighted also in the later stages, indicating that economic considerations become crucial during the prioritization and decision phase. This suggests that financial planning and support are critical in ensuring that the retrofitting projects not only commence but are seen through to completion. Finally, the placement of advisory intermediaries as change agents during the implementation and monitoring phase underscores the ongoing need for expert input and advice throughout the retrofitting process, not just at the outset. These intermediaries can bridge the gap between theory and practice, ensuring that the solutions are sustainable and effective in the long term.

Overall, the survey revealed that the energy retrofitting of heritage buildings is a complex interplay of diverse factors where each stakeholder group can exert a unique influence. The survey not only helped in reinforcing the validity of the barriers identified from the literature but also provided new insights, with respondents adding more barriers across the five categories: Technical, Legislative and Regulatory, Economic, Environmental, and Social. Clear patterns have emerged indicating where targeted interventions could streamline processes, reduce inefficiencies, and enhance collaboration towards the shared goal of sustainable heritage conservation. It also highlighted that no single group could achieve this alone and that a collective effort is required, with each actor understanding their role and its impact on the entire ecosystem.

4.3.1 Estonia

The insights gathered from stakeholders in Estonia are instrumental in shaping the approach to energy retrofitting of heritage buildings within the Herit4ages project's pilot site. Drawing on the experiences and viewpoints of nine representatives, including advisory bodies, intermediaries, occupants, and regulators, the feedback provides a detailed portrayal of the local environment and its unique retrofitting challenges. Such localized intelligence is indispensable for crafting retrofitting strategies that resonate with Estonia's specific conditions and cultural heritage preservation requirements.

FIGURE 11: BARRIER PRIORITIZATION IN ESTONIA

FIGURE 12: BARRIER EXPOSURE ANALYSIS ACROSS ENERGY PLANNING PHASES AND STAKEHOLDER GROUPS (ESTONIA)

The survey conducted among stakeholders regarding the EE of heritage buildings in Estonia elucidates a spectrum of barriers that manifest with varying intensity across the lifecycle of retrofitting projects (see Table 3). The highest-scoring barrier, denoted as E3, pertains to the high upfront costs, which is particularly prominent in Phase 2, where detailed analysis and energy modeling take place. This suggests that stakeholders recognize the significant financial barrier that must be overcome early in the planning stage. T2, another high-scoring barrier, deals with structural constraints and the complexity of retrofit solutions, spanning Phases 1 and 2, indicating that technical challenges are perceived as most critical when planning and analyzing retrofitting strategies. T3 and L2, pertaining to the lack of one-size-fits-all solutions and bureaucratic hurdles respectively, are highlighted in Phase 1,

suggesting that the inception of a project is hindered by regulatory complexities and the need for customized retrofit approaches. Other important barriers —L3 (Preservation Regulations), E1 (Investment playback time), E2 (Hidden costs), E4 (Scarcity of support), EN2 (Visual impacts), and S2 (Stakeholder consensus)—also carry significance. L3 becomes prominent in Phase 2, where the focus is on aligning retrofitting efforts with historical preservation. E1, E2, and E4, which all revolve around economic constraints, suggest that financial considerations are a continuous concern, most notably during the phases where planning and financial decisions are made (Phases 1 and 2). The visual and landscape impacts (EN2) are considered during the initial phases of planning and design (Phases 1 and 2), while S2 indicates that the absence of consensus among stakeholders is a notable concern during the preparatory and prioritization phases (Phases 1 and 3).

TABLE 3 - INTEGRATED RESULTS (ESTONIA)

ESTONIA						
Barrier Code	Overall Relevance Score	Exposed groups (Relative Comparison (+ 1))	Scenario	Enabler (abs max)	Mitigator (abs max)	Change Agents (abs max)
T2	83	Heritage owners + Advisory Intermediaries	Phase 1, Phase 2	Heritage occupants	Installer/Contractor, Advisory bodies	Suppliers
T3	81	Heritage owners, Advisory Intermediaries, Installers/contractors + Regulators	Phase 1			
L2	83	Heritage owners + Advisory Intermediaries	Phase 3	Installers/contractors	Heritage owners, Heritage occupants	Regulators
L3	78	Heritage owners	Phase 2			
E1	75	Heritage owners	Phase 2	Heritage owners, Heritage occupants	Advisory intermediaries, Advisory body	Advisory body, BMO
E2	78	Heritage owners + BMO	Phase 1, Phase 4			
E3	89	Heritage owners	Phase 2			
E4	78	Heritage owners	Phase 2			
EN2	78	Heritage owners, Regulators + Advisory Intermediaries	Phase 1, Phase 2	Installers/contractors	Advisory body	Advisory intermediaries
S2	78	Heritage owners, Regulators	Phase 1, Phase 3	Heritage owners	Advisory body, BMO	Financiers

The alignment of exposed groups with the occurrence of barriers in these phases indicates a direct correlation between the stakeholders' exposure to risk and the challenges posed by these barriers (see Figure 13) The data highlights heritage owners as persistently exposed, bearing the brunt of decisions affecting their properties. Their vulnerability is heightened by

their direct involvement and the impact of decisions made on their property. Advisory intermediaries face similar risks, particularly in early strategic phases. Regulators are also mentioned as exposed, which might be attributed to the regulatory challenges that arise in the early stages of retrofitting projects, and the Building Management Operators' heightened risk at both project's start and end underscores their operational and sustainability concerns.

FIGURE 13: PROBLEM TREE (ESTONIA)

Enablers like heritage owners and occupants, alongside installers and contractors, are pivotal across phases, combining stewardship with practical insights to influence EE solutions. As the custodians of these buildings, owners bear the responsibility of stewardship, ensuring that any EE measures are sensitive to the building's historical integrity. Occupants offer a lived experience that can provide unique insights into the building's performance and day-to-day energy challenges. Their engagement is especially important in identifying the nuances of each barrier, such as the high upfront costs of EE measures (E3) and the complexities in tailoring retrofit solutions to individual heritage properties (T2 and T3). As enablers, they provide the practical perspective that is crucial for devising feasible solutions that respect the essence of heritage buildings. Installers and contractors, traditionally involved later, now emerge early on, suggesting a shift towards

recognizing the value of their input from the planning phase for integrated, practical solutions. It could be surmised that such collaboration is seen as a mechanism to bridge the gap between theoretical planning and practical implementation, ensuring that the solutions developed are not only respectful of the heritage values but also technically sound and practicable. Advisory bodies stand out as principal mitigators across multiple phases of the retrofitting process. With their expertise in both the technical realms of building conservation and the intricacies of regulatory landscapes, they help heritage owners and other stakeholders manage and adapt to the constraints posed by barriers. Alongside these bodies, heritage owners and occupants also assume mitigating roles, drawing from their intimate knowledge of the buildings to inform strategies that minimize the risk to the buildings' historical values. The involvement of building management operators and installers/contractors suggests a hands-on approach to mitigation, applying practical know-how to address barriers directly during the planning, analysis, and decision-making stages.

The effort of these groups to mitigate challenges highlights the collaborative nature of successful heritage retrofitting projects, where each stakeholder contributes uniquely towards a cohesive goal of sustainable preservation. Change agents are represented by building management operators, advisory intermediaries, suppliers, advisory bodies, regulators, and financiers.

Building management operators, with their specialized knowledge of building operations, are pivotal in steering the projects towards sustainable models, particularly visible in their strategic input. Advisory intermediaries, by providing expert counsel, facilitate the navigation through regulatory and technical mazes, enabling more fluid transitions from planning to implementation.

Suppliers inject the process with up-to-date, energy-efficient materials and technologies, while advisory bodies contribute governance and strategic oversight, ensuring that conservation measures align with broader objectives. Regulators, though often perceived as gatekeepers, can serve as change agents by updating and refining policy frameworks to better accommodate the unique needs of heritage conservation.

Financiers unlock potential by providing the necessary financial support, enabling projects that might otherwise stall due to economic barriers. Together, these change agents form a multifaceted group, each contributing distinct resources and perspectives that collectively reshape the landscape of heritage building retrofitting. While Estonian stakeholders face challenges similar to those identified globally, their specific roles and the stages at which they exert influence provide tailored opportunities for intervention.

Heritage owners and occupants emerge as active contributors whose insights are pivotal to formulating retrofitting plans that are both realistic and sensitive to the heritage context. This challenge in Estonia could point towards a more complex regulatory environment or

greater economic constraints within the country, requiring sustained support and intervention for these stakeholders. The role of regulators as change agents emerges later in Estonia, starting from Phase 2, that could indicate that in Estonia, legal intricacies become particularly challenging as retrofitting projects progress. It signals a clear need for collaborative efforts, integrating diverse perspectives to foster sustainable conservation and retrofitting practices.

The findings reveal the specific obstacles within the Estonian context, such as regulatory intricacies and economic constraints, but also the broader applicability of these challenges. The distinction of certain stakeholders as exposed or as key change agents at different project stages in Estonia provides a detailed roadmap for targeted interventions.

4.3.2 Italy

From Italy, a total of 18 responses were collected as part of the Herit4ages project's survey, representing a mix of advisory bodies, intermediaries, heritage occupants, and regulators. This diverse input provides a well-rounded view of the barriers encountered in energy retrofitting within the Italian heritage sector and identifies the specific challenges and stakeholders that are instrumental in shaping the retrofitting strategies to meet Italy's distinct needs.

BARRIER ID	T1	T2	T3	T4	L1	L2	L3	E1	E2	
SCORE	58	69	69	64	63	85	71	72	67	
	E3	E4	E5	EN1	EN2	EN3	S1	S2	S3	S4
	82	76	64	65	69	67	71	76	67	68

FIGURE 14: BARRIER PRIORITIZATION IN ITALY

The survey conducted among Italian stakeholders regarding the EE barriers of heritage buildings illuminates the multifaceted challenges of improving energy performance within

historic edifices. In this assessment, the focus on bureaucratic hurdles, high upfront costs, scarcity of public financial support, and the absence of consensus among stakeholders encapsulates the core barriers, as distinguished by their barrier codes L2, E3, E4, and S2, respectively (see Table 4).

FIGURE 15: BARRIER EXPOSURE ANALYSIS ACROSS ENERGY PLANNING PHASES AND STAKEHOLDER GROUPS (ITALY)

Significantly, none of these barriers were deemed prominent during the phase of implementation and monitoring. This absence of highlighted barriers during the final phase may suggest that once the initial stages of planning, design, and decision-making are

successfully navigated, the path to actualizing EE improvements faces fewer obstacles. Alternatively, it may reflect a lack of data or insight into this final phase due to its ongoing nature or a potential underestimation of the challenges inherent in the practical application of plans and monitoring their effectiveness.

TABLE 4 - INTEGRATED RESULTS (ITALY)

ITALY						
Barrier Code	Overall Relevance Score	Exposed groups (Relative Comparison (+ 1))	Scenario	Enabler (abs max)	Mitigator (abs max)	Change Agents (abs max)
L2	85	Heritage owners + Advisory intermediaries	Phase 2, Phase 3	Heritage occupant	Installers/contractors	Regulators
E3	82	Heritage owners	Phase 1, Phase 3	Heritage occupant	Advisory intermediaries	Regulators
E4	76	Heritage owners	Phase 1, Phase 3			
S2	76	Heritage owners	Phase 1	Heritage occupant	Installers/contractors	Advisory intermediaries

As mapped at the problem tree (see Figure 16), heritage owners emerge as the most exposed group across all phases. The prominence of advisory intermediaries as exposed stakeholders, particularly in Phase 2, suggests that the technical and procedural complexities encountered in this phase and the consequential reliance on specialized knowledge to navigate them. The vulnerability of owners and advisory intermediaries during the initial phases intimates a significant demand for expert guidance and support from the outset of EE projects. Occupants of heritage buildings are recognized as key enablers throughout the process. Their continuous interaction with the building enables them to contribute valuable insights into the practical aspects of its daily operation, which can be crucial in identifying inefficiencies and supporting the prioritization and application of EE measures. This acknowledgment may carry significant weight, as it suggests that the occupants' experiential knowledge is not only acknowledged but also relied upon to drive energy improvements. Mitigators of barriers, primarily installers and contractors, exhibit a significant presence across various stages. Their technical expertise and practical experience in implementing energy solutions make them pivotal in addressing barriers. Additionally, advisory intermediaries appear as mitigators, likely offering necessary guidance and insights to navigate the complexities inherent in retrofitting heritage buildings. This highlights the importance of technical knowledge and sector-specific advice in dealing with barriers such as bureaucratic hurdles and the absence of consensus. Change agents are predominantly identified as regulators and, to a lesser extent, advisory intermediaries. Regulators are crucial in creating and reforming policies to facilitate EE projects. Their role as change agents

indicates a recognition that the policy environment can be a significant driver of or obstacle to energy conservation in heritage buildings. It suggests that regulatory frameworks must evolve to accommodate the unique challenges of retrofitting heritage buildings without compromising their historical value.

FIGURE 16: PROBLEM TREE (ITALY)

Comparing Italian to global survey results on EE in heritage buildings reveals commonalities and differences in stakeholder roles. Heritage occupants, regulators, and advisory intermediaries are pivotal both in Italy and globally, reflecting a shared recognition of the complex retrofitting challenges. The Italian data, however, highlights a specific need for greater collaboration with heritage occupants and owners and suggests that enhancing connections between advisors and regulators could better address economic barriers.

From the Italian data in relation to the overall survey results, one can infer that while the types of barriers may be consistent, the roles and influence of stakeholders are shaped by the local context. In Italy, there seems to be a particularly acute need for collaborative efforts that involve heritage occupants and owners more deeply in the retrofitting process to enable a smoother transition toward EE. The results also imply that fostering a stronger nexus between advisory intermediaries and regulators could help mitigate economic barriers more effectively.

4.3.3 Portugal

The survey data from Portugal, collected from a balanced mix of nine stakeholders, offers crucial insights for the Herit4ages project, highlighting the unique interplay of roles within the energy retrofitting of heritage buildings. The participating stakeholders from Portugal included advisory bodies, intermediaries, building management operators, and regulators, each providing perspectives that contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the retrofitting challenges specific to the Portuguese context.

BARRIER ID	T1	T2	T3	T4	L1	L2	L3	E1		
SCORE	78	75	69	72	64	81	75	72		
	E3	E4	E5	EN1	EN2	EN3	S1	S2	S3	S4
	81	81	72	75	78	75	78	67	67	69

FIGURE 17: BARRIER PRIORITIZATION IN PORTUGAL

The survey conducted among Portuguese stakeholders to identify barriers to EE in heritage buildings offers a nuanced understanding of the challenges and dynamics involved in this sector. Through this examination, a range of barriers, including technical, legal, economic, environmental, and social, were highlighted as obstacles in the pursuit of EE in heritage buildings (see Table 5).

FIGURE 18: BARRIER EXPOSURE ANALYSIS ACROSS ENERGY PLANNING PHASES AND STAKEHOLDER GROUPS (PORTUGAL)

The most significant barriers, as scored by the respondents, are bureaucratic hurdles (L2) along with high upfront costs (E3) and limited access to public financial support (E4). Among the other significant barriers are Technical barriers, such as the complexity of technology dependent on specific competencies (T1) and structural constraints in conservation-compatible retrofit solutions (T2), along with legal barriers like preservation regulations safeguarding historical values (L3) or environmental and social barriers like installation-related impacts (EN1), long-term visual and landscape impacts (EN2), system inefficiency's impact on the carbon footprint (EN3), and lack of awareness or interest (S1). These barriers were not uniformly prominent across all phases of EE projects. Technical barriers (T1 and T2) appear during the phases two and three, signaling the intricate nature of retrofitting heritage buildings with modern technology. These are the phases where practical solutions are sought and detailed plans are drawn up, requiring high technical expertise. While Legal barriers (L2 and L3) emerge in the later stages, underscoring the challenge of navigating preservation regulations and bureaucratic processes when actual changes are being enacted.

TABLE 5 - INTEGRATED RESULTS (PORTUGAL)

PORTUGAL						
Barrier Code	Overall Relevance Score	Vulnerable groups (Relative Comparison (+ 1))	Scenario	Enabler (abs max)	Mitigator (abs max)	Change Agents (abs max)
T1	78	Installer/Contractor	Phase 2, Phase 3	Heritage owners, Heritage occupants	Advisory Intermediaries	Advisory body
T2	75	Installer/Contractor	Phase 2, Phase 3			
L2	81	Heritage owners	Phase 3, Phase 4	Heritage occupant	BMO	Advisory body
L3	75	Advisory Intermediaries + Heritage owners	Phase 3, Phase 4			
E3	81	Heritage owners	Phase 1, Phase 2, Phase 3	Heritage occupant	Advisory Intermediaries, Suppliers, Advisory body	Heritage owner, Financiers
E4	81	Heritage owners	Phase 1			
EN1	75	Heritage owners + Heritage occupants, Installer/Contractor	Phase 2, Phase 4	Installer/Contractor	BMO	Advisory body, Regulators
EN2	78	Heritage owners + BMO, Advisory Intermediaries	Phase 3, Phase 4			
EN3	75	Advisory Intermediaries + Heritage owners	Phase 3, Phase 4			

S1	78	Heritage owners	Phase 1, Phase 2	Heritage owner, Installer/Contractor	Advisory Intermediaries	Regulators
----	----	-----------------	------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------	------------

The problem tree (see Figure 19) visualizes that exposed groups, such as heritage owners, were consistently highlighted across all phases, indicating their central role and the challenges they face at every stage of the EE process. Owners are crucial in both their responsibility for making decisions and their potential to be impacted by the barriers due to their financial and emotional investment in the properties. Installers and contractors also emerged as particularly exposed during the latter three phases, possibly due to their direct involvement in the implementation of energy-efficient solutions and the technical and regulatory challenges they face.

FIGURE 19: PROBLEM TREE (PORTUGAL)

Conversely, these exposed groups were also identified as enablers, especially installers/contractors, occupants, and owners indicating their potential to support the pursuit of EE through their actions and choices. This dual role as both exposed to and enablers of EE barriers highlights the complex interplay of different stakeholder groups within the heritage building sector.

Mitigators are vital in easing the barriers, with advisory intermediaries, building management operators, advisory bodies, and suppliers taking this role at varying phases. The fluctuating presence of mitigators throughout the project phases suggests the need for targeted strategies to address specific barriers as they become prominent at different stages. This understanding can guide the formulation of interventions that are timely and contextually relevant.

Change agents, notably regulators, consistently play a crucial role throughout all project phases. Their influence can pave the way for overcoming barriers through policymaking, regulation adjustments, and providing incentives. The involvement of other change agents, such as owners, advisory bodies, and financiers, demonstrates the importance of a multi-stakeholder approach in effecting sustainable change in the sector.

Comparing the results from Portugal with the general survey findings, it appears that while the identified barriers are consistent across regions, the roles and influence of stakeholders vary. The role of stakeholders - particularly heritage owners and advisory intermediaries - emerges clearly from both surveys. They are consistently challenged by the complex interplay of barriers, which is reflective of their vulnerability in both contexts. Their difficulties underscore the need for support systems and strategic interventions tailored to mitigate the identified barriers. In the broader survey, just as in the Portuguese scenario, regulators and financiers are recognized as key change agents, emphasizing the importance of policy and financial frameworks in facilitating energy-efficient retrofits. However, there are also some differences. In the general survey, legal barriers are indicated as prominent during the first three phases, which include the early stages of preparation and decision-making. In contrast, the Portuguese survey indicates that legal barriers (L2 and L3) are more prominent during phases three and four, suggesting that these issues become more critical later in the process when decisions are being enacted, and the projects are in the implementation phase. Economic barriers are consistently a challenge in both surveys, but the Portuguese survey highlights their relevance across the first three phases, while the general survey suggests they are predominant particularly during the initial preparation and decision-making stages. This could indicate a heightened awareness or sensitivity to financial issues from the outset in the general context. Environmental impacts are significant in both surveys but are emphasized during the implementation and monitoring phase in the general survey, whereas in the Portuguese context, they are spread across phases two, three, and four, indicating a broader span of concern about the environmental aspects during the project lifecycle.

Data from Portugal underscores the need for a strategic approach that capitalizes on the strengths of each stakeholder group to foster collaborative and effective energy retrofitting in heritage buildings. This approach must balance the need for technical expertise, streamlined regulatory processes, and robust financial models to create sustainable, culturally respectful retrofitting solutions.

4.3.4 Spain

The Spanish survey results, encompassing a varied group of ten stakeholders, provide a nuanced understanding of the energy retrofitting landscape in the region, an essential component of the Herit4ages project. With input from advisory intermediaries, building management operators, heritage occupants, installers/contractors, and suppliers, the dataset reveals the specific challenges and roles within Spain’s heritage retrofitting sector.

FIGURE 20: SYNTHESIS OF BARRIER ANALYSIS IN SPAIN

FIGURE 21: BARRIER EXPOSURE ANALYSIS ACROSS ENERGY PLANNING PHASES AND STAKEHOLDER GROUPS (SPAIN)

According to the survey's results, barriers to EE in heritage buildings are complex and varied (see Table 6). The most highlighted barriers included bureaucratic hurdles like regulatory approvals (L2), structural constraints and complexity in retrofit solutions (T2), the absence of universal solutions (T3), and scarcity of public financial support (E4). Additionally, stakeholders contended with the demand for specialized materials (T4), stringent preservation regulations (L3), and financial challenges such as investment playback time (E1), high upfront costs (E3), and concerns related to installation impacts like noise and waste (EN1), long-term visual and landscape impacts (EN2), and the inefficiency of systems affecting the carbon footprint (EN3).

TABLE 6 - INTEGRATED RESULTS (SPAIN)

SPAIN						
Barrier Code	Overall Relevance Score	Exposed groups (Relative Comparison (+ 1))	Scenario	Enabler (abs max)	Mitigator (abs max)	Change Agents (abs max)
T2	80	BMO + Heritage owners, Advisory Intermediaries	Phase 2, Phase 3	Regulators	BMO	Advisory Intermediaries, Suppliers
T3	80	Heritage owners	Phase 1, Phase 3			
T4	75	Heritage owners + Suppliers	Phase 4			
L2	83	Advisory Intermediaries + Heritage owners	Phase 1, Phase 3	Heritage occupant, Regulators, Financiers, BMO, Installer/Contractor, Advisory body	Advisory Intermediaries, Suppliers	Advisory body
L3	78	Heritage owners	Phase 1, Phase 3			
E1	75	Heritage owners	Phase 1, Phase 3	Installer/Contractor, BMO	Advisory Intermediaries	Financiers
E3	75	Heritage owners	Phase 1			
E4	80	Heritage owners	Phase 1			
EN2	78	Heritage owners + Heritage occupants	Phase 2	Heritage occupant	Heritage owners, Advisory bodies	Suppliers

EN3	75	Heritage owners	Phase 2, Phase 4			
-----	----	-----------------	------------------	--	--	--

Vulnerability among stakeholder groups was predominantly noted in heritage owners throughout all project phases (see Figure 22). This could be attributed to the inherent responsibilities they bear, from maintaining the integrity of their heritage buildings to balancing the financial and practical aspects of EE measures. Advisory intermediaries also emerged as exposed, particularly in the early to mid-phases of projects. This vulnerability may be linked to their role in navigating between different stakeholders and regulations, which can be fraught with complexities and opposing interests.

Regulators and heritage occupants are primarily identified as enablers across all phases of EE projects. Regulators, for instance, while they hold the power to facilitate improvements through policy adjustments, can also reinforce barriers through stringent regulations that do not account for the unique challenges of retrofitting heritage buildings. Heritage occupants, through their daily practices, may unintentionally perpetuate energy inefficiencies, particularly if there is a lack of awareness or incentive to adopt more efficient habits or technologies. Similarly, building management operators, installers/contractors, and financiers could also act as enablers of barriers if their operations, installation choices, or investment strategies do not align with EE goals or if they lack the knowledge of conservation-compatible solutions. Their active participation is crucial in overcoming the myriad of technical, legal, and financial barriers that typically arise. These enabler groups, with their diverse yet complementary roles, underscore the importance of creating synergies among stakeholders to foster an environment conducive to the realization of energy-efficient heritage buildings.

FIGURE 22: PROBLEM TREE (SPAIN)

In the context of the Spanish stakeholders' survey, building management operators emerged as prominent mitigators, instrumental in their ability to identify and apply practical and feasible solutions to EE barriers. Their expertise allows them to propose modifications that respect both the architectural integrity of heritage sites and the need for modern energy standards. Other stakeholder groups, including advisory intermediaries, heritage owners, suppliers, and advisory bodies, contribute to mitigation efforts to varying degrees. Their collective actions often include advocating for policy adjustments, offering technical advice, supplying appropriate materials, and navigating the financial landscape to support EE projects. These stakeholders' mitigatory actions appear most effective when barriers - be it technical, legal, or economic—are most pronounced. Advisory intermediaries and suppliers emerge as prominent change agents, leveraging their expert knowledge and market influence to introduce innovative solutions and practices. Their actions often bridge the gap between the preservation of heritage and the implementation of modern energy-efficient technologies. Financiers and advisory bodies complement this transformative role by providing the necessary financial backing and policy advocacy to support such initiatives. The effectiveness of these change agents is most evident in phases where barriers are most pronounced, suggesting a strategic focus on overcoming the most critical challenges. Their proactive engagement not only addresses immediate barriers but also sets a precedent for

long-term adaptive change, providing a blueprint for other stakeholders aiming to balance heritage preservation with environmental sustainability.

Comparing the survey results from Spain with the general results, it seems that heritage owners and advisory intermediaries emerge as central figures in both surveys, consistently grappling with the intricacies of retrofitting heritage structures within the confines of existing regulatory, environmental, and financial frameworks. Furthermore, in both contexts, advisory intermediaries are pivotal in mediating between the technical feasibility of energy solutions and the preservation of historical integrity, indicating a universally multifaceted role. Moreover, there is a general trend, where heritage owners are seen as both aware of EE benefits, yet constrained by the complexities associated with implementing upgrades. However, there are some differences. In the Spanish survey, there is a significant emphasis on the technical barriers such as the complexity of conservation-compatible retrofit solutions (T2) and the absence of universal retrofit solutions (T3), which are not as explicitly detailed in the general survey. The Spanish stakeholders also face a pronounced challenge with the demand for scarce heritage-compatible materials (T4), whereas the general survey does not single out this issue. Regarding enablers, Spanish regulators, occupants, and other management operators are identified as having a more active role in supporting the transition towards EE across all phases. The general survey, meanwhile, highlights heritage occupants' consistent support but does not as strongly feature regulators or management operators.

Survey results for Spain underscore the intricate interplay between different stakeholders and barriers across the phases of enhancing EE in heritage buildings. The findings illuminate not just the obstacles but also the dynamics of vulnerability, enablement, mitigation, and change agency that shape the landscape of EE in heritage structures. These insights from Spain reinforce the imperative for a collaborative and context-sensitive approach that harnesses the strengths of each stakeholder group. Such a strategy will be pivotal in advancing the shared objectives of energy efficiency and cultural heritage preservation under the Herit4ages project.

5. Policy Framework of Energy Efficiency of Heritage Buildings

The policy framework for enhancing EE in heritage buildings encompasses a complex layer of considerations, central to which is the balance between preserving cultural value and advancing sustainability goals. A multi-governmental approach is instrumental in this context, underscoring the importance of coordinated efforts across various levels of governance—from the European Union's overarching policies to national, regional, and local initiatives. The European Union sets the tone with directives and funding mechanisms aimed at improving EE while respecting the historical integrity of buildings. However, the implementation of these policies relies heavily on the adaptability and innovation at the national, regional, and local levels, where specific heritage considerations and energy-saving targets can vary significantly. This comprehensive analysis serves as a foundational basis for mapping out governance mechanisms, highlighting the need for an integrated policy framework that considers the unique energy behaviors of heritage buildings. By doing so, decision-makers could be equipped with a holistic understanding that enables the formulation and implementation of measures tailored to unlock the energy-saving potential of these buildings.

5.1 Methodology of the analysis

The methodology employed in analyzing the Policy Framework of EE of Heritage has a systematic approach to data collection and classification.

The initial phase of this research entailed a desktop review of active European policies, which provided understanding of the regulatory landscape pertaining to EE in heritage buildings and regulatory background. This was crucial to grasp the broader context before delving into more localized settings. In-depth examination was made of active national, regional, and local policy measures at pilot sites level: Italy, Spain, Estonia, and Portugal. The policies were selected to ensure intersection across the domains of cultural heritage, EE, renovation or retrofitting, and energy behavior.

To ensure the relevance of identified policies, the research methodology included validation processes at the pilot sites, engaging local experts in the assessment. The local experts were requested to assign specific attributes to the policies identified, enabling a nuanced understanding of their operational scope and potential impact. These attributes encompassed type of policy measures such as regulatory, Financial and Fiscal, Information campaigns, Labelling and voluntary agreements, as outlined in the European Commission's

Guidance for National Energy Efficiency Action Plans²; type of compliance such as affirmative (promoting) and negative (restricting) and level of abstraction such as High-level (general policy goals), Mid-level (policy objectives) and Low-level (specific policy settings). The attribution of stakeholders and the various phases of energy planning were consistent with previous sections, contributing to the coherence of the report. The gathered data was organized visually in graphs and diagrams for clarity, connecting to a 'problem tree' developed in earlier sections, thereby presenting a cohesive narrative of the issues at hand.

However, the research acknowledges some limitations. The policies studied were those found with the help of local experts, so there might be additional relevant policies not included in this report. This limitation frames the findings presented in the subsequent sections, emphasizing that while comprehensive, they are based on the information available and validated through this collaborative approach.

The findings from analysis of EE policies in heritage buildings are presented in a structured two-part format. Initially, there will be a comprehensive presentation of the European regulatory framework, detailing the overarching policies that set the stage for energy conservation in heritage buildings. Following this, the focus will shift to the pilot site countries. The policies identified within these local contexts—Italy, Spain, Estonia, and Portugal—will be systematically listed and thoroughly examined. This examination will assess how the interplay between various policy measures and compliance motivations manifests in practice and the implications this has for the safeguarding and energy management of heritage sites. The sections aim to offer a clear and comparative insight into the similarities and differences across these regulatory landscapes, considering the localized nuances that inform their implementation.

5.2 European Policy Instruments

The European Union has been at the forefront of integrating climate goals, demonstrating a complex landscape where policy, EE, and heritage conservation intersect. The focus on energy-efficient retrofitting of existing buildings, including historic ones, reflects a significant policy direction at both national and international levels. The EE in historic buildings is an extremely sensitive issue. The EU's ambition to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, coupled with its commitment to improve EE by at least 32.5% by 2030, lays a solid foundation for integrating sustainable practices with cultural heritage preservation. Previously, it aimed to achieve the so-called 20-20-20 targets, including a 20% improvement in EE, which was successfully accomplished. This integration is not without its challenges, as the retrofitting of historic buildings for EE demands a careful balance between modern

² European Commission, "Guidance for National Energy Efficiency Action Plans Accompanying the document COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION establishing a template for National Energy Efficiency Action Plans under Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and the Council /* SWD/2013/0180 final */," Brussels, 6.11.2013. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52013SC0180>

energy standards and the preservation of architectural and cultural integrity. The complexity of this task is mirrored in the multifaceted policy instruments the EU has developed, which aim to address both the preservation of cultural heritage and the enhancement of EE across Member States.

The EU's ambition to become climate neutral by 2050 has catalyzed enacting a series of policy measures and regulations, addressing new and existing buildings to make them more energy efficient and reduce CO2 emissions. The European Union employs a variety of policy instruments to pursue its objectives, and facilitate cooperation among its Member states.

Mapping European Policy Instruments for EE and cultural heritage energy retrofit reveals a complex framework that attempts to reconcile the need for sustainable energy use with the imperative to safeguard Europe's rich historical legacy. These policy instruments, shaped by the EU's broader climate and energy goals, encapsulate a range of directives, funding mechanisms, and collaborative frameworks designed to guide and support the energy retrofitting of buildings, including those with historical value. Notably, the intricate framework of European policy instruments attempts to navigate the delicate act of enhancing EE without compromising the unique characteristics that define Europe's cultural heritage buildings. This delicate balance is achieved through a combination of regulatory measures, incentives, and guidelines that encourage the adoption of energy-efficient technologies and practices, while also providing for the conservation of historic structures.

The forthcoming review of key EU policies provides a critical opportunity to evaluate the current policy framework's capacity to embrace these challenges, offering insights into potential areas for improvement and innovation. This evaluation is not just about assessing policy efficacy but also about envisioning a future where sustainable energy use and cultural heritage conservation coalesce into a unified strategy for achieving climate neutrality and preserving Europe's rich historical tapestry for generations to come.

5.2.1 European Directives

The European Directives are very broad legislative instruments describing objectives to be fulfilled by Member States and, at the same time, allowing national policymakers a margin of choice regarding appropriate approaches to be used in fulfilling the given objectives. This then makes it the part of the national legislatures to transpose these EU directives into domestic law, reflecting varied national priorities, and to delineate procedures for bureaucratic execution.

The two principal European Union Directives that are predominantly concerned with EE include The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) and The Energy Efficiency Directive (EED). These legislative measures are pivotal in setting the framework for

enhancing energy performance across the EU, focusing significantly on the renovation of existing building stock and the integration of advanced technical elements and systems to improve EE. However, a critical gap identified in these Directives is their lack of explicit guidelines or provisions for the retrofitting of historic buildings. This oversight implies a nuanced challenge within the domain of EE, where the unique characteristics and preservation needs of historic structures necessitate a tailored approach.

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive

The European Commission has taken significant steps to reduce energy consumption within the EU through the implementation of two pivotal Energy Performance of Buildings Directives: Directive 2002/91/EC and its subsequent recasting, Directive 2010/31/EU, commonly referred to as the EPBD. The initial directive, Directive 2002/91/EC, focused primarily on establishing methodologies for new constructions, the recast EPBD, Directive 2010/31/EU, shifted this focus towards existing buildings, acknowledging the importance of major renovations and the retrofitting or replacement of building technical elements and technical systems.

To further bolster EE, the Directive mandates EU countries to establish long-term renovation strategies, set cost-optimal minimum energy performance requirements, and ensure that, since 2021, all new buildings meet NZEB standards. Additional measures include the issuance of energy performance certificates upon the sale or rental of buildings and the implementation of inspection schemes for heating and air conditioning systems. In addressing the renovation of existing buildings, the EPBD emphasizes the need for ambitious mandatory energy performance standards to minimize energy needs through deep renovation and to facilitate the integration of RE. Moreover, the Directive includes provisions for the phased introduction of minimum energy performance standards for non-residential buildings, national trajectories to reduce primary energy use in residential buildings, and an enhanced standard for new buildings to achieve zero-emission status. Financial incentives are also outlined to support the EE of buildings, alongside strategies for modernizing building systems for better energy system integration.

This directive not only prioritizes the enhancement of energy performance in existing structures but also introduces the concept of nearly zero energy buildings (NZEBs; art.9 EPBD). NZEBs are characterized by their very high energy performance, with the minimal amount of energy they require predominantly sourced from renewable energies. The directive fosters the integration of smart technologies, such as building automation systems, IoT devices, and advanced energy management systems, to optimize energy use and support the achievement of NZEB standards.

Special consideration is given to historical or listed buildings, acknowledging that applying certain requirements might pose challenges. However, adherence to these standards is not

expected to alter the heritage buildings' character, ensuring a balanced approach to preserving their integrity while promoting EE. Therefore, Member States have the discretion to exempt certain buildings from the requirements outlined in EPBD, specifically officially recognized for their historical or architectural significance within a protected area, where adhering to specific minimum energy performance standards could compromise their character or appearance in an unacceptable manner (art. 4 EPBD).

In 2021, the European Commission set forth a proposal to revise EPBD, reflecting a pivotal moment in the EU's journey towards elevated climate ambitions as delineated in the European Green Deal. By December 2023, a provisional agreement on EPBD revision was reached between the European Parliament and the Council. The revision introduces a suite of measures designed to boost the energy performance of buildings significantly. Key among these is the establishment of national trajectories by Member States, targeting a reduction in the average primary energy use of residential buildings by 16% by 2030 and between 20-22% by 2035. Furthermore, the directive sets forth provisions to gradually elevate the energy performance of non-residential buildings through minimum energy performance standards, aiming for the renovation of a significant portion of the worst-performing buildings by 2030 and 2033. To support informed decisions and financing, improved Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) based on a common EU template will be introduced, alongside measures to combat energy poverty and support renovations targeted at vulnerable customers and poorly performing buildings. It establishes national Building Renovation Plans, building renovation passport schemes, and one-stop-shops to provide comprehensive support to building owners, SMEs, and stakeholders involved in the renovation process. It introduces a zero emissions standard for new buildings, requiring all new residential and non-residential buildings to have zero on-site emissions from fossil fuels by specific dates. The directive also mandates that new buildings be solar-ready, fostering the norm of installing solar energy installations on new constructions.

Following the provisional agreement, the subsequent steps include the formal adoption of the revised directive by both the European Parliament and the Council. Once this legislative process is successfully completed, the new legislation is slated to be published in the Official Journal of the European Union and will thereafter enter into force. The timeline for these developments is targeted for the first half of 2024, marking a critical phase in the EU's legislative procedure aimed at enhancing the EE and reducing the GHG emissions of buildings across the Union.

The Energy Efficiency Directive

EPBD and its recasting set the stage for member states to focus on energy-saving interventions in existing buildings, culminating further in the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) of 2012 (2012/27/EU), a pivotal piece of legislation that aimed for a 20% increase in EE by 2020. Recognizing the need for more ambitious targets, the Directive was amended in

2018 (EU 2018/2002) and in 2023 (EU 2023/1791), setting a new goal of improving EE by at least 32.5% by the year 2030 across the EU-27 and further nearly doubled the energy savings obligations, mandating member states to achieve a 1.49% annual reduction in final energy consumption from 2024 to 2030. The timeline of the directive's evolution from 2012 to 2023 reflects a journey towards higher EE standards, with notable milestones including the formal agreement of the revised directive in July 2023 and the proposal for its recast as part of the EU Green Deal package in July 2021. This journey underscores the EU's commitment to decreasing dependency on fossil fuel imports and addressing the challenges posed by climate change.

The new EED, emphasizing the "energy efficiency first" principle as a cornerstone of EU energy policy. This principle advocates for fulfilling energy needs with less energy, aiming to reduce costs, dependence on imported fossil fuels, and CO₂ emissions. This directive mandates EU Member States to incorporate the new objectives into their National Energy and Climate Plans and transpose the directive into national legislation within two years. It establishes a legally-binding target to reduce the EU's final energy consumption by 11.7% by 2030 compared to the 2020 reference scenario, with an annual energy saving increase from 1.3% during 2024-2025 to 1.9% from 2028. These efforts are bolstered by enhanced measures to alleviate energy poverty, empower consumers through increased awareness and information, and improve regulations to encourage EE renovations.

For the industrial sector, the EED expands energy audit obligations and mandates energy management systems for large consumers to foster optimization of EE. It also requires Member states to ensure a high level of competence among EE professionals and mandates reporting on EE investments to enhance transparency and accountability. Additionally, EED addresses heating and cooling as well as data centres, aiming for a fully decarbonised district heating and cooling supply by 2050 and introducing monitoring obligations for data centres to assess their energy performance and water footprint.

The EED notably addresses building renovations, urging member states to devise long-term strategies to mobilize investment in renovating both public and private residential and commercial buildings. It specifies an annual renovation rate of 3% for buildings owned and occupied by central government, ensuring compliance with minimum energy performance requirements as per Article 4 of EPBD.

Particularly noteworthy is the directive's provision for historical buildings (art.6 EED). Recognizing the unique challenges and constraints associated with upgrading the EE of buildings of historical or architectural merit, the EU directives afford member states the latitude to exempt such structures from the stringent application of certain energy performance requirements. This exemption is predicated on the understanding that enforcing these requirements on historical buildings could lead to undesirable alterations in

their character or appearance, thus balancing the need for EE with the preservation of cultural and architectural heritage.

5.2.1 *European Green Deal*

The European Green Deal represents a cornerstone in the European Union's ambitious plan to become the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. Announced on December 11, 2019, by the European Commission, the European Green Deal is an ambitious blueprint aimed at transforming the EU's economy. It encompasses a broad spectrum of initiatives targeted at reducing GHG emissions, decarbonizing the energy sector, and enhancing the EE of buildings, among other goals. One of the key objectives is to reduce the EU's net GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, marking a significant increase from the previous target of a 40% reduction and serving as a critical milestone on the path to achieving climate neutrality by 2050. Additionally, the European Green Deal seeks to significantly increase the use of RE across the EU, with the *"Fit for 55"* package setting a roadmap to reduce the EU's GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels. Improving the EU's EE by at least 32.5% by 2030 is another aim, with the potential to further increase this target, emphasizing the importance of EE measures in reducing overall energy consumption and lowering emissions. Integral to the Green Deal is the **Renovation Wave strategy**, which aims to at least double renovation rates in the next decade and ensure that renovations lead to higher energy and resource efficiency. This ambitious initiative targets the renovation of 35 million buildings by 2030, a move that is expected not only to enhance EE but also stimulate economic growth and job creation. Furthermore, the Social Climate Fund, established under the 'Fit for 55' package, allocates significant financial resources to support vulnerable citizens and small businesses in the green transition, including through investments in EE and building renovation.

The European Green Deal and the "Fit for 55" package imply several obligations for member countries, particularly in integrating these ambitious targets into their national policies. Member states are required to draft, update, and implement National Energy and Climate Plans that align with the overarching goals of the European Green Deal and the "Fit for 55" package. These plans must detail how each country intends to contribute to the 2030 targets for emissions reduction, RE uptake, EE, and other key areas. Countries are obligated to facilitate the renovation of 35 million buildings by 2030, as outlined in the Renovation Wave strategy. This includes implementing national policies that encourage or mandate EE upgrades in both private and public buildings, including heritage buildings. Member states are encouraged to integrate the objectives of the European Green Deal into their own sustainable development strategies, ensuring coherence between national and EU-level efforts. Member states are expected to invest in environmentally friendly technologies and infrastructure, supported by funding mechanisms like the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Cohesion Fund, among others. These investments are crucial for

decarbonizing the energy sector, developing sustainable transport, and enhancing EE. The "Fit for 55" package involves updates to existing EU directives and regulations, such as the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS), the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), and EED. Member states must transpose these revised directives into national law and ensure compliance across sectors.

5.2.2 *European Frameworks*

European frameworks encompass a variety of structures designed to guide and regulate activities within the European Union, spanning both legislative and conceptual domains. Legislative frameworks set forth binding legal guidelines and standards for specific policy areas, directly influencing member states' laws and regulations. On the other hand, conceptual frameworks offer an overarching structure for understanding and addressing complex issues, though they are not binding. Together, these frameworks play a crucial role in shaping policies, strategies, and actions across the EU, aiming to harmonize practices, promote common goals, and address shared challenges within the Union.

In October 2014, the European Council approved the **2030 Climate and Energy Framework**, setting forth ambitious EU-wide targets and policy objectives for the 2020 to 2030 period to transition towards a more competitive, secure, and sustainable energy system. This framework, originating from the Commission's proposal in January 2014, aims to reduce GHG emissions by at least 40% compared to 1990 levels, increase the EE to at least 27% compared with the business-as-usual scenario. It includes a reformed EU emissions trading scheme (ETS) and introduces new indicators for assessing the competitiveness and security of the energy system. The framework emphasizes the need for a new governance system based on national energy and climate plans, fostering greater transparency, policy coherence, and coordination across the EU. This strategic move also addresses energy security concerns by advocating for the completion of internal energy market interconnections and supporting measures to reduce the EU's energy dependence. The 2030 framework builds on the momentum of the 2020 climate and energy package, aligning with long-term visions such as the Roadmap for moving to a competitive low carbon economy in 2050 and the Energy Roadmap 2050. It represents a balanced approach to environmental sustainability, economic competitiveness, and energy security.

The **European Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage**, aligned with the new European Agenda for Culture, adopted following the European Year of Cultural Heritage in 2018, signifies the EU's dedication to nurturing a sustainable future that harmonizes EE with the preservation of cultural heritage. It seeks to guide heritage-related activities at the European level, urging Member States to adopt similar frameworks to bolster cultural heritage preservation. Within this comprehensive strategy, specific attention is paid to safeguarding cultural heritage against the adverse effects of natural disasters and climate change. The

initiative to enhance the structural resilience of historical buildings to earthquakes, goes hand in hand with efforts to improve their EE. Furthermore, between 2019 and 2020, a group of experts from EU Member States, convened under the Open Method of Coordination, embarked on a mission to explore innovative policy measures that address the impact of climate change on heritage sites.

5.2.3 European Strategies

The intertwining of EE with cultural heritage preservation underpins the European Union's strategic approach to fostering a sustainable, resilient future. This intricate balance is navigated through a suite of strategic frameworks, each outlining the Union's commitment to sustainable development, heritage conservation, and EE.

Central to the EU's energy policy is the **Energy Union Strategy**, introduced in 2015, which targets a radical transformation of Europe's energy system. The strategy prioritizes EE, recognizing it as essential to achieving the EU's broader objectives of reducing energy dependence, curbing emissions, and promoting economic growth. It establishes ambitious goals for reducing energy consumption across all sectors, underscoring the adoption of the "energy efficiency first" principle. This principle not only pertains to the energy system but extends across the entire economy, advocating for energy savings from production through to final consumption. Specific measures include reforming the EU emissions trading scheme and enhancing the energy performance of buildings and transport, highlighting EE as a cornerstone of the EU's path towards a competitive, secure, and sustainable energy future.

The Renovation Wave Strategy directly targets the building sector, the largest single energy consumer in Europe, with the aim of doubling renovation rates by 2030. This strategy is pivotal in reducing energy consumption in buildings, many of which hold significant cultural and historical value. By focusing on energy renovation, the strategy aligns with the goals of preserving Europe's architectural heritage while moving towards an energy-neutral future. The strategy emphasizes the need for smart and sustainable renovation practices that respect the architectural integrity of historic buildings, ensuring that EE improvements are compatible with heritage conservation. One of the core targets of the Renovation Wave is to double the annual energy renovation rate of buildings by 2030. This means increasing the current rate from around 1% to 2%, significantly accelerating the pace at which Europe's building stock becomes more energy efficient. By 2030, the strategy aims to have renovated 35 million buildings to be more energy efficient. This initiative is expected to significantly reduce energy bills, improve living conditions, and create jobs, thereby contributing to the EU's climate objectives and economic recovery.

5.2.4 European Standards and Guidelines

Recognizing the unique challenges posed by historic buildings, the European Directives afford Member States the latitude to exempt buildings of historical or architectural significance from the stringent requirements outlined in them. This exemption acknowledges that meeting specific energy performance standards could, in some cases, adversely affect the character or appearance of such buildings. In this situation of the initial lack of specific guidance on retrofitting historic buildings, in place of rigid legislative requirements, an alternative approach through "soft law" instruments as standards and guidelines provides the necessary flexibility, facilitating adaptation to future circumstances and promoting cooperation without imposing stringent commitments.

The European Committee for Standardization (CEN), specifically through **CEN/TC 346** (Conservation of Cultural Property) and WG 8 "Energy Efficiency of Historic Buildings," is advancing the creation of guidelines to improve EE in cultural and historical buildings, aiming for a procedural standard that marries historic preservation with modern energy needs. Initiated in 2001 by UNI, the Italian Standard Body, CEN/TC 346's efforts are in line with European Council directives to enhance cultural heritage preservation through standardized support for conservation professionals. The committee's work has broadened to encapsulate a comprehensive scope that integrates the analysis of materials, deterioration, and environmental impacts with conservation techniques, striving for the preservation and significance of tangible cultural heritage. Despite facing challenges in funding and resource prioritization, CEN/TC 346's standardization efforts, underpinned by collaboration with European and international bodies, aim to unify conservation methodologies, enhance diagnostic practices, and promote the global dissemination of standards, thereby contributing significantly to the sustainable conservation of cultural heritage worldwide.

The European standard **EN 16883:2017**, "Guidelines for Improving the Energy Performance of Historic Buildings," offers an innovative framework that bridges the gap between EE and heritage conservation and marks a pivotal shift in the approach to the energy retrofit of historic buildings. Unveiled by the European Committee in 2017, this standard advocates for a flexible methodology that steers away from mandating a specific outcome. Instead, it provides a strategic roadmap for the planning phase, underscoring the notion that suitable solutions for enhancing EE while preserving heritage values should be tailored to each building's unique circumstances.

EN 16883:2017 first establishes general considerations for the sustainable management of historic buildings, emphasizing the principles of conservation, the qualifications of professionals involved, and a deep understanding of the building envelope, technical systems, and user behavior in relation to energy performance. It then unfolds a comprehensive step-by-step procedure for enhancing EE, starting from the initiation of the planning process, conducting thorough building surveys and assessments, and meticulously

documenting the current state and heritage significance of the building. The process advances by specifying objectives, determining the need for energy performance improvements, and the careful assessment and selection of suitable measures, culminating in the implementation, documentation, and evaluation of these improvements. To support the practical application of these guidelines in real-world contexts, it offered templates and examples, such as a building information template and an assessment table example, ensuring that the standard can be effectively applied across various historic building conservation projects.

5.2.5 Financial instruments

The European Union has placed EE at the core of its strategy to achieve a sustainable, competitive, and secure energy system. Recognizing the critical role of financial support in realizing EE goals, the EU has established a comprehensive suite of financial instruments. These mechanisms are designed to facilitate the investment needed to upgrade infrastructure, implement innovative technologies, and support the transition towards a more energy-efficient and low-carbon economy.

Central to the EU's financing strategy, **European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF)** provides significant funding for EE projects across the Union. This includes support for upgrading building stock, enhancing industrial EE, and investing in smart energy systems at the municipal level. The funds are allocated to member states and are instrumental in supporting national and regional initiatives aimed at reducing energy consumption and carbon footprints. Succeeding Horizon 2020, **Horizon Europe – Cluster 5 (Climate, Energy, and Mobility)** is the EU's flagship research and innovation program. Within Cluster 5, the program focuses on advancing EE through innovation in materials, technology, and social practices. It supports projects that explore new ways of reducing energy use in buildings, industry, and transport, contributing to the EU's climate objectives. Envisioned as a temporary recovery instrument, the **Next Generation EU** is a bold €750 billion package designed to spearhead the economic revival of EU member states, especially those bearing the brunt of the pandemic's impact. The Next Generation EU plan sought to blend grants and loans to facilitate economic recovery and resilience, ultimately culminating in a €750 billion fund that intertwines with the €1.074 trillion to form a comprehensive €1.824 trillion recovery strategy. Central to the Next Generation EU strategy is the **Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)**, encompassing €672.5 billion in loans and grants designed to support member states' investment and reform agendas aligned with EU priorities, including ecological and digital transformations. Dedicated to supporting the EU's clean energy transition, the **LIFE Clean Energy Transition Programme** focuses on building capacities, facilitating the deployment of solutions, and stimulating investment in EE and RE. With a budget of nearly EUR 1 billion for 2021-2027, it addresses the decarbonization of the EU energy system,

promoting EE across various sectors. With its focus on a ‘Smarter Europe’ and ‘Greener Europe,’ the **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) 2021-2027** promotes the adoption of smart technology in buildings and the wider economy. It supports projects that enhance EE, foster sustainable urban development, and contribute to the EU's climate and energy targets. Additionally, established to ensure that the shift towards a green economy is fair and leaves no one behind, the **Just Transition Fund (JTF)** provides targeted support to regions most affected by the transition challenges. With a budget of EUR 17.5 billion for 2021-2027, the fund supports economic diversification, job creation, and the implementation of EE measures in impacted regions, contributing to a socially equitable energy transition. Lastly, a joint initiative by the European Investment Bank and the European Commission, the **European Local Energy Assistance (ELENA)** provides technical assistance for the development and implementation of EE, distributed RE, and urban transport programs. ELENA helps project promoters to build technical, economic, and legal expertise necessary for launching successful investments.

Through these diverse financial instruments, the European Union is making significant strides toward its EE and climate goals. By mobilizing investments in smart, sustainable technologies and practices, the EU not only aims to reduce its energy consumption and GHG emissions but also to drive economic growth, enhance energy security, and improve the quality of life for its citizens. These financial mechanisms underscore the EU's commitment to leading by example in the global transition to a more energy-efficient future.

5.3 National, regional, and local policy instruments

The juxtaposition of national, regional, and local policy instruments against the backdrop of European Union directives presents a rich tapestry for examination in the pursuit of EE within the context of heritage buildings. This section sets out to navigate the complexities inherent in reconciling the imperatives of energy savings with the conservation of historical value. The European Union has established directives primarily focused on enhancing energy savings in existing buildings. However, the specificity required to address heritage buildings, which are repositories of historical value, remains an area requiring further attention. The current European directives do not distinctly define the measures for energy retrofitting that would ensure the preservation of historical buildings, creating a gap that necessitates member states intervention. Across the European Union, member states have indeed embraced the mandate to promote EE. However, not all have directly addressed the unique needs of cultural heritage buildings. Policy instruments vary, with some focusing on sector-specific support or targeting particular regions, while others apply more broadly on a national scale. The goals of these policies range from achieving strict energy or carbon savings to encompassing broader policy objectives.

This section explores policies identified in our case studies at the national, regional, and local levels. This exploration will not only outline the individual and collective impacts of these policies but also seek to uncover their potential impact on stakeholders at different phases of energy planning. Through this evaluation, we shed light on the intricate dance between overarching energy behavior patterns, barriers to energy efficiency and the ground-level actions that play out in the member states, with a view toward achieving a harmonious balance between EE and the preservation of our shared historical heritage.

5.3.1 Estonia

Data on 32 policy instruments, which encompass 19 legal, 10 economic, and 3 informational categories, was collected across various administrative levels: 25 at the national level in Estonia, 3 at the regional level in Tartu County, and 4 at the local level in Tartu City.

Estonia's regulatory landscape for EE appears to be a complex mosaic of strategies and measures, tentatively aimed at fostering sustainable energy use, especially within the realm of infrastructure. As inferred from Figure 23, policy instruments seemingly converge at the nexus of EE and cultural heritage, suggesting a considerate approach that tentatively balances the imperatives of energy conservation with the preservation of heritage assets. It seems that there has been a discernible, albeit gradual, escalation in policy initiatives across several layers of governance, embracing a spectrum of interventions including financial incentives, regulatory mandates, awareness campaigns, and voluntary agreements. The concentration of policy activity coinciding with pivotal EU directives and frameworks like the EPBD Recast, EED, and the EU Green Deal tentatively suggests an alignment with the

expansive legislative efforts of the European Union to promote EE. Furthermore, the regulatory framework's emphasis on both rewarding compliance and enforcing penalties may indicate an attempt at a balanced regulatory approach, potentially enhancing compliance through a combination of incentives and obligations. The variation in policy focus, from broad, overarching targets to specific, detailed objectives, might suggest an evolving strategy that straddles high-level aspirations and tangible, ground-level actions. However, the true efficacy of these policies and their harmonious integration into the fabric of Estonia's energy and cultural tapestry would likely require further observation and analysis over time.

At the national level, the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications has primary responsibility for implementing the EPBD. This commitment was further solidified with the amendments to the **Building Act** in October 2006, which effectively transposed the core components of Directive 2002/91/EC, marking a significant step in aligning national legislation with European standards on building energy performance. Estonia's **National Energy and Climate Plan** sets forth a strategy for significant GHG emission reductions and a marked increase in both EE and the RE share. Its key objective is achievement of an 80% reduction in GHG emissions by 2050 (including 70% by 2030). Estonia set a target for 2030 to maintain the current level of final energy consumption and to reduce primary energy consumption by up to 14 % compared to its peak in recent years (2013-69.4 TWh). Though the National Energy and Climate Plan does not directly address cultural heritage, which is instead covered under the Heritage Protection Act. This act is committed to the preservation and enrichment of Estonia's historical heritage, which implies consideration for EE measures in the context of heritage conservation. Although it does not explicitly mandate energy behavior strategies, it sets the stage for retrofitting historical buildings in a manner that is sensitive to their conservation.

The **Energy Sector Development Plan** sets clear objectives and methodologies for refurbishment of buildings with emphasis on enhancing sustainability through increased production of RE. It sets expectations for energy consumption: by 2030, primary energy consumption is anticipated to be reduced by 10% relative to 2012 levels. Furthermore, it projects final energy consumption to reach 32 TWh (115 PJ), while positioning the Estonian economy towards improved EE. These targets not only underscore Estonia's commitment to EE but also reflect the nation's strategic steps towards a greener, more sustainable energy paradigm. The **National Energy Efficiency Action Plan** outlines a roadmap for energy conservation, while the **Long-Term Strategy for Building Renovation** specifically aims to enhance the energy performance of older buildings. The **Energy Sector Organization Act** mandates a 3% annual renovation goal for government buildings, emphasizing high EE in public procurements. Section 6 of the Act lays down the obligation for central government authorities to purchase only products, services and buildings with high EE. The overarching "**Estonia 2035**" strategy integrates these goals within a broader societal context, implying a

commitment to preserving cultural heritage within a sustainable, high-quality living environment.

FIGURE 23: SYNTHESIS OF POLICY MAPPING IN ESTONIA

Furthermore, in 2020, Estonia implemented regulations setting forth specific **requirements for the energy efficiency of technical systems** in existing buildings. This directive encompasses heating, cooling, ventilation, and lighting systems. It mandates that any installation or replacement of these systems meets stringent standards designed not only to enhance the building's energy performance. Estonia has also implemented a detailed set of **minimum energy efficiency requirements** for buildings, designed to lower energy use and encourage sustainable practices across a diverse range of building types. These regulations specify exact performance metrics that all buildings, whether residential, commercial, or otherwise, must meet or exceed, aiming to ensure energy-conscious construction and renovation practices across the country. Besides, it defines regulations for low-energy buildings, NZEB and net ZEBs. For new low-energy buildings, the document sets forth a range of EE values, beginning with small residential homes with a heated area of less than 120 square meters, which are required to have an EE value of no more than 165 kWh/(m²·a). This requirement scales down for larger homes and different building types, with industrial buildings having a requirement of up to 140 kWh/(m²·a), and large energy-consuming buildings capped at 850 kWh/(m²·a). Significantly reconstructed buildings have slightly different, often higher, EE value requirements due to the challenges and limitations inherent in retrofitting existing structures. These measures aim to integrate RE sources, boost the nation's overall EE, and align with Estonia's commitment to environmental sustainability and improved living conditions through conscientious energy management in the built environment.

Regional and local levels have their own tailored approaches. **Tartu County's Development Strategy 2040**, for instance, places a strong emphasis on EE and sustainability, while the city of **Tartu's Energy 2030** action plan showcases direct implementation of EE in the municipal, residential, and transportation sectors. **Tartu City's Master Plan 2040** extends this vision at the local level, where EE and sustainable public transportation are key themes. Heritage buildings within Tartu are expected to align with this vision, integrating EE measures in compliance with the city's comprehensive urban planning goals. Lastly, the "**Restoration support scheme**" available in Tartu City provides financial support for the restoration of original architectural details of heritage buildings. This scheme facilitates the incorporation of EE measures into restoration projects, ensuring that the energy retrofitting aligns with the preservation of the buildings' historical features.

Financial incentives play a pivotal role in Estonia's policy ecosystem, serving as catalysts for integrating EE into the broader realm of heritage building conservation and contributing to promoting EE (affirmative function). The **Reconstruction Grant Scheme for Apartment Buildings** and the **Support Scheme for the Conservation of Cultural Monuments** allocate funds for significant renovations and the introduction of RE heating systems. Similarly, the **Regulation on the allocation and use of money from the ownership reform** reserve fund directly aids in the energy retrofitting of heritage buildings, enabling them to uphold their historical significance while enhancing their energy profile. The **Support scheme for**

conservation of rural architecture extends this support to rural heritage buildings, facilitating their transition to EE while maintaining their architectural integrity. These financial mechanisms not only incentivize the preservation of cultural value but also ensure that Estonia's heritage buildings are not left behind in the shift towards a more sustainable and energy-conscious future.

The validation exercise revealed interesting dynamics across various phases of policy implementation (see Figure 24). Local experts suggested that the 'Prioritisation and decision' phase exhibits the least coverage by the regulatory framework. Despite this, it effectively targets a broad array of stakeholders and third parties, suggesting a democratic and inclusive approach to policy development. Despite targeting a wide spectrum of stakeholders and third parties, the pronounced barriers at this stage - specifically bureaucratic hurdles (L2) and the challenge of reaching stakeholder consensus (S2) - suggest a potential bottleneck in the policy development process. These barriers hold significant weight and may impede the smooth progression of policies from planning to action. The strength of these barriers indicates that while the policy intentions are commendable, the execution phase could be fraught with delays and compromises that need strategic navigation to ensure policy goals are not undermined.

Conversely, the 'Preparation and orientation' and 'Implementation and monitoring' phases are the most thoroughly addressed within the policy framework. This indicates a strong emphasis on setting solid groundwork for policy initiatives and rigorous follow-through on their execution. The broad engagement of stakeholders in these phases - with an emphasis on those acting as mitigators and change agents - suggests a proactive and adaptable policy environment that encourages continuous improvement and responsiveness to emerging challenges. However, the designation of enablers in the 'Implementation and monitoring' phase is indicative of challenges that could arise from within the system intended to support policy execution. This could include resistance from entities that are responsible for enabling policy measures, potentially stemming from a misalignment of objectives, lack of resources, or resistance to change. The prominent roles played by mitigators and change agents in the initial phases reflect a proactive approach to identifying and addressing potential obstacles to policy success.

5.3.2 Italy

Data on 44 policy instruments, which encompass 24 legal, 14 economic, and 6 informational categories, was collected across various administrative levels: 25 at the national level of Italy, 16 at the regional level in Emilia-Romagna region, and 3 at the local level in Bologna City.

Italy's response to EU directives maps out a route to balance preservation of historical fabric with the energy transition. The policy instruments related to EE, cultural heritage, and renovation/retrofit are numerous and interconnected, demonstrating a holistic approach to integrating energy considerations into the heritage conservation domain. The policies span across municipal, state, and federal levels, indicating a decentralized approach where local administrations have considerable autonomy in implementing regulations (see Figure 25). It's also apparent that there has been a spike in policy activity corresponding with major EU directives and initiatives such as EPBD, EED, and the recasts and amendments thereof. The influence of overarching EU frameworks, including the 2030 Climate and Energy Framework, the EU Green Deal, and the Renovation Wave, suggests that Italy's policy landscape is responsive to and aligned with broader European EE goals.

At the national scale, the **National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan** establishes a forward-looking strategy to curtail primary energy consumption to 125 Mtep by 2030, reflecting ambitious improvements in EE - 56% in the large industry sector and 34% in the tertiary and transport sectors. It also seeks to ameliorate energy poverty from 8.6% to 7% by the end of the decade, demonstrating an integrated approach to sustainable development. **The National Energy Strategy** instead is a roadmap designed to revamp Italy's energy system by 2030, fostering a model of increased competitiveness, sustainability, and security. The strategy's targets are ambitious and include a reduction in final energy consumption by 10 Mtoe by 2030, achieving a 28% share of renewables in total energy consumption, and a 55% share in electricity consumption by the same year. The **Program for the Energy Requalification of Central Public Administration Buildings** is an initiative aimed at enhancing the EE of national building heritage, specifically targeting public administration properties. It is designed to fulfill the EU's directive on EE, mandating a yearly energy requalification to achieve at least a 3% annual improvement in the conditioned surface area's energy performance. The "**Strategy for Energy Retrofitting of National Building Stock**" outlines Italy's approach to enhancing EE within its building sector. It targets a significant reduction in energy consumption and CO₂ emissions by promoting adoption of new materials and technologies, improving building envelopes, increasing the use of RE sources, and integrating deep renovation practices. Lastly, the system Energy Efficiency Certificates, also known as **White Certificates**, plays a pivotal role in advancing Italy's commitment to EE within the built environment. This innovative mechanism mandates electricity and natural gas distributors to achieve yearly energy savings targets by either undertaking EE projects or by purchasing Energy Efficiency Titles (EETs) on the market. By incentivizing a wide range of energy-saving projects, from retrofitting lighting systems to

improving heating and cooling infrastructures in residential and commercial buildings, the White Certificates system encourages significant reductions in energy consumption.

FIGURE 25: SYNTHESIS OF POLICY MAPPING IN ITALY

Funded by the European Union

D 2.1. Study of multi-level barriers

Central to Italy's heritage protection is the **Cultural Heritage And Landscape Code** which encompasses regulations aimed at the protection and valorization of Italy's cultural heritage and landscape. This code is designed to safeguard monuments, buildings, artworks, and landscapes that are of historical, artistic, or archaeological significance to the nation. Its provisions involve the management, conservation, and public accessibility of these assets, ensuring they are preserved for future generations. Besides, the Italian Ministry of Cultural Heritage (MIBAC) published "**Guidelines for the improvement of energy efficiency in cultural heritage**" in 2015. These guidelines are devised to aid stakeholders in the planning and assessment of potential solutions before implementation. They harmonize restoration theory concepts with technical advice for energy diagnosis, integrating context knowledge, EE assessment, and EE improvement into a cohesive narrative. These guidelines, although non-binding, play a vital role in steering EE endeavors within the heritage conservation sector.

Italy also established a wide range of financial and fiscal incentives that aims to stimulate EE across a spectrum of buildings. The **Superbonus 110%** scheme is particularly notable, offering a 110% tax deduction for EE improvements, RE installations, and seismic upgrades, under certain conditions until the end of 2025. The **Ecobonus** provides a 65% tax deduction for a wide range of energy-saving measures, from installing efficient windows to solar panels for water heating. The **Bonus Casa** encourages the renovation of residential buildings, with a 50% tax deduction capped at €96,000, which could cover EE measures that align with heritage conservation principles. For direct financial support, the **National Energy Efficiency Fund (FNEE)** provides subsidized loans and guarantees for EE projects, a potential source for funding heritage-appropriate energy interventions. Similarly, the **Thermal Account** offers incentives for the installation of efficient heating systems. the Thermal Account incentive program serves as a key driver for improving EE and bolstering the uptake of renewable thermal energy in buildings. By offering capital contributions to support small-scale installations, the program directly reduces the upfront costs associated with the adoption of energy-efficient technologies and RE systems. The Thermal Account program thus addresses two critical aspects of building efficiency: reducing the energy demand through better insulation and replacing conventional, fossil-fuel-based heating systems with RE sources, leading to lower energy consumption and a reduction in GHG emissions from the building sector.

The strategic approach at the regional and local level to EE and climate action demonstrates a commitment to proactive environmental stewardship within an urban context. The **Regional Energy Plan 2030 of Emilia-Romagna**, with its far-reaching climate and energy objectives, integrates a strong push towards EE in buildings, including significant interventions in heritage buildings to reach nearly zero-energy standards. Similarly, the **Triennial Implementation Plan 2022-2024** underscores the importance of EE in building stock and supports deep renovations aligned with national strategies and EU directives,

potentially offering a blueprint for energy-efficient retrofitting of historic buildings. **Act N.1838** facilitates a dual objective: it nurtures cultural heritage by allocating a substantial budget for the preservation and enhancement of historical assets, while also encouraging their integration into the local community fabric, thereby fostering sustainable development and cultural tourism. This underscores the act's holistic approach to heritage, viewing it as an active participant in regional development rather than merely a static relic to be conserved. The Emilia-Romagna Regional Government has instituted the **Energy Fund 2024**, a novel financial mechanism that couples economic incentives with an environmentally progressive agenda. This fund is particularly conducive to enhancing the EE of heritage buildings, given its support for seismic retrofitting combined with energy upgrades. Such provisions ensure that the historical integrity of buildings is maintained while their energy consumption is reduced. Finally, initiatives such as the **Boiler Bonus** and the **Heating Stove Bonus**, which provide incentives for the adoption of less polluting heating alternatives, can potentially be applied to heritage buildings.

The **Action Plan for Sustainable Energy and Climate** for the City of Bologna reflects a rigorous agenda to address the broader impacts of global warming. By aligning with the Mayors Adapt initiative and the Covenant of Mayors for Energy and Climate, Bologna is not only pledging to reduce GHG emissions but is also pursuing a holistic decarbonization strategy.

The analysis of Italy's policy framework attributes reveals that it seems plausible to suggest that the comprehensive coverage across all phases of policy development, with a particular focus on the initial phase, indicates a strategic preference (see Figure 26). There is a notable emphasis on the initial phase of preparation and orientation. This suggests a strategic focus on laying a solid groundwork for EE initiatives, which is fundamental for aligning stakeholders' interests and setting clear objectives. The attention to this phase could signify an intention to create a shared understanding and buy-in from various stakeholders early on, which is essential for the success of any policy implementation. However, most policies appear to target building management operators, who do not directly confront the most pronounced barriers to EE in Italy. This disconnection might indicate a potential misalignment between policy targets and the actual agents of change within the framework. The impact of this could be twofold: on the one hand, it suggests that more could be done to engage directly with those who face the barriers; on the other hand, it could also imply an opportunity to further empower building management operators to take a more active role in overcoming these barriers. The role of third parties, especially during the first phase, is significant, with advisory intermediaries acting as mitigators and change agents. This involvement is crucial, as these stakeholders can provide expertise and guidance to navigate through the technical, legal, and economic complexities of EE projects. Their transition to enablers in the prioritization and decision phase underlines their importance in influencing the direction and scope of EE measures. Among the listed policies from the federal level, the local experts identified an apparent accent on the final phase of implementation and

monitoring, yet this is not matched by identified strong barriers at this level, which could suggest a well-established regulatory environment or a potential underestimation of the challenges at the federal level. The absence of pronounced barriers at this level could lead to complacency, potentially overlooking emerging challenges or need for policy refinement.

FIGURE 26: INTEGRATING RESULTS OF POLICY MAPPING IN PROBLEM TREE (ITALY)

Italy's policies reflect a balance between safeguarding cultural heritage and advancing EE. While the framework is robust, fostering energy-smart heritage buildings, its efficacy will hinge on adapting to new energy and conservation challenges. The policies could be fine-tuned to support stakeholders facing the practical barriers of this transition more directly.

5.3.1 Portugal

Data on 24 policy instruments, which encompass 20 legal, 3 economic, and 1 informational categories, was collected across various administrative levels: 20 at the national level of Portugal, 2 at the regional level in Madeira region, and 2 at the local level in Funchal City.

Portugal's strategic framework for enhancing the EE of heritage buildings forms a critical component of its broader environmental and energy goals. This effort is underpinned by a sophisticated policy landscape that balances the preservation of cultural heritage with the imperatives of climate change mitigation and energy conservation. The country's policy approach to EE, especially within the context of heritage buildings, is multifaceted, blending legislative mandates with financial incentives, technological innovation, and collaborative governance. The listed policies regulating EE and the preservation of heritage buildings are predominantly steered at the national level, with less frequency and prominence of policies emanating from local and regional authorities (see Figure 27). There are distinct policies which directly consider energy behavior, suggesting a holistic approach to policy-making where energy consumption patterns are taken into account. Policy development in Portugal is responsive to broader European Union directives and frameworks, evidenced by spikes in activity that correspond with key EU legislative milestones, such as the recast of EPBD and EED, as well as the introduction of initiatives like the Renovation Wave and the EU Green Deal. This trend suggests that Portugal's policy framework is closely aligned with EU goals and commitments, translating EU-level ambitions into the national context.

At the heart of Portugal's EE drive is its alignment with EED. The "**Long-Term Strategy for Carbon Neutrality of the Portuguese Economy by 2050**" and the "**National Energy and Climate Plan 2021-2030**" articulate Portugal's holistic strategy to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050. They lay out a long-term vision for transforming the energy system into one that is sustainable, resilient, and carbon-neutral. Portugal's **National Energy and Climate Plan** specifies 2030 targets, reflecting the nation's strategic measures to contribute significantly to the EU's collective EE goals. Portugal's targets for EE by 2030 focus on a significant reduction in energy consumption. The country's indicative contribution to EE is set against the EU Reference Scenario of 2007, using the PRIMES model as a baseline. Portugal has committed to reducing its primary energy consumption by 35% compared to this reference, aligning with the EU-wide target of a 32.5% EE increase. By 2030, Portugal's targets are to limit primary energy consumption between 21.5 to 15.6 Mtoe and to limit final energy consumption between 14.4 to 14.9 Mtoe. The **National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency** further extends Portugal's efforts to increase EE and ensure the quality and reliability of energy services. The **National Buildings Energy Performance Certification System** is a cornerstone of Portugal's regulatory efforts to improve building EE. By mandating Energy Performance Certificates, the system not only assesses the energy performance of buildings but also serves as a tool for raising awareness and encouraging EE improvements in the real estate market.

FIGURE 27: SYNTHESIS OF POLICY MAPPING IN PORTUGAL

In Portugal, a series of interlinked policies is advancing EE of heritage buildings, harmonizing the imperatives of conservation with modern energy standards. **Decree-Law 140/2009** plays a pivotal role in the conservation and management of Portugal's cultural heritage. It provides a comprehensive legal framework for undertaking works on cultural assets that are either already classified or in the process of classification for their national, public, or municipal significance. This legislation mandates rigorous prior control and ensures accountability for any intervention on cultural heritage assets. It requires detailed preliminary reports from legally qualified technicians and mandates continuous oversight by the designated cultural heritage administration. The process culminates in a comprehensive final report, aiming to ensure the quality of interventions, foster professional development in the heritage sector, and maintain a control mechanism for urban operations concerning immovable cultural assets. The **Law n.º 107/2001** instead casts a wide net in defining cultural heritage to include both tangible and intangible elements, affirming the importance of preserving the Portuguese language and traditional culture. It delineates the state's responsibility in safeguarding cultural heritage, ensuring its transmission to future generations, fostering national and international appreciation, and facilitating public and private efforts in its preservation and enhancement. Together, these laws underscore Portugal's commitment to the valorization and protection of its cultural heritage, integrating these objectives within the broader context of urban development and environmental sustainability.

Beyond individual buildings, the "**Long-Term Strategy for Building Renovation**" and the "**Energy Efficiency Programme for Public Administration**" are part of a broader strategy that aims to elevate public administration buildings to higher efficiency standards, reflecting Portugal's holistic approach to combining environmental sustainability with the preservation of its cultural patrimony.

Financial instruments and programs play a crucial role in translating policy objectives into tangible outcomes. These programs underscore the importance of leveraging financial incentives to encourage the adoption of EE measures. By providing funding for the renovation of heritage buildings, these initiatives not only contribute to energy savings but also ensure that Portugal's cultural heritage is preserved for future generations. The **Plan to Promote Efficiency in Energy Consumption** exemplifies how competitive funding mechanisms can stimulate investment in EE projects. Complementing this, the "**Cultural Heritage Safeguard Fund**" along with pertinent decrees, construct a legislative safeguard for heritage buildings, mandating that energy retrofits uphold the cultural integrity of these structures. The "**More Sustainable Buildings**" initiative actively incentivizes the integration of energy-efficient solutions and RE in residential spaces, including historically significant buildings, thereby reducing energy consumption and GHG emissions.

The plans at the regional and municipal levels reflect a concerted effort by Madeira and Funchal to address global environmental challenges while pursuing regional growth and development. They exhibit an integrated approach that considers EE and sustainability as central to both environmental resilience and cultural richness, aligning regional and local initiatives with broader national and European objectives.

The **Action Plan for Sustainable Energy and Climate** in the Autonomous Region of Madeira is a robust framework that sets forth comprehensive targets for 2030 and 2050. It is strategically designed to dovetail with EU and national energy and climate policies. Key focal points of this plan include the adoption of RE, reduction of GHG emissions, and improvement of EE. The **Program of the XIV Regional Government of Madeira** extends the focus of regional development beyond energy and environmental concerns to encompass economic recovery, social cohesion, public health, and technological innovation. The program's emphasis on EE as part of a comprehensive approach to sustainability and its alignment with climate action initiatives indicate a holistic approach to regional development challenges. **Funchal's Action Plan for Sustainable Energy and Climate** represents the municipality's strategic initiative to confront energy sustainability and climate challenges head-on. The plan's commitment to achieving the objectives of the European Covenant of Mayors by 2050 exemplifies Funchal's dedication to playing a significant role in creating a sustainable and resilient energy system within the region. By 2030, Funchal has committed to reducing final energy consumption by 39% compared to 2010 levels. It also aims to increase the use of RE by 170% and reduce fossil fuel consumption by 51% relative to 2010. Furthermore, the plan sets a goal to decrease CO₂eq emissions by 45% by 2030. For 2050, the targets are even more ambitious: a 77% reduction in final energy consumption, a 244% increase in RE usage, a 92% reduction in fossil fuel consumption, and an 86% decrease in CO₂eq emissions, all in comparison to 2010 levels. Complementing the aforementioned plans, the **Municipal Strategic Plan for Culture 2021-2031** is a testament to Funchal's innovative approach to cultural policy. It's the region's first plan developed through a participatory process, aiming to utilize culture as a catalyst for social dynamics, inclusivity, and economic development. This plan shows the importance of cultural vibrancy to the region's identity and supports Funchal's ambition to be recognized as a European Capital of Culture.

The policy framework analysis in Portugal, as depicted in problem tree (see Figure 28), highlights a possible imbalance in the coverage of regulatory frameworks across different phases of EE projects. The "Prioritization and decision" phase emerges as possibly underrepresented in regulatory guidance, a phase which, according to previous investigations, is fraught with a variety of barriers: technical, legal, environmental, and economic barriers. This lack of regulatory support in the critical phase of "Prioritization and decision" can potentially result in hesitation or resistance from stakeholders, project delays, and increased complexity in managing retrofit projects. It also places greater onus on the role of change agents like financiers and regulators, who must navigate these barriers without the clear guidance of an extensive regulatory framework. The "Preparation and orientation" phase benefits from a robust policy foundation, addressing common challenges such as awareness, financial barriers, and access to support, thereby underlining an intention to facilitate the early stages of retrofitting initiatives. The strong policy presence here indicates an understanding of the need to foster early engagement and support for stakeholders embarking on EE projects. Main policy target groups during this phase are suppliers and third-party advisory bodies, suggesting that the framework aims to facilitate

the provision of technical advice and the availability of materials and services necessary for project initiation. The main target groups within available policies are identified as suppliers and advisory bodies as third parties, suggesting a policy focus on upstream provision of expertise, materials, and services necessary for the initial steps of EE projects.

FIGURE 28: INTEGRATING RESULTS OF POLICY MAPPING IN PROBLEM TREE (PORTUGAL)

Portugal's policy framework for enhancing the EE of heritage buildings shows the country's commitment to sustainable development, cultural preservation, and climate action. This approach is characterized by a strategic alignment with EU directives, the implementation of ambitious national targets, and the development of innovative financing mechanisms. The strategy is both pragmatic, in its focus on immediate operational changes, and visionary, with its long-term targets for energy and climate.

5.3.2 Spain

Data on 33 policy instruments, which encompass 22 legal, 8 economic, and 3 informational categories, was collected across various administrative levels: 21 at the national level in Spain, 11 at the regional level in Province Palencia and autonomous community of Castile-León Region, and 1 at the local level in city of Aguilar De Campoo of Province Palencia.

The regulatory landscape in Spain for EE, building renovation, and heritage preservation appears quite comprehensive and adaptive, integrating a variety of policy tools across several tiers of government, as depicted in Figure 29. There's a discernible interplay between domains like EE, heritage conservation, and renovation, with policies seemingly interwoven to address the multifaceted nature of energy behavior. It seems there is a recognition of the significant role human behavior plays in energy conservation and efficiency, crucial for reaching energy targets. However, it's worth noting that the extent of this recognition and its effectiveness could vary. The presence of financial and fiscal policy measures suggests an intention to facilitate the required investments, especially vital for the specialized needs of heritage building retrofitting, which often entails higher costs. The timeline indicates an ebb and flow of policy initiatives, with a discernible intensification around 2010 and peaking in 2013, followed by a lull and subsequent resurgence post-2020. This pattern could imply a phase of vigorous policy formulation and enactment, potentially aligning with the EU's legislative benchmarks like the EPBD and EED. The uptick in activity from 2020 onwards might be associated with the European Green Deal and the Renovation Wave initiative, aiming to amplify renovation rates across the EU, though the graph does not provide complete clarity on the direct impact or success of these initiatives.

The Spanish framework for energy and climate is based on a 2050 objective of national climate neutrality, 100% RE in the electricity mix and 97% RE in the total energy mix. Spain's commitment to EE is a key aspect of its **National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan**, targeting a 39.5% improvement by 2030, in line with EU directives. It proposes 17 measures to meet the 2030 target, 10 of which were designed along a sectoral approach, applying proportional savings to each sector based on its consumption. Central to this plan is the large-scale retrofitting of existing structures, including an ambitious goal to upgrade the thermal envelopes of 1.2 million homes and the heating and water systems of 300,000 homes annually until 2030. These efforts are underpinned by a substantial €7,675 million in public funding, anticipated to trigger an investment surge of €26,102 million, focusing primarily on residential buildings. The National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan strategically integrates EE with heritage preservation, ensuring that the unique character and integrity of Spain's historical edifices are maintained amidst modernization, symbolizing a harmonious blend of sustainability with cultural stewardship.

FIGURE 29: SYNTHESIS OF POLICY MAPPING IN SPAIN

Complementing this, *the ERESEE 2020* strategy sets ambitious goals for reducing energy consumption in buildings, with special attention to the conservation needs of heritage sites during energy retrofits. The *Urban Rehabilitation, Regeneration, and Renewal Act* (Ley 8/2013) furthers these efforts by promoting the sustainable development of urban spaces, ensuring that the revitalization of cities enhances both the living environment and energy performance of buildings. Lastly, the *Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan* stands as a comprehensive economic framework aimed at bolstering Spain's recovery in the post-COVID-19 era. Within this plan, there is a strong focus on digital transformation, the green economy, and social cohesion, with provisions to enhance the EE of public administration buildings, many of which may have historical value.

Spanish policy safeguards heritage buildings as vital cultural and urban entities, mandating resilience against climate change. The most stringent protection, 'Bien de Interés Cultural' (BIC), applies to national treasures and necessitates a 'Management Plan' from owners, guiding gradual conservation and adaptive reuse. Both central and regional governments may establish such plans, especially for distinctive categories like industrial heritage. Heritage preservation is further enshrined in the *Law 16/1985*, which establishes the framework for the protection, conservation, enrichment, and dissemination of Spanish historical heritage. Alongside this, the *Royal Decree 111/1986* provides the implementation details, ensuring that EE interventions harmonize with heritage preservation principles. These legislative instruments underscore the nation's commitment to upholding its historical legacy within the context of contemporary environmental challenges. There are several *National Plans for Heritage*. Plans are considered for, for example, preventive conservation, emergencies and risks, monasteries, 20th-century cultural heritage, and industrial heritage. Furthermore, the *National Plan for Traditional Architecture* acknowledges the dual goals of preserving cultural heritage and promoting EE. The plan advocates for the use of traditional construction methods and materials that are both environmentally sustainable and energy-efficient, applying them to the rehabilitation of historical buildings. This reflects an understanding that EE interventions need to be customized to maintain the essence of heritage buildings. The *2% Culture Law (Law 14/2021)* ensures a dedicated portion of public works funding to safeguard and enhance Spain's cultural heritage, incorporating EE and sustainability.

Spain's EE framework is financially anchored by the *National Energy Efficiency Fund (FNEE)*, bolstered by Law 18/2014, which secures funding through contributions from the energy sector, expected to reach around €2 billion by 2030. This fund is central to Spain's strategy, providing technical and financial support for energy-saving initiatives across various sectors. In tandem, the Energy Saving Certificates System (SCE in Spanish), established by Royal Decree 36/2023, creates a market for *Energy Savings Certificates* that represent quantifiable energy reductions, allowing investors in EE to trade these savings, thereby

promoting compliance with regulations and supporting the broader objectives of emission reductions and energy conservation.

In Castilla y León, regional policies like the Renewable Implementation Criteria and the Cultural Heritage Regulations illustrate a harmonized approach to EE and heritage preservation, reflecting the region's distinctive historical identity. **Decree-Ley 2/2022 e 4/2022**, for instance, integrates RE deployment with the protection of traditional landscapes, while **Law 12/2002** actively protects the region's historical heritage during modernization efforts.

At the local level, Aguilar de Campoo in Palencia includes tailored EE measures within its **Energy Efficiency Improvement Plan**. This plan, specific to the town's needs, focuses on reducing energy consumption and enhancing sustainability through initiatives like LED lighting upgrades, simultaneously advancing environmental and economic objectives while preserving the town's historical essence.

The analysis of Spain's policy framework, as depicted in Figure 30, tentatively suggests that the phase of prioritization and decision might not be as robustly covered by existing regulations, which could arguably lead to challenges given its central role in steering policy application. It appears that this phase's limited coverage, in conjunction with the involvement of a diverse array of stakeholders, might imply a risk of misalignment among various interests, possibly leading to obstacles. These potential barriers, which include bureaucratic complexities, intricate retrofitting needs, strict preservation rules, and economic constraints, seem to have the capacity to significantly slow progress, although this requires further investigation for conclusive evidence.

The visualized policy framework for EE in Spain suggests a well-established emphasis on the implementation and monitoring phase. This could indicate that Spanish policies are geared towards concrete actions and ensuring that policy measures are followed through to their intended outcomes. The comprehensive coverage in this phase reflects a strong commitment to accountability and measurable results, which is beneficial for ensuring that initiatives have tangible impacts on EE goals. Another well-covered phase is seen to be the model design and detailed analysis phase. It demonstrates a strong emphasis on the technical groundwork for EE. Building management operators are consistently targeted across all phases, highlighting their central role as mitigators in the EE process. This focus on building managers might suggest that they are considered as pivotal players who can directly influence the energy performance of buildings. However, the potential downside is that an overemphasis on building managers could overshadow the involvement of other key stakeholders, possibly leading to a less collaborative and more siloed approach. Advisory bodies come into play as third parties at almost all phases, presumably offering expertise and guidance. Heritage occupants are notably engaged as third parties during the model design and detailed analysis phase and implementation, indicating that the lived experience of these stakeholders is valued and considered when shaping and applying energy policies.

In essence, Spain’s national policies on EE demonstrate a strategic and holistic approach, marrying the objectives of sustainable development and heritage conservation. Through a well-orchestrated mix of legislative action, financial incentives, and a strong regulatory framework, Spain is making strides toward a future that respects its illustrious past while embracing the imperatives of EE and environmental stewardship.

FIGURE 30: INTEGRATING RESULTS OF POLICY MAPPING IN PROBLEM TREE (SPAIN)

6. Good Practices

While “basic” practices might represent standard or “business as usual” approaches, “good practice” examples emerge as the pinnacle of what is currently achievable using the latest technology and methodologies. In response to previously identified barriers, a collection of good practices aimed at addressing these challenges effectively has been identified. Good practices have the main and important role to clearly connect research with practice (Vasely, 2011). These examples serve as invaluable references for decision-makers and practitioners, especially when renovation projects are detailed alongside accounts of the building’s heritage value and cultural significance. This section seeks to showcase a spectrum of these practices, offering insight and inspiration for those undertaking the delicate task of integrating modern efficiency improvements within historically significant structures. Through exploring these good practices, stakeholders are equipped to navigate the complexities of renovation, ensuring a balance between preserving the past and meeting the sustainability demands of the future.

TECHNICAL BARRIERS

- Guidance “[Planning Responsible Retrofit of Traditional Buildings](#)” and “[Energy Efficiency and Traditional Homes](#)” funded by Historic England, delve into the intricacies and uncertainties of integrating new technologies within older buildings. They emphasize the interplay between the building’s existing fabric, technological innovations, natural elements, and human factors. Central to this guidance is the advocacy for a whole-building approach, which is crucial for mitigating risks and minimizing liabilities. This includes comprehensive home energy assessments to understand the specific needs and limitations of a heritage asset. This approach ensures that any interventions are sympathetic to the building’s character and use materials that, while efficient, do not detract from its historical integrity.
- The [HiBERTool](#), developed to aid in the energy retrofitting of historic buildings, offers a detailed catalogue of over 100 EE measures. Each entry provides technical specifics, practical applications, benefits, and drawbacks, aiming to simplify complex retrofit decisions. Accompanied by best practice examples from the HiBERAtlas and online resources, the HiBERTool serves as a comprehensive guide for balancing EE improvements with historical preservation.
- The [Responsible Retrofit Guidance Wheel](#), supported by the UK Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, stands as an innovative online interactive tool. It offers users the ability to explore over 50 energy retrofit measures, providing insights into how these measures interact and highlighting potential risks to consider prior to implementation.
- [Shallow Geothermal Heating and Cooling at the Parliament of Andalusia](#): The Parliament of Andalusia utilizes a shallow geothermal heating and cooling system,

showcasing the integration of eco-friendly technology in historic structures. This system, relying on stable underground water temperatures, offers a reliable, efficient alternative to traditional HVAC by providing seasonal heat storage and no water waste. Key benefits include improved EE and reduced fossil fuel reliance, with challenges such as initial investment costs and heritage constraints.

- [The technical advice line](#), funded by Historic England, provides free and confidential support to anyone with questions about the care and repair of old buildings. This service is managed by a skilled team of building surveyors and architects, capable of answering over 1,000 inquiries each year from a diverse group including building owners, professionals, and contractors.
- [Energy bookkeeping](#), mandated by the Local energy agency Spodnje Podravje, Slovenia, centralizes data on energy use within a computerized database for buildings over 250 sq.meters. It records annual energy and costs, building technical characteristics, and EE measures. Essential for buildings managed by or for public entities, it streamlines energy monitoring and identifies savings opportunities, promoting informed management and efficiency improvements.
- The Lendava library's retrofit, [involving geothermal heating and paraffin-based latent](#) heat storage, supported by Local Energy Agency Pomurje, Slovenia, addresses the challenges of integrating modern energy solutions within cultural heritage constraints. Installed in a neo-Baroque villa recognized for its historical significance, this approach circumvents space limitations and preservation restrictions by leveraging compact, efficient paraffin storage and sustainable geothermal energy, demonstrating a harmonious blend of conservation and contemporary EE.
- The "[Energibyggar](#)" (Energy Builder) education program in Sweden, the project prepared craftsmen, construction workers, and installers with high-standard curriculums and hands-on training. This initiative has successfully educated 802 trainers and 2,350 craftsmen across Sweden, fostering cross-professional dialogue and practical skills in energy-efficient building techniques through its comprehensive online platform and targeted training modules.

LEGISLATIVE AND REGULATORY BARRIERS

- The [Guidance "When is permission required?"](#), provided by the UK government, clearly delineates which EE improvements necessitate either planning permission or listed building consent. Essential for homeowners and developers alike, this information aims to streamline the process of making buildings more energy-efficient by specifying the types of projects that require official approval. Hosted on the GOV.UK platform, this resource serves as a valuable tool for navigating the regulatory landscape, ensuring that EE measures are implemented in compliance with the law.
- The [POSIT'IF](#) initiative, through its Semi-Public Company ENERGIES POSIT'IF, operationalizes a public-private partnership model in the Ile-de-France region to

promote energy-efficient refurbishments, particularly for heritage buildings. By blending public oversight with private sector innovation and flexibility, it offers tailored Energy Service Company (ESCO) solutions that address the unique retrofitting challenges of historic structures. The company operates by offering ESCO solutions specifically tailored for low-energy refurbishments. This involves conducting energy audits, proposing energy-saving measures, financing the retrofit projects, and overseeing the implementation.

- The [USA Improvements to Generator Interconnection Procedures and Agreements](#) aim to accelerate the permitting process for generator interconnection, ensuring efficient, transparent, and non-discriminatory access to the transmission system. These improvements include a first-ready, first-served cluster study approach, speeding up queue processing with firm deadlines and penalties for delays, and incorporating technological advancements such as co-location of generating facilities and consideration of electric storage and alternative transmission technologies. Compliance is mandated within 90 days of the rule's publication, with transitional options available based on the progress of interconnection requests. This approach aims to minimize interconnection delays and enhance the grid's capacity to integrate new generation projects effectively.
- The [2023 Energy Efficiency Policy Toolkit](#), unveiled by the International Energy Agency (IEA) during the 8th Annual Global Conference on EE held in Versailles, offers a detailed blueprint for boosting EE worldwide. Tailored to assist governments in formulating, endorsing, and applying policies related to EE, this toolkit confronts a range of challenges associated with enhancing EE in various types of buildings, inclusive of those with historical value. It provides a cohesive strategy that merges overarching strategic directives with specific policy recommendations pertinent to distinct sectors, thereby laying the groundwork for a holistic approach to improving EE in a broad spectrum of buildings.

ECONOMIC BARRIERS

- The [Financial calculation tool](#), developed with support of County Administrative Board of Dalarna (Sweden) aims at aiding building managers in evaluating EE investments. Unlike traditional payback methods, which overlook long-term profitability and technical lifespan, this tool incorporates advanced financial techniques like Net Present Value and Internal Rate of Return. Available in both Excel and web formats, the tools are user-friendly and have proven effective in recalibrating energy audit outcomes, advocating for a shift towards more nuanced financial analyses in EE planning.
- [Seattle City Light's Energy Efficiency initiative](#) adds a twist by allowing tenants to pay for their energy use at a rate that reflects both actual consumption and the estimated consumption if energy upgrades had not been made. The difference in cost is then reimbursed to the landlord, effectively compensating them for their

investment in EE through a long-term power purchase agreement. This setup incentivizes landlords to upgrade their properties by ensuring they're compensated for the energy savings generated, while tenants benefit from a more energy-efficient living or working space without upfront costs.

- The [ProKilowatt](#) scheme of Switzerland is an innovative auction program supports electricity-saving initiatives across industries, households, and the service sector, requiring projects to demonstrate payback periods beyond four years. By focusing on the efficiency of investments—measured in kWh saved per CHF spent—the scheme has successfully implemented 800 projects between 2010 and 2021, achieving significant annual energy savings.
- The [Sustainable Energy Finance Initiative](#) (SEFI) by the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) seeks to craft the necessary policy and economic landscape for sustainable energy to meet the global energy demand effectively. SEFI acts as a pivotal platform, offering financial experts the necessary tools, support, and networks needed to foster financial innovations aimed at enhancing the environmental sustainability of the energy mix. Further information on SEFI's approach to bolstering sustainable energy finance can be found on its dedicated website.

ENVIRONMENTAL BARRIERS

- The UK government has acknowledged the direct rebound effect in EE measures, particularly insulation, by adjusting policy models to reflect real-life energy savings. Recognizing that improvements like loft and cavity wall insulation often lead to increased indoor temperatures due to behavioral changes, not all theoretical energy savings are realized. To account for this, a reduction factor, including a specific comfort factor, is applied, reducing predicted energy savings by approximately 15% to account for "comfort taking." This adjustment ensures policy evaluations and consumer savings advice accurately reflect the potential for increased energy use despite efficiency improvements, providing a more realistic framework for assessing the impact of EE policies on reducing carbon emissions and energy consumption.
- The US Department of National Park Service offers a [guide for recognizing the visual attributes of historic buildings](#) to aid in their preservation. This guide outlines a three-step approach to identifying character-defining elements: beginning with an assessment of the building's overall visual character, followed by a detailed examination at close range, and concluding with an exploration of the interior visual character. Aimed at assisting owners and architects, this guideline emphasizes the importance of pinpointing those features or elements that contribute to a building's visual distinctiveness, ensuring their conservation in preservation efforts.

SOCIAL BARRIERS

- BSES Rajdhani Power Limited's pioneering behavioral EE program in Delhi, supported by Oracle Opower tool, delivered personalized [Home Energy Reports](#) to 200,000 customers, achieving an estimated energy savings of 1-3%. This program utilized a mix of digital and traditional communications to encourage smarter energy use among consumers, highlighting BSES's commitment to reducing energy consumption and environmental impact. Through engaging digital tools and informative reports, the initiative successfully promoted energy awareness and efficiency, contributing to broader environmental objectives by addressing the residential sector's energy demand.
- [Denmark's Citizens' Assembly on Climate Issues](#), consisting of 99 members reflecting the nation's demographic diversity, aims to foster consensus on climate policies by directly involving the public in decision-making. After extensive discussions, the Assembly proposed 119 diverse recommendations for a green transition, addressing issues from education to carbon taxation. These suggestions were forwarded to key government officials, illustrating a participatory approach to resolving stakeholder differences on climate action. This method exemplifies a structured process for achieving widespread agreement on environmental policies.
- The [ACHIEVE project](#) (France) addresses reluctance to depart from conventional systems by directly engaging vulnerable households through energy assessments. The process involved two home visits to analyze energy and water consumption, culminating in a report with actionable recommendations for reducing energy use, complemented by the installation of energy-saving devices. With 136 households served, significant annual savings and CO2 reductions were achieved. The success of this project highlights the potential for local, hands-on programs to make EE accessible and to shift traditional practices towards more sustainable alternatives.
- In 2022, the UK government introduced a digital service [find ways to save energy in your home](#) to offer tailored advice for making homes more energy-efficient and cost-effective. This tool aims to be an authoritative source for retrofitting information, providing recommendations suitable for individual homes, including those with historic value. Historic England supports this initiative by updating its guidance for historic home owners, focusing on appropriate energy-saving measures, necessary consents, and the critical role of maintenance for EE.

7. Conclusion

The study conducted a thorough analysis that systematically identified and examined the complex barriers to enhancing EE in heritage buildings, organizing these obstacles into five key categories: technical, legislative and regulatory, economic, environmental, and social. This examination sheds light on the challenges of integrating energy-efficient measures into such buildings, underscoring the critical need for a balanced approach that equally values preservation and sustainability. This strategic approach aims to foster an environment conducive to the integration of EE within heritage buildings as a viable and appealing objective. It involves crafting clear, supportive policies and regulations, providing financial incentives to alleviate the costs associated with EE measures, pioneering technological solutions compatible with heritage preservation, and nurturing consensus and shared commitment to sustainability among all stakeholders.

The policy analysis underscored the necessity of aligning legislative and regulatory frameworks with the dual objectives of EE enhancement and heritage preservation. The insights gained from the policy analysis are instrumental in shaping the project's strategy for addressing the identified barriers. These recommendations will advocate for an integrated approach that combines policy reform, financial support, technological innovation, and stakeholder engagement, ensuring that future efforts are well-coordinated and effective. In addition to the comprehensive analysis and policy review, the study engaged in the collection and examination of good practices, grouped according to the identified barriers: technical, legislative and regulatory, economic, environmental, and social. This endeavor aimed to showcase effective strategies and initiatives that have successfully addressed the challenges of enhancing EE in heritage buildings. By examining these practices, the study not only highlighted viable solutions but also provided a source of inspiration and guidance for stakeholders involved in similar projects.

The outcomes not only fulfill the project's analytical needs but also establish a foundation for meaningful interventions that are in line with the broader goal of sustainable heritage preservation. This strategic approach is set to influence the field positively, catalyzing a shift towards more sustainable and energy-efficient conservation practices in heritage buildings. The derived knowledge from this study could potentially steer the formulation of policy recommendations, the development of financial support structures, the crafting of stakeholder engagement initiatives, and the innovation of retrofitting technologies that respect cultural heritage values. These initiatives are poised to significantly advance the project's aims, promoting the seamless integration of EE into heritage conservation in a manner that is both impactful and respectful of historical significance.

8. References

Amecke, H., Deason, J., Hobbs, A., Novikova, A., Xiu, Y., & Shengyuan, Z., "Buildings Energy Efficiency in China, Germany, and the United States," Climate Policy Initiative, Apr. 2013. Available: <https://climatepolicyinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/Buildings-Energy-Efficiency-in-China-Germany-and-the-United-States.pdf>

Ástmarsson, B., Jensen, P. A., & Maslesa, E., "Sustainable renovation of residential buildings and the landlord/tenant dilemma," in *Energy Policy*, vol. 63, pp. 355–362, 2013. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2013.08.046

Baechler, M. C., Gygi, K. F., & Hendrickson, P. I., "Potential Environmental Effects of Energy Conservation Measures in Northwest Industries," PNL-8015, UC-310, prepared for Bonneville Power Administration under a Related Services Agreement with the U.S. Department of Energy, Contract DE-AC06-76RLO 1830, Pacific Northwest Laboratory, Richland, Washington, January 1992.

Baek, C., & Park, S., "Policy measures to overcome barriers to energy renovation of existing buildings," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 3939–3947, 2012.

Battista, G., de Lieto Vollaro, E., Ocloń, P., & de Lieto Vollaro, R., "Retrofit Analysis of a Historical Building in an Architectural Constrained Area: A Case Study in Rome, Italy," *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 12, no. 23, Art. no. 12305, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app122312305>

Berg, F., Flyen, A.-C., Godbolt, Å. L., & Broström, T., "User-driven energy efficiency in historic buildings: A review," *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, vol. 28, pp. 188–195, 2017.

Blomqvist, S., Glad, W., & Rohdin, P., "Ten years of energy efficiency—Exploring the progress of barriers and drivers in the Swedish residential and services sector," *Energy Reports*, 8, 14726–14740, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2022.10.439>

Blumstein, C., Krieg, B., Schipper, L., & York, C., "Overcoming social and institutional barriers to energy conservation," *Energy*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 355–371, Apr. 1980. Available: <https://escholarship.org/content/qt1bd54276/qt1bd54276.pdf?t=p21n7r>

Brooks, E., Law, A., & Huang, L., "A comparative analysis of retrofitting historic buildings for energy efficiency in the UK and China," *disP - The Planning Review*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 66–75, 2014. DOI: 10.1080/02513625.2014.979044.

Buda, A., de Place Hansen, E. J., Rieser, A., Giancola, E., Pracchi, V. N., Mauri, S., Marincioni, V., Gori, V., Fouseki, K., Polo López, C. S., Lo Faro, A., Egusquiza, A., Haas, F., Leonardj, E., & Herrera-Avellanosa, D., "Conservation-Compatible Retrofit Solutions in Historic Buildings: An Integrated Approach," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 2927, Mar. 2021. DOI: 10.3390/su13052927

Cagno, E., Worrell, E., Trianni, A., & Pugliese, G., "A novel approach for barriers to industrial energy efficiency," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 19, pp. 290-308, 2013. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2012.11.007

Caputo, P., & Pasetti, G., "Overcoming the inertia of building energy retrofit at municipal level: The Italian challenge," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 15, pp. 1-9, 2015. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2015.01.001>

Christiernsson, A., Geijer, M., & Malafry, M., "Legal Aspects on Cultural Values and Energy Efficiency in the Built Environment—A Sustainable Balance of Public Interests?" *Heritage* 2021,4,3507–3522. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage4040194>

Conticelli, E., Proli, S., & Tondelli, S., "Integrating energy efficiency and urban densification policies: Two Italian case studies," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 155, pp. 308-323, Nov. 15, 2017. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.09.036>

D'Oca, S., Ferrante, A., Ferrer, C., Perneti, R., Gralka, A., Sebastian, R., & Op 't Veld, P., "Technical, Financial, and Social Barriers and Challenges in Deep Building Renovation: Integration of Lessons Learned from the H2020 Cluster Projects," *Buildings*, vol. 8, no. 12, Art. no. 174, Dec. 2018. DOI: 10.3390/buildings8120174.

Department of Energy & Climate Change (DECC) and ENWORKS, "Research to Assess the Barriers and Drivers to Energy Efficiency in Small and Medium Sized Enterprises," Nov. 2014.

DiasPereira, L., Tavares, V., & Soares, N., "Up-To-Date Challenges for the Conservation, Rehabilitation and Energy Retrofitting of Higher Education Cultural Heritage Buildings," *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 2061. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042061>

Dixon-O'Mara, C., & Ryan, L., "Energy efficiency in the food retail sector: Barriers, drivers, and acceptable policies," UCD Centre for Economic Research Working Paper Series No. WP17/16, University College Dublin, UCD School of Economics, Dublin. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/184816>

Dogan Şahin, C., Durmus Arsan, Z., Tuncok, S. S., Broström, T., & Akkurt, G. G., "A transdisciplinary approach on the energy efficient retrofitting of a historic building in the Aegean Region of Turkey," in *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 96, pp. 128-139, 2015. DOI: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2015.03.018.

Dowson, M., Poole, A., Harrison, D., & Susman, G., "Domestic UK retrofit challenge: Barriers, incentives, and current performance leading into the Green Deal," *Energy Policy*, vol. 50, pp. 294-305, Oct. 2012, Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.07.019>

Du, P., Zheng, L.-Q., Xie, B.-C., & Mahalingam, A., "Barriers to the Adoption of Energy-Saving Technologies in the Building Sector: A Survey Study of Jing-jin-tang, China," *Energy Policy*, vol. 75, pp. 206-216, 2014. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2014.09.025

European Commission, "Commission Recommendation (EU) 2019/1019 of 7 June 2019 on Building Modernisation," *Official Journal of the European Union*, vol. L 165, pp. 70-128, Jun. 21, 2019. Available: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/2019/1019/oj>

European Commission, "Commission Welcomes Political Agreement on New Rules to Boost Energy Performance of Buildings Across the EU," *Press Release*, Brussels, Dec. 7, 2023. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_6423

European Commission, "Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Recast)," COM(2021) 802 final, 2021/0426(COD), Brussels, Dec. 15, 2021. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0802>

European Environment Agency, "Trends and Projections in Europe 2021," *EEA Report No 13/2021*, 2021. Available: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/trends-and-projections-in-europe-2021>

European Parliament and Council of the European Union, "Directive (EU) 2018/2002 of 11 December 2018 Amending Directive 2012/27/EU on Energy Efficiency," *Official Journal of the European Union*, vol. L 328, pp. 210-230, Dec. 21, 2018. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/2002/oj>

European Parliament and Council of the European Union, "Directive (EU) 2023/1791 of 13 September 2023 on Energy Efficiency and Amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (Recast)," *Official Journal of the European Union*, vol. L 231, pp. 1-111, Sep. 20, 2023. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/1791>

European Parliament and Council of the European Union, "Directive 2002/91/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2002 on the Energy Performance of Buildings," *Official Journal of the European Union*, vol. L 001, pp. 65-71, Jan. 4, 2003. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32002L0091>

European Parliament and Council of the European Union, "Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the Energy Performance of

Buildings (Recast)," Official Journal of the European Union, vol. L 153, pp. 13, Jun. 18, 2010. Available: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/31/2021-01-01>

European Parliament and Council of the European Union, "Directive 2012/27/EU of 25 October 2012 on Energy Efficiency, Amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EU and Repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC," Official Journal of the European Union, vol. L 315, pp. 1-56, Nov. 14, 2012. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:315:0001:0056:en:PDF>

Friedman, K., & Cooke, A., "Is UK Planning a barrier to energy efficient heritage retrofit: a comparative analysis of a selection of London Boroughs", Retrofit 2012 Conference, Salford, 24-26 January.

Galiano-Garrigós, A., González-Avilés, Á., Rizo-Maestre, C., & Andújar-Montoya, M. D., "Energy Efficiency and Economic Viability as Decision Factors in the Rehabilitation of Historic Buildings," Sustainability, vol. 11, no. 18, 4946, Sep. 2019. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11184946>

Galvin, R., "How occupant behavior can undermine a building's energy performance: A review of the literature," Energy Efficiency, 7(5), 857-870.

Galvin, R., & Sunikka-Blank, M., "Quantification of (p)rebound effects in retrofit policies – Why does it matter?" in Energy, vol. 95, pp. 415-424, 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2015.12.034

Garzulino, A., "Energy Efficiency: A Multi-Criteria Evaluation Method for the Intervention on Built Heritage," Sustainability, 12, 9223. doi:10.3390/su12219223

Galtung, J., Peace by Peaceful Means: Peace and Conflict, Development and Civilization. London: Sage, 1997, p. 72. Available: https://chesseyou.files.wordpress.com/2017/08/johan_galtung_peace_by_peaceful_means_peace_andbookzz-org.pdf

Glew, D. W., Smith, M., Miles-Shenton, D., & Gorse, C., "Assessing the quality of retrofits in solid wall dwellings," International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation. ISSN 2398-4708 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBPA-05-2017-0022>

Golove, W., & Eto, J., "Market Barriers to Energy Efficiency: A Critical Reappraisal of the Rationale for Public Policies to Promote Energy Efficiency," Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory. Available at: <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/5834r163>

Gruber, E., & Schleich, J., "Barriers to Energy Efficiency – An Econometric Analysis of Determinants," in Proceedings of the ECEEE 2003 Summer Study – Time to Turn Down Energy Demand, 2003, pp. 1033-1039

Gillingham, K., Newell, R. G., & Palmer, K., "Energy Efficiency Economics and Policy," NBER Working Paper No. 15031, National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge, MA, June 2009. Available: <http://www.nber.org/papers/w15031>

Herrera-Avellanosa, D., Haas, F., Leijonhufvud, G., Brostrom, T., Buda, A., Pracchi, V., Webb, A. L., Hüttler, W., & Troi, A., "The IEA-SHC Task 59 path towards the lowest possible energy demand and CO2 emissions," *International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 539-553, 2019. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBPA-12-2018-0102> (Listed twice, keep only one)

Howarth, R. B., & Andersson, B., "Market barriers to energy efficiency," *Energy Economics*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 262-272, Oct. 1993, Available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-9883\(93\)90016-K](https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-9883(93)90016-K)

Howlett, Michael, & Cashore, Professor Benjamin, "The Dependent Variable Problem in the Study of Policy Change: Understanding Policy Change as a Methodological Problem," *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, 11:1, 33-46, DOI: 10.1080/13876980802648144

Hirst, E., & Brown, M., "Closing the efficiency gap: barriers to the efficient use of energy," *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, vol. 3, pp. 267-281, 1990. Elsevier Science Publishers B.V./Pergamon Press plc. Available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0921-3449\(90\)90023-W](https://doi.org/10.1016/0921-3449(90)90023-W)

Hu, S., Yan, D., Azar, E., & Guo, F., "A systematic review of occupant behavior in building energy policy," *Building and Environment*, vol. 106807, 2020. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2020.106807>

Jaffe, A. B., & Stavins, R. N., "The energy-efficiency gap: What does it mean?" *Energy Policy*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 804-810, 1994. Available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-4215\(94\)90138-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-4215(94)90138-4)

Kangas, H.-L., Lazarevic, D., & Kivimaa, P., "Technical skills disinterest and non-functional regulation: Barriers to building energy efficiency in Finland viewed by energy service companies," *Energy Policy*, vol. 114, pp. 63–76, 2018. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2017.11.060

Kaveh, B., Mazhar, M. U., Simmonite, B., Sarshar, M., & Sertyesilisik, B., "An investigation into retrofitting the pre-1919 owner-occupied UK housing stock to reduce carbon emissions," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 174, pp. 62-77, 2018. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.06.038>

Kyritsi, E., Philokyprou, M., Kyriakidis, A., Michael, A., & Michopoulos, A., "Energy retrofitting of heritage buildings: an integrated methodology," in *IOP Conf. Series: Earth*

and Environmental Science, vol. 1196, no. 1, 012108, 2023, doi:10.1088/1755-1315/1196/1/012108.

Legnér, M., & Leijonhufvud, G., "A Legacy of Energy Saving: The Discussion on Heritage Values in the First Programme on Energy Efficiency in Buildings in Sweden c. 1974–1984," *The Historic Environment: Policy & Practice*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 40-57, 2019, doi: 10.1080/17567505.2018.1531646.

Lidelöw, S., Örn, T., Luciani, A., & Rizzo, A., "Energy-efficiency measures for heritage buildings: A literature review," in *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 45, pp. 231-242, 2019. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2018.09.029>

Litti, G., Audenaert, A., & Braet, J., "Energy Retrofitting in Architectural Heritage: Possible Risks Due to the Missing of a Specific Legislative and Methodological Protocol," in *Proc. of The European Conference on Sustainability, Energy & the Environment 2013*, 2013.

Lucchi, E., "Renewable Energies and Architectural Heritage: Advanced Solutions and Future Perspectives," in *Buildings*, vol. 13, no. 631, pp. 1-26, 2023. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13030631>

Lutzenhiser, L., "A cultural model of household energy consumption," *Energy*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 47-60, Jan. 1992. Available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-5442\(92\)90032-U](https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-5442(92)90032-U)

Marincioni, V., Gori, V., de Place Hansen, E.J., Herrera-Avellanosa, D., Mauri, S., Giancola, E., Egusquiza, A., Buda, A., Leonardi, E., & Rieser, A., "How Can Scientific Literature Support Decision-Making in the Renovation of Historic Buildings? An Evidence-Based Approach for Improving the Performance of Walls," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 2266, 2021. DOI: 10.3390/su13042266

Marquez, L., McGregor, J., & Syme, M., "Barriers to the Adoption of Energy Efficiency Measures for Existing Commercial Buildings," April 2015. Available: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.1963.9847>

Mata, É., Peñaloza, D., Sandkvist, F., & Nyberg, T., "What is stopping low-carbon buildings? A global review of enablers and barriers," *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.erss.2021.102261.

May, P. J., "Compliance motivations: Affirmative and negative bases," *Law & Soc. Rev.*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 41–68, Mar. 2004, doi: 10.1111/j.0023-9216.2004.03801002.x.

Melvin, J., "The split incentives energy efficiency problem: Evidence of underinvestment by landlords," *Energy Policy*. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.11.069>

Nagesha, N., & Balachandra, P., "Barriers to energy efficiency in small industry clusters: Multi-criteria-based prioritization using the analytic hierarchy process," *Energy*, vol. 31, no. 12, pp. 1969–1983, 2006. Available: [10.1016/j.energy.2005.07.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2005.07.002).

Nair, G., Gustavsson, L., & Mahapatra, K., "Barriers to Implement Energy Efficiency Investment Measures in Swedish Co-Operative Apartment Buildings," in *World Renewable Energy Congress - Sweden, Linköping, Sweden, 8-13 May 2011, Linköping Electronic Conference Proceedings*, vol. 57, no. 47, pp. 1110-1117, Nov. 2011. DOI: [10.3384/ecp110571110](https://doi.org/10.3384/ecp110571110).

Nair, G., Verde, L., & Olofsson, T., "A Review on Technical Challenges and Possibilities on Energy Efficient Retrofit Measures in Heritage Buildings," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 20, Art. no. 7472, Oct. 2022, doi: [10.3390/en15207472](https://doi.org/10.3390/en15207472)

Paiho, S., & Ahvenniemi, H., "Non-Technical Barriers to Energy Efficient Renovation of Residential Buildings and Potential Policy Instruments to Overcome Them—Evidence from Young Russian Adults," in *Buildings*, vol. 7, no. 4, p. 101, October 2017, doi:[10.3390/buildings7040101](https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings7040101).

Palm, J., & Bryngelson, E., "Energy efficiency at building sites: barriers and drivers," *Energy Efficiency*, vol. 16, no. 7, 2023. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12053-023-10088-7>

Pino, J. M., "The New Holistic Paradigm and the Sustainability of Historic Cities in Spain: An Approach Based on the World Heritage Cities," *Sustainability*, vol. 10, no. 7, p. 2301, Jul. 2018, doi: [10.3390/su10072301](https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072301).

Polo López, C.S.; Lucchi, E.; Leonardi, E.; Durante, A.; Schmidt, A.; Curtis, R., "Risk-Benefit Assessment Scheme for Renewable Solar Solutions in Traditional and Historic Buildings," *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 5246. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095246>

Polo López, C.S., & Frontini, F., "Energy efficiency and renewable solar energy integration in heritage historic buildings," in *Energy Procedia*, vol. 48, pp. 1493-1502, 2014.

Rispoli, M., & Organ, S., "The drivers and challenges of improving the energy efficiency performance of listed pre-1919 housing," in *International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 288-305, 2019, doi: [10.1108/IJBPA-09-2017-0037](https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBPA-09-2017-0037).

Sáez-Pérez, M. P., García Ruiz, L. M., Durán-Suárez, J. A., Castro-Gomes, J., Martínez-Ramírez, A., & Villegas-Broncano, M. Á., "Comparative Analysis of Thermal Behavior in Different Seasons in Building Heritage: Case Study of the Royal Hospital of Granada," *Buildings*, vol. 13, no. 12, pp. 3048, Dec. 2023, doi: [10.3390/buildings13123048](https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13123048).

Santangelo, A., & Tondelli, S., "Occupant behaviour and building renovation of the social housing stock: Current and future challenges," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 145, pp. 276-283, Jun. 15, 2017. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.04.019>

Schleich, J., "Barriers to energy efficiency: A comparison across the German commercial and services sector," *Ecological Economics*, 2009. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2009.02.008>

Schleich, J., "The economics of energy efficiency: Barriers to profitable investments," *EIB Papers*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 82-109, 2007.

Sorrell, S., O'Malley, E., Schleich, J., & Scott, S., "The Economics of Energy Efficiency: Barriers to Cost-Effective Investment," *Fraunhofer ISI*, Jan. 2004. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/43185108_The_Economics_of_Energy_Efficiency_Barriers_to_Cost-Effective_Investment

Stephenson, J., Barton, B., Carrington, G., Gnoth, D., Lawson, R., & Thorsnes, P., "Energy cultures: A framework for understanding energy behaviours," *Energy Policy*, vol. 38, no. 10, pp. 6120-6129, Oct. 2010. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.05.069>

Sudhakara Reddy, B., "Barriers and drivers to energy efficiency – A new taxonomical approach," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 74, 2013, pp. 403-416, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2013.06.040.

Thollander, P., Palm, J., & Rohdin, P., "Categorizing Barriers to Energy Efficiency – an Interdisciplinary Perspective," in *Energy Efficiency*, August 2010, Available: <https://www.intechopen.com/sections/11463>. (Listed twice, keep only one)

Trianni, A., Cagno, E., & Farné, S., "Barriers, Drivers, and Decision-making Process for Industrial Energy Efficiency: A Broad Study Among Manufacturing Small and Medium-sized Enterprises," *Applied Energy*, vol. 161, pp. 718-730, 2014. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.02.078>

Tuominen, P., Klobut, K., Tolman, A., Adjei, A., & de Best-Waldhober, M., "Energy savings potential in buildings and overcoming market barriers in member states of the European Union," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 49, pp. 22-28, 2012. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2012.04.015>

Ulu, M., & Arsan, Z.D., "Deep renovation of historic buildings: Retrofit strategies for energy efficiency of historic urban fabric in Mediterranean climate," *Atmosphere*. 2020;11(7):742. doi:10.3390/atmos11070742

Vallati, A., Di Matteo, M., & Fiorini, C.V., "Retrofit Proposals for Energy Efficiency and Thermal Comfort in Historic Public Buildings: The Case of the Engineering Faculty's Seat of Sapienza University," *Energies* 2023,16,151. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16010151>

Vadodaria, K., Loveday, D., Haines, V., Mitchell, V., & Bayer, S., "UK solid-wall dwellings: Thermal comfort, energy efficiency refurbishment and the user perspective - Some preliminary analysis from the CALEBRE project," *Adapting to Change: New Thinking on Comfort*. Cumberland Lodge, Windsor, UK, 9–11 April 2010. London: Network for Comfort and Energy Use in Buildings, 1–16

Vesely, A., "Theory and Methodology of Best Practice Research: A Critical Review of the Current State", *Cent. Eur. J. Public Policy* 2011, 2, 98–117.

Weber, L., "Some reflections on barriers to the efficient use of energy," *Energy Policy*, vol. 25, no. 10, pp. 833-835, Aug. 1997. Available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-4215\(97\)00084-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-4215(97)00084-0)

Weiss, J., Dunkelberg, E., & Vogelpohl, T., "Improving policy instruments to better tap into homeowner refurbishment potential: Lessons learned from a case study in Germany," *Energy Policy*, vol. 44, pp. 406-415, 2012. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2012.02.006

Yazdani Mehr, S., & Wilkinson, S., "Technical issues and energy efficient adaptive reuse of heritage listed city halls in Queensland, Australia," *International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation*, 36(5), 529-542. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBPA-02-2018-0020>

Zhang, Y., & Wang, Y., "Barriers' and policies' analysis of China's building energy efficiency," *Energy Policy*, vol. 62, pp. 768-773, 2013. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2013.06.128

Zuhaib, S., Manton, R., Hajdukiewicz, M., Keane, M. M., & Goggins, J., "Attitudes and approaches of Irish retrofit industry professionals towards achieving nearly zero-energy buildings," *Int. J. of Building Pathology and Adaptation*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 16-40, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.1108/IJBPA-07-2016-0015.

9. Annexes

ANNEX 1 – TAXONOMY OF BARRIERS TO ENRGY EFFICIENCY OF HERITAGE BUILDINGS

<p>TECHNICAL BARRIERS</p>	<p>T1. Competence-Dependent Technology Complexity and Skilled Workforce Shortage: A notable lack of expertise among professionals involved in retrofits, impacting coordination and decision-making while the high specialization required for the design, installation, and maintenance of the energy systems</p>	<p>T2. Structural constrains and Complexity in Conservation-Compatible Retrofit Solutions: The initial design limitations, old and fragile building's structures, heritage elements, space constrains and diverse building typologies restrict the options for effective energy performance improvements</p>	<p>T3. No One-Fits-All Solutions: The necessity for individually tailored energy-efficiency measures arises from the diverse characteristics of historical buildings, encompassing variations in age, typology, function, location, and occupancy patterns, potentially introducing disruptions to the construction process.</p>	<p>T4. Demand for Costly and Scarce Heritage-Compatible Materials: The challenge of selecting materials that not only meet high thermal performance and low-cost criteria but also ensure mechanical, physical, and chemical compatibility between original and retrofitting materials, thus addressing the long-term preservation concerns in addition to energy-saving goals</p>	
<p>LEGISLATIVE AND REGULATORY BARRIERS</p>	<p>L1. Lack of policy coherence and Protocol Deficiency: The absence of consistent and specific regulations, standards, and protocols at various levels (regional, national, and European) for improving energy performance in cultural built heritage conservation. This deficiency is particularly notable during the retrofit planning phase, hindering the establishment of compulsory standards or targets and creating challenges in aligning national legislation with European directives, resulting in ambiguity regarding definitions, regulations,</p>	<p>L2. Bureaucratic Hurdles: Regulatory Approvals and planning permissions regime: The criteria set by local planning authorities may lag behind technical innovations, due to potential conflicts with outdated regulations, varied approval processes, and increased permitting costs</p>	<p>L3. Preservation Regulations Safeguarding Historical, Sociocultural, and Architectural Values: The challenge posed by the belief that implementing energy-efficient technologies might compromise or jeopardize the cultural value of heritage buildings leading to the regulatory frameworks aimed at preserving the cultural and architectural significance of heritage structures, which may hinder the implementation of retrofit solutions necessary for meeting contemporary energy performance standards, particularly in cases where high</p>	<p>L4. Insufficient support and guidance: The lack of adequate assistance and clear directives from local government and regulatory authorities, hindering stakeholders from implementing modern and energy effective measures</p>	

	and effective energy measures for historical buildings.		levels of legal protection are in place.		
ECONOMIC BARRIERS	E1. Investment playback time: The duration required for the return on energy efficiency investments	E2. Hidden costs: Expenses associated with information-seeking, contract negotiation, systems' maintenance and other activities, potentially inhibiting cost-effective measures when included in the overall investment assessment	E3. High upfront costs: The costs associated with energy-efficient technologies can be higher, involving a significant initial financial investment, making them less appealing compared to alternative, conventional options	E4. Scarcity and limited access to Public Financial Support: Financial constraints, compounded by limited access to credit and challenges in securing external financing	E5. Split incentive: A situation where the entity responsible for making energy-efficient investments is not the same as the one bearing the cost of energy consumption, creating a disconnect in incentives for adopting energy-saving measures
ENVIRONMENTAL BARRIERS	EN1. Installation-related impacts, including noise, drilling vibrations, waste, and pollution leakage: These include aspects such as drilling operations, potential challenges in securing fuel and materials, waste removal concerns, and the necessity for effective management of environmental disruptions in the proximity of residents and other stakeholders	EN2. Long-term visual and landscape impacts: Enduring effects on the visual aesthetics and overall landscape character, particularly during construction and operation phases	EN3. System Inefficiency Impact on Carbon Footprint: Innovative energy-efficient systems may experience reduced efficiency due to constraints in existing structures, leading to higher power consumption and elevated CO2 emissions compared to new buildings with higher system efficiency. This is particularly pronounced in older buildings with poor insulation, single-glazed windows, and diverse building typologies that predate energy consumption regulations, presenting challenges for internal and external wall insulation and contributing to substantial heat loss.		

<p>SOCIAL BARRIERS</p>	<p>S1. Lack of awareness or interest stemming from insufficient or asymmetric information: The challenge in determining where to start and which measures to prioritize due to informational barriers. The challenge is further exacerbated by the misconception that the success of energy-efficient technologies or systems is unproven, leading to a general lack of social interest in such projects.</p>	<p>S2. Absence of consensus among various stakeholders: Divergent values and interests among owners, building professionals, and local communities involved in the retrofit process, that can lead to tensions or synergies in decision-making</p>	<p>S3. General reluctance to depart from conventional systems and traditional materials: Expressing a mindset ingrained in conservatism, stakeholders commonly exhibit a hesitancy to depart from the use of conventional systems and traditional materials typically employed in construction industry .</p>	<p>S4. Hesitancy to disrupt the regular operation during site works and/or relocate: The reluctance or hesitancy among stakeholders to interfere with the normal functioning of these buildings during construction/installation activities, which may arise from concerns about the potential impact on daily operations, exhibits, or residents relocation, etc.</p>	
-------------------------------	--	---	--	---	--

ANNEX 2 –ADDITIONAL BARRIERS IDENTIFIED THROUGH SURVEY

NN	ADDED BARRIERS FROM THE SURVEY	ASSIGNED CATEGORY	COUNTRY	COMMENT
1.	Regulatory updates (<i>original: Adeguamenti normativi (rilevante - proprietario/gestore - fase 1)</i>)	Technical	Italy	Should be assigned to Legal barriers
2.	Cold climate, ice and snow. Necessity of insulation, normally done from outside, but with heritage buildings should be conducted from the interior - thus condensation problems, etc.	Technical	Estonia	Corresponds to EN3
3.	Impact of the technological solution on the landscape (<i>original: Impatto della soluzione tecnologica nel paesaggio (attore più sfidato: proprietario del patrimonio, occupante del patrimonio, intermediari di consulenza, finanziatori- FASE: Fase 1: preparazione e orientamento)</i>)	Technical	Italy	Corresponds to EN2
4.	Impact of the technological solution on the typological-structural conservation of the historic building (<i>original: impatto della soluzione tecnologica nella conservazione tipologico-strutturale dell'edificio storico (attore più sfidato: proprietario del patrimonio, occupante del patrimonio, intermediari di consulenza, finanziatori- FASE: Fase 2: progettazione del modello e analisi dettagliata)</i>)	Technical	Italy	Corresponds to L3
5.	Lack of financing	Technical	Estonia	Corresponds to E4
6.	Lack of HBIM models/data and/or other heritage parametric data that enables for renovation solutions' analyses and simulation (Relevant - Heritage Owners, Advisory intermediaries - Phase 1)	Technical	Spain	
7.	Heritage protection laws. They are not effective in terms of energy renovation and greatly hinder the processes, Very relevant Challenged actors: Owners, occupants, operators, advisors, regulators Most affected phase: Phase 1 (<i>original: Leyes de protección del patrimonio. No son efectivas en cuanto a la renovación energética y dificultan mucho los procesos.Relevancia: Muy relevante Actores desafiados: Propietarios, ocupantes, operadores, asesores, regladores Fase más afectada: Fase 1)</i>)	Technical	Spain	Corresponds to L3
8.	Owners and tenants as they may refuse the implementation of case best solutions, Phase 3 - Prioritization and decision, relevance high,	Technical	Poland	Corresponds to S3

9.	Conservation limitations (challenged actors: conservation authorities, which prefer restrict obligations, conservation approach towards the protected structure, which unfortunately do not include inclusive approach to provide access and use the protected structure)	Technical	Poland	Corresponds to L3
10.	Limited knowledge of the owner/occupant of a heritage conservation building (relevant - advisory intermediaries/advisory bodies/regulatory authorities - phase 1/2/3) <i>(original: muinsuskaitsealuse hoone omaniku/elaniku vähesed teadmised. (asjakohane - nõuandvad vahendajad/nõuandvad organid/reguleerivad asutused - faas 1/2/3))</i>	Technical	Estonia	Corresponds to S1
11.	Not thinking in bigger picture to create the grid of systems and energy solutions that can be useful in the whole concept as all (i.e. at university campus in which every building can use the most effective solutions for given plot - sustainable city /plot /quater is something more then set of sustainable buildings it is a sustainable organism) - Problems can be visible in phase 1 (if you don't have enough knowledge to create the grid) but during the implementation it will be phase 3 (who will make a decision that this plot/building should focus on this type of solutions, where will be energy magazines placed on the plots, who will be the owner etc.)	Technical	Poland	
12.	The limitation of technical solutions results from the low awareness of contemporary challenges in offices responsible for protecting heritage.	Technical	Poland	Corresponds to S1
13.	Restrictions imposed by the Heritage Authority - Mainly involving the project designers - I would add a Phase 5 Design of interventions. All barriers T1...T4 are in the phase 5 of design, except for barrier T1, which will concern the construction phase. In the phases preceding the design, the above barriers are hardly considered because the problems - and their solutions - emerge during the design phase and not in the decision-making or planning phase <i>(original: Vincoli imposti dalla Sovrintendenza - Coinvolti soprattutto i progettisti dell'opera - Aggiungerei una Fase 5 Progettazione degli interventi. Tutte le barriere T1...T4 sono nella fase 5 di progettazione, ad eccezione della barriera T1 che riguarderà la fase di cantiere. Nelle fasi precedenti alla progettazione, difficilmente si tiene conto delle barriere di cui sopra poiché i problemi - e relative soluzioni - emergono in fase di progettazione e non in fase decisoria o di pianificazione.)</i>	Technical	Italy	Corresponds to L2
14.	The contradiction between the construction code and heritage conservation regulations. The former	Legal	Estonia	

	prescribes and plans for the replacement/modernization of authentic structures, while the latter mandates the preservation of the authenticity of authentic structures and buildings. (<i>original: Ehitusseadustiku ja muinsuskaitse alaste regulatsioonide vastuolulisus. Esimene näeb ette ja programmeerib autentsete tarindite asendamise/kaasajastamise, teine seab ülesandeks autentsete tarindite ja hoonestuse autentsuse säilimise.</i>)			
15	No regulations at the University level how to follow a procedure for reconstruction and changes - show what is the main gist and main goals which should be achieved. Phase 3	Legal	Poland	
16	Procedures needed to buy materials and make a payment after work done. Phase 4 / Phase 3	Legal	Poland	
17	Fragmented decision-making, divided responsibility. Phase 3.	Legal	Poland	Corresponds to S4
18	Land/house ownership questions and border changing - when border is aligned with old wall surface (Relevant - Heritage owners - Phase 2)	Legal	Estonia	
19	Procedures needed to buy materials and make a payment after work done. Phase 4 / Phase 3	Economic	Poland	Repetition (see 16)
20	Owners with low income (Very relevant - Owners - Phase 1)	Economic	Estonia	Corresponds to E3
21	High number of owners of same house with different income levels (Very relevant - Owners - Phase 1)	Economic	Estonia	Corresponds to S2
22	Low property value areas - rural, villages, far from economic centers (Relevant - Owners, Financiers - Phase 1)	Economic	Estonia	
23	Creating chains in circular economy solutions. Phase 3	Environmental	Poland	
24	Impact on biodiversity. Phase 4	Environmental	Poland	
25	Existence of local bio-habitats - Phase 1 - Preparation and orientation - major impact urban water retention - Phase 1 - Preparation and orientation - major impact	Environmental	Poland	
26	Recycling of technologies and materials used for energy efficiency at the end of life (Relevance: Relevant. Most challenged actor: Installer, Supplier, Advisory Intermediary, PHASE: phase 3) (<i>Original: Riciclo delle tecnologie e dei materiali utilizzati per l'efficientamento energetico a fine vita (Rilevanza: Rilevante. Attore più sfidato: Installatore, Fornitore, intermediario di consulenza, FASE: fase 3)</i>)	Environmental	Italy	
27	All barriers must be analyzed and resolved in phase 5, the design phase. Often, such issues emerge - and therefore need to be resolved - during the	Environmental	Italy	

	<p>implementation phase (phase 6) or the operation phase (phase 7) (<i>Original: Tutte le barriere vanno analizzate e risolte in fase 5, di progettazione. Spesso, tali problemi emergono - e quindi vanno risolti - in fase di realizzazione (fase 6) o di esercizio (fase 7)</i>)</p>			
28	<p>The benefits of environmentally friendly solutions (especially passive) are not sufficiently presented in a way that is affordable and accessible to the socio-economic environment Phase 4 or even 5 - evolution and information about action</p>	Social	Poland	

